

Camp Navajo
Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
Bellemont, Arizona

June 2020

Submitted To:

Arizona Army National Guard
Department of Emergency and Military Affairs
Environmental Office
5636 East McDowell Road
Phoenix, Arizona 85008

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CAMP NAVAJO
INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
BELLEMONT, ARIZONA

The Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan meets the requirements of the Sikes Act (16 United States Code §670(a) *et seq.*, as amended). This plan has set appropriate and adequate guidelines for conserving and protecting the natural resources of Camp Navajo.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ACUB	Army Compatible Use Buffer	EA	Environmental Assessment
ADEQ	Arizona Department of Environmental Quality	EMO	Environmental Management Office
AGFD	Arizona Game and Fish Department	EMU	Ecological Management Unit
AMSL	Above mean sea level	EO	Executive Order
ANPL	Arizona Native Plant Law	EOD	Explosive Ordnance Disposal
AR	Army Regulation	EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ARNG I&E	Army National Guard's Installation and Environment Directorate	EPM	Environmental Program Manager
ARNG-TRS	Army National Guard's director of operations, training, and readiness	ESA	Endangered Species Act
ASLD	Arizona State Land Department	FMO	Facilities Management Office
ASA	Ammunition Storage Area	HS	Highly Safeguarded
AZDEMA	Arizona Department of Emergency and Military Affairs	I-40	Interstate 40
AZARNG	Arizona Army National Guard	INRMP	Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
BGEPA	Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act	IPA	Intergovernmental Personnel Act of 1972
bgs	Below ground surface	IPMP	Integrated Pest Management Plan
BMP	Best Management Practice	ITAM	Integrated Training Area Management
BNSF	Burlington-Northern/Santa Fe	IWFMP	Integrated Wildland Fire Management Plan
BO	Biological Opinion	LT	Listed Threatened
BRAC	Base Realignment and Closure	M16	5.56-millimeter Semiautomatic Rifle
CFMO	Construction and Facilities Management Office	M203	40-millimeter Grenade Launcher on M16
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations	MBTA	Migratory Bird Treaty Act
CWA	Clean Water Act	MEC	Munitions and Explosives of Concern
DA	Department of Army		
DESCOM	Army Depot System Command		
DoD	Department of Defense		

MOU	Memorandum of Understanding	RTLA	Range and Training Land Assessment
MP	Military Police	SAIA	Sikes Act Improvement Act
MSO	Mexican Spotted Owl	SC	Species of Concern
N/A	Not Available	SDWA	Safe Drinking Water Act
NADA	Navajo Army Depot Activity	SGCN	Species of greatest conservation need
NAGPRA	Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act	SHPO	State Historic Preservation Office
NAU	Northern Arizona University	SPCCP	Spill Prevention Control and Countermeasure Plan
NBA	New Breeding Area	SR	Salvage Restricted
NDAA	National Defense Authorization Act	SRP	Sustainable Range Program
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act	STEP	Status Tool for the Environmental Program
NGB	National Guard Bureau	SWBEMC	Southwestern Bald Eagle Management Committee
NHPA	National Historic Preservation Act	SWMU MRWA	Solid Waste Management Unit Munitions Response Work Area
NOD	Navajo Ordinance Depot	TAG	The Adjutant General
NRCS	Natural Resources Conservation Service	UGM	Upper Gila Management Zone
NRM	Natural resources manager	USACE	United States Army Corps of Engineers
OB/OD	Open Burn/Open Detonation	USC	United States Code
OHV	Off-Highway Vehicle	USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
PAC	Protected Activity Center	USFS	United States Forest Service
PCPA	Post-closure Permit Area	USFWS	United States Fish and Wildlife Service
PFA	Post-Fledging Family Area	UXO	Unexploded ordnance
PIF	Partners in Flight	WOTUS	Waters of the United States
PM _{2.5}	Particulate Matter less than 2.5 microns in diameter		
POTO	Plans, operations, and training officer		
RCMP	Range Complex Master Plan		

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SECTION 1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The mission of Arizona Garrison Training Center is to command, operate, manage, and administer the use of resources of the Level III Training Center to accomplish assigned missions. The mission includes providing year-round service through administrative, engineering, logistical, training, and operational support to assigned, attached, or transient (support component) units and joint forces for multiple battalions. The vision is to maximize the capability, availability, and accessibility to Ranges and Training Lands to support doctrinal requirements, mobilization, and deployments under normal and surge conditions. The Camp Navajo Training Site (Camp Navajo) mission statement is “to operate a training site and storage facility at Bellemont, Arizona.” To achieve this mission, Camp Navajo focuses on three essential areas:

- 1) The operation of a National Guard training site for troops and units, including transportation, engineering, Military Police (MP), aviation, ordnance, medical quartermaster, and related units.
- 2) The provision of depot-level storage services to sustain and maintain the military readiness of various Department of Defense (DoD) agencies and civilian customers.
- 3) The provision of command and control for the Arizona Army National Guard (AZARNG) force structure in Arizona.

The AZARNG is committed to providing sound environmental stewardship, providing continuous improvement and compliance to regulatory and other requirements, conserving its natural resources, preventing pollution or contamination, gaining the support of the communities in which its staff work and live, and incorporating professionalism and environmental planning into all that they do.

Camp Navajo is located in north-central Arizona, 12 miles west of Flagstaff, 17 miles east of Williams, and adjacent to the small community of Bellemont located along Interstate 40 (I-40). A large portion of the land surrounding Camp Navajo is undeveloped and managed by the United States Forest Service (USFS), and Arizona State Land Department (ASLD), (the Kaibab and Coconino National Forest lands being the predominant land managers). Camp Navajo provides a variety of environmental conditions and ecosystems in which to train Soldiers. This training objective must be met in a way that provides for sustainable, healthy ecosystems; complies with applicable environmental laws and regulations; and ensures no net loss in the capability of military installation lands to support the military mission. Integrated Natural Resources Management Plans (INRMPs) help installation commanders manage natural resources more effectively, ensuring that installation lands remain available and in good condition to continually support the military mission. The purpose of this INRMP is to outline the AZARNG plan to maximize training opportunities available at Camp Navajo while managing and preserving the natural resources on the installation by complying with environmental laws and regulations, primarily those related to threatened and endangered species.

Natural resource management within the installation includes specific objectives detailed in the Sikes Act Improvement Amendments of 1997 (16 United States Code [USC] § 670[a] *et. seq.*) (SAIA) and management programs that ensure conservation and restoration of natural resources and compliance with applicable regulations. SAIA established the federal requirement for creating INRMPs. The scope of this document is the integration and coordination of all external and internal activities at Camp Navajo that affect or may affect natural resources. In the event that significant changes in proposed activities

42 occur or new activities are planned, the INRMP will be updated to reflect these actions and their effects
43 on the environment. The current INRMP (2019) will be reviewed under the standards set by DoD
44 Instruction 4715.03. Using principles of ecosystem management, Camp Navajo has developed
45 partnerships with various federal and state agencies to support management of its natural resources.
46 AZARNG will continue to consult with these agencies regarding current and future actions that may
47 affect natural and wildlife resources at Camp Navajo.

48 Major partners in implementing this plan are the United States Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and
49 Arizona Game and Fish Department (AGFD). USFWS and AGFD are required to cooperate in preparation
50 of the INRMP under the Sikes Act, amended under the SAIA. Other partners include DoD agencies,
51 federal and state agencies, universities, contractors, and private citizens. An interdisciplinary approach
52 to collect information about the management of natural resources at Camp Navajo has and will continue
53 to be gathered from the AZARNG Environmental Management Office (EMO) through partnerships and
54 various collaborators mentioned above. In addition, the public will be provided an opportunity to
55 comment on the INRMP during a 30-day public comment period. A distribution list for the draft INRMP
56 as well as initial agency and Tribal coordination and response letters are included in **Appendix C** as well
57 as the Administrative Record, which is available at the EMO at Camp Navajo.

58 **1.2 BENEFITS**

59 Implementation of the INRMP will improve the quality of training land and enhance mission readiness
60 by providing more opportunities for training. The INRMP will also improve the military's ability for long-
61 range planning at Camp Navajo. Such planning may decrease long-term environmental costs and reduce
62 personal and installation liabilities from environmental noncompliance of environmental regulation.
63 Implementation of this INRMP will benefit the installation and the surrounding community by improving
64 forest resiliency and increasing the environmental awareness.

65 The INRMP provides the basis for ecosystem management and the protection of natural resources,
66 including biodiversity within the installation. Implementation of this plan will increase overall knowledge
67 of Camp Navajo's natural resources through surveys, research, and outreach programs.

68 **1.3 PRIMARY NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT GOALS**

69 The primary purpose of Camp Navajo is to support the military missions of the AZARNG. The design of
70 the INRMP supports and accommodates accomplishment of military missions while providing for
71 scientifically sound natural resources stewardship. Specific installation management goals identified by
72 the INRMP (Section 8) are as follows:

- 73 • Manage forests to sustain military readiness and improve the diversity of conditions available
74 for units and Soldier training;
- 75 • Minimize disruptions in Soldier training by protecting training lands from large-scale
76 disturbances (such as catastrophic wildfires and bark beetle infestation);
- 77 • Restore forest resiliency, function, and historic forest structure, pattern, and composition.
78 Resiliency increases the ability of the forest to survive natural disturbances such as insects,
79 disease, fire, and climate change;

- 80 • Restore resiliency and function to grassland and meadows which provide important training
81 conditions and habitat for many wildlife species. Maintain, monitor, restore, and manage water
82 resources for plants and wildlife;
- 83 • Restore fire to its natural role in the ecosystem to sustain and/or enhance military training
84 lands;
- 85 • Protect and sustain native plant communities;
- 86 • Protect vegetation communities from non-native, invasive species;
- 87 • Manage Mexican spotted owl (MSO) (*Strix occidentalis lucida*) and bald eagle (*Haliaeetus*
88 *leucocephalus*). Monitor and study other raptor species and migratory birds;
- 89 • Manage habitat for small mammals, herpetofauna, invertebrates, and game animals;
- 90 • Implement the Integrated Pest Management Plan (IPMP) (**Appendix M**);
- 91 • Maintain or enhance soil productivity;
- 92 • Protect soils to prevent erosion;
- 93 • Enforce wildlife and natural resource laws to best manage, maintain, and protect resources;
- 94 • Inform troops and the public about natural resources stewardship efforts.

95 These goals are supported in the INRMP by objectives and projects, which provide management
96 strategies and specific actions to achieve these goals. A detailed discussion of goals and objectives can
97 be found in Section 8 of this INRMP and in **Appendix G**. These goals will ensure the success of the
98 military mission and the conservation of natural resources. The general philosophies and methodologies
99 used throughout the Camp Navajo Natural Resources Management Program focus on conducting
100 required military training while maintaining ecosystem viability.

101 **1.4 IMPLEMENTATION AND EFFECTIVENESS**

102 This INRMP provides a description of the installation (e.g., location, history, and mission), information
103 regarding the on-site and adjacent physical and biotic environment, and an assessment of the
104 anticipated impacts of mission activities on natural resources. The INRMP includes recommendations for
105 various management practices designed to enhance the natural resource base and proactively mitigate
106 anticipated negative impacts that may result through the successful execution of the military mission at
107 Camp Navajo.

108 Existing cultural resources at Camp Navajo are referenced within the context of established
109 management protocols to ensure the compatibility of this document. Additionally, this INRMP presents
110 methods that will increase the environmental awareness of AZARNG personnel, guest units using Camp
111 Navajo for training, and the general public. The implementation of this INRMP at Camp Navajo will
112 ensure the continued success and accomplishment of Camp Navajo's military mission while providing for
113 multiple uses of natural resources and promoting adaptive stewardship practices that sustain ecosystem
114 and biological integrity.

115 This document complies with applicable Army and DoD policies as well as applicable federal, state, and
116 local mandates. AZARNG will actively cooperate with federal, state, and local organizations to carry out
117 national land use and conservation policies to the extent practicable and in concert with the assigned
118 mission.

119 The EMO will coordinate the implementation of the INRMP and compliance with regulations throughout
120 the installation. An annual review will be conducted each fiscal year by AZARNG in cooperation with
121 USFWS and AGFD to report the progress and effectiveness of the INRMP. The INRMP is a “living”
122 document that will be continually refined as management actions are implemented, as goals and
123 objectives are met, and to address changes in mission and training requirements at Camp Navajo.

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SECTION 2 OVERVIEW GENERAL INFORMATION, COMPLIANCE, INTEGRATION, AND RESPONSIBILITIES

2.1 PURPOSE

This INRMP is a revision of the 2002 to 2006 INRMP for Camp Navajo. The INRMP is used by the National Guard Bureau (NGB), and the AZARNG as the primary tool for managing natural resources at Camp Navajo. The reasons for the INRMP revision include 1) incorporating integrated wildland fire management, 2) incorporating forest treatments, and 3) collecting updated resource information.

Updates to this INRMP experienced many delays throughout the years. During updates in 2012, Camp Navajo's proposed forest treatments were incorporated into a Maneuver Training Center Lite Environmental Assessment (EA) for range construction instead of the Camp Navajo INRMP EA, causing delays in the process. Also in 2012, breeding MSO were detected within the area of the Proposed Action, necessitating an amendment to the Biological Opinion (BO) and prior EA, further delaying proceedings. When reviewed in September 2015, NGB suggested the forest treatments be removed from the prior EA and analyzed under the current INRMP EA (**Appendix B**). This INRMP contains the revisions necessary and describes the current ways in which Camp Navajo manages its resources.

The purpose of the INRMP is to develop a plan that integrates natural resources management with the military mission. Camp Navajo must provide a variety of environmental conditions and ecosystems in which to train Soldiers. This objective must be met in a way that provides for sustainable, healthy ecosystems; complies with all applicable environmental laws and regulations; and provides for no net loss in the capability of military installation lands to support the military mission on the installation. An INRMP helps installation commanders manage natural resources more effectively to ensure installation lands remain available and in good condition to support the military mission. It also must be prepared in cooperation and mutual agreement with the USFWS and AGFD. This INRMP provides a comprehensive approach to ecosystem management on Camp Navajo.

The purpose of Camp Navajo's INRMP is to:

- Support training by fulfilling a variety of natural resources management needs on Camp Navajo;
- Describe Camp Navajo's natural resources and incorporate natural resources management plans into one cohesive document;
- Integrate land use carrying capacities with ecosystem management to conserve and preserve natural and cultural resources so they will be available for use by present and future generations;
- Ensure compliance with applicable federal and state laws, acts, and regulations, including the SAIA and the Endangered Species Act (ESA);
- Establish lines of communication between agencies to facilitate ecosystem management;
- Identify species, areas, and ecosystems that are unique, sensitive to disturbance, or in need of special consideration and then provide a plan for protection of these species, areas, and ecosystems;
- Identify natural resources information needs and provide methods to fulfill them (e.g., surveys and studies);

- 40 • Achieve no net loss in the capability of military installation lands to support the military mission;
41 and
- 42 • Facilitate the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) process.

43 The AZARNG recognizes that its on-going and proposed training activities can potentially use or
44 consume the natural resources on mission land and that successful execution of their mission is
45 dependent upon sustainable use of these lands. The AZARNG recognizes its responsibility to guarantee
46 continued access to its land, air, and water resources for realistic military training while ensuring that
47 the natural and cultural resources are sustained in a healthy condition for scientific research, education,
48 and other compatible uses by future generations.

49 This document will become part of the installation's master plan. The INRMP will be reviewed annually
50 and updated as needed. This INRMP will ensure that natural resource conservation and installation
51 mission activities are integrated and consistent with federal mandates for land stewardship.

52 **2.2 AUTHORITY**

53 **2.2.1 Arizona Army National Guard**

54 2.2.1.1 The Adjutant General

55 The Adjutant General (TAG) is the director of the Arizona Department of Emergency and Military Affairs
56 (AZDEMA) and is responsible for the Arizona National Guard (Air, Army, Joint Task Force), the Division of
57 Emergency Management, and the Division of Administrative Services. The TAG is a signatory on the
58 INRMP, authorizes its adoption and implementation, and has liability for environmental compliance.

59 2.2.1.2 Construction Facilities and Maintenance Office

60 The Construction Facilities Management Office (CFMO) oversees the EMO and provides functional
61 leadership for all AZARNG facility engineering programs, including facility construction, maintenance,
62 fire/emergency service, and real estate, with an emphasis on safeguarding the environment and
63 providing sustainable training areas and work environments.

64 2.2.1.3 Environmental Management Office

65 Nested within the Facilities Management Office (FMO), the EMO is responsible for the environmental
66 management of AZARNG lands. It ensures Camp Navajo complies with state and federal environmental
67 laws and regulations. The EMO is the primary organization within AZARNG responsible for the
68 implementation of the INRMP. Outlined below are the supporting positions responsible for the
69 implementation and oversight of the INRMP.

70 2.2.1.4 Training Site Command

71 The Training Site Command is responsible for ensuring that the facilities and training areas are
72 maintained to support the military mission of Camp Navajo. Responsibilities include the readiness and
73 availability of lands on which to conduct training and working with the Environmental Program manager
74 (EPM) to ensure compliance with regulations. The training site commander is directly responsible for
75 operating and maintaining Camp Navajo, including the implementation and the enforcement of the
76 INRMP.

77 2.2.1.5 Environmental Program Manager

78 The EPM oversees the implementation of the INRMP and the compliance of regulations throughout the
79 AZARNG. The EPM supervises the Conservation and Compliance Program managers.

80 2.2.1.6 Conservation Programs Manager

81 The Conservation Program manager is responsible for the natural resources programs throughout the
82 AZARNG. The manager directly supervises the Natural Resources Program managers and integrated pest
83 management coordinator and works with the EPM to ensure compliance with federal and state laws
84 pertaining to natural resources.

85 2.2.1.7 Natural Resources Manager

86 The natural resources manager (NRM) coordinates efforts to protect, enhance, and use the natural
87 resources found on Camp Navajo under the direct supervision of the Conservation Program manager.
88 The manager serves as the liaison between the AZARNG and other natural and cultural resources
89 agencies such as AGFD, USFWS, ASLD, USFS, and others. Responsibilities include assuring that natural
90 resources on the installation remain capable of supporting the training mission, working with the EPM
91 and training site commander in setting installation-specific hunting requirements, coordinating wildlife
92 and vegetative surveys, forest management and restoration activities, assisting the EMO with NEPA and
93 Section 7 ESA compliance, and other natural resource responsibilities.

94 2.2.1.8 Cultural Resources Manager

95 The cultural resource manager coordinates all efforts to protect, enhance, and use the cultural resource
96 found on Camp Navajo under the direct supervision of the EPM. This person is the liaison between the
97 AZARNG and cultural resource agencies such as the State Historic Preservation Office (SHPO) and others.
98 Responsibilities include assuring the cultural resources on the installation are capable of supporting the
99 training mission, working with the EPM and garrison commander, coordinating cultural resources
100 surveys, assisting the AZARNG with NEPA and Section 106 compliance, and other cultural resources
101 responsibilities.

102 2.2.1.9 Integrated Pest Management Coordinator

103 The integrated pest management coordinator provides oversight for all activities that involve pest
104 management by and for the AZARNG and ensures pest management activities, including but not limited
105 to contracts and facility operations, are consistent with the IPMP. The IPMP is a tool to manage pests by
106 combining biological, cultural, physical, and chemical tools in a way that minimizes economic, health,
107 and environmental risks.

108 2.2.1.10 Plans, Operations, and Training Officer

109 The plans, operations, and training officer (POTO) is responsible for maintaining training facilities and
110 scheduling training on Camp Navajo. The POTO establishes training methods to fulfill military mission
111 requirements while complying with environmental policies. The POTO plays an integral part in the
112 review process for the completion of this INRMP.

113 **2.2.2 National Guard Bureau**

114 The NGB is the higher headquarters for the AZARNG. Two directorates are involved in the management
115 of natural resources: The Army National Guard's Installation and Environment Directorate (ARNG I&E)
116 and the director of operations, training, and readiness (ARNG-TRS). ARNG I&E ensures operational
117 readiness by sustaining environmental quality through tracking projects, providing technical assistance
118 and quality assurance, and execution of funds. ARNG I&E provides policy guidance and resources to
119 create, sustain, and operate facilities that support the ARNG. ARNG-TRS is responsible for training and
120 training site support, which includes sustainable range management.

121 The NGB is responsible for providing natural resources management resources and policy for ARNG
122 units across the nation. The majority of the funding for the completion and implementation of this
123 INRMP is provided by the NGB. The NGB also provides environmental legal assistance, NEPA review, and
124 other specialized technical support for implementing this plan. The chief of the ARNG I&E reviews and
125 signs the INRMP on behalf of NGB. The NGB is the federal entity that must comply with SAIA.

126 **2.2.3 Other Federal Agencies**

127 2.2.3.1 United States Fish and Wildlife Service

128 Under SAIA, USFWS is required to work in cooperation with military installations to develop INRMPs
129 (Sikes Act SEC. 101. 16 USC 670a (a) (2)). Cooperative efforts with USFWS involve identifying potential
130 endangered species on Camp Navajo. The USFWS also provides general information on other sensitive
131 species, Species of Concern (SC), and habitat information. The USFWS has partnered with the NGB and
132 the AZARNG to conserve and protect currently listed species and their habitats and to work with military
133 partners to implement proactive conservation actions for SC and existing rare habitats. The USFWS is a
134 cooperating and signatory agency for the implementation of this plan in accordance with the SAIA. The
135 AZARNG will consult informally and/or formally with the USFWS prior to the implementation of any
136 action included in the INRMP that may affect listed or proposed species. The AZARNG will cooperate
137 with the USFWS on updating this document per the July 2013 Memorandum of Understanding (MOU)
138 between the DoD, USFWS, and the Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies for a Cooperative INRMP on
139 military installations.

140 2.2.3.2 United States Forest Service

141 The USFS is the land manager for federal property surrounding Camp Navajo. Biologists from the
142 Coconino and Kaibab national forests contributed information on sensitive species and their habitat
143 requirements for this document. Studies and experiments have been conducted on Camp Navajo by the
144 Forest and Range Experiment Station in Flagstaff, the results of which have supplied insect, disease, and
145 rodent control information to Camp Navajo NRMs. USFS personnel provide fire detection assistance for
146 Camp Navajo by manning the lookout tower on the installation. Four other lookout towers on adjacent
147 USFS lands provide additional fire surveillance. The Coconino and Kaibab national forests have been
148 invited to review this INRMP.

149 **2.2.4 State Agencies**

150 **2.2.4.1 Arizona Game and Fish Department**

151 In accordance with the SAIA, AGFD is required to work in cooperation with any military installation to
152 prepare an INRMP. Per SAIA: “the resulting plan for the military installation or State-owned National
153 Guard installation shall reflect the mutual agreement of the parties concerning conservation, protection,
154 and management of fish and wildlife resources” (Sikes Act SEC. 101. 16 USC 670a (a) (2)). The AGFD is
155 responsible for the management of fish and wildlife populations in the State of Arizona. The AGFD
156 conducts wildlife research on Camp Navajo at the direction of the EMO. In addition to wildlife research,
157 AGFD works with the AZARNG and other community partners to identify wildlife resources within the
158 approved Army Compatible Use Buffer (ACUB) (see Section 3.6). The AZARNG will cooperate with the
159 AGFD on updating this document per the July 2013 MOU between the DoD, USFWS, and the Association
160 of Fish and Wildlife Agencies for a Cooperative INRMP on military installations. The AGFD and the
161 AZARNG at Camp Navajo will meet on an annual basis to agree upon harvest objectives, permit
162 numbers, season dates, weapon types, and allocation of permits/access for elk, pronghorn, mule deer,
163 and turkey. The AGFD also assists the AZARNG in enforcing state hunting regulations on Camp Navajo.

164 **2.2.5 Tribes**

165 Camp Navajo will work with the Tribal government in policies and determinations that have Tribal
166 implication to incorporate traditional knowledge and experience into is land management decisions.
167 Natural resource and cultural managers will continue to promote enhanced and ongoing
168 communication, cooperation, and trust with Tribes and consider the traditional knowledge, experience,
169 and perspectives of Native American people to manage fish, wildlife, and natural and cultural resources.
170 The AZARNG will work with the Tribal governments to determine and act in accordance with applicable
171 treaty rights and trust responsibilities as they pertain to Camp Navajo.

172 **2.2.5 County and Local Agencies**

173 Camp Navajo works cooperatively with Coconino County to identify and conserve county open space
174 within the approved ACUB (see Section 3.6 for additional information). Coconino County, Naval
175 Observatory Flagstaff Station, and Camp Navajo completed a Joint Land Use Study conducted by military
176 installations and the communities surround them.

177 **2.2.6 Universities**

178 The AZARNG collaborates with universities to conduct research projects of mutual interest on Camp
179 Navajo. Expertise from universities have been valuable in providing specialized knowledge needed to
180 effectively manage natural resources on the installation. As of 2020, Camp Navajo is collaborating
181 working with Northern Arizona University (NAU).

182 **2.2.7 Contractors**

183 Contractors are an asset used by the NRM to provide short-term studies and reports. Contractors have
184 been used by the installation to develop plans for cultural and natural resources and complete the
185 necessary documentation to comply with environmental legislation. Camp Navajo will likely continue to
186 use contractors for projects related to implementation of the INRMP and forest and fire management
187 plans as well as NEPA documentation. Contractors give Camp Navajo access to a wide variety of
188 specialties and fields.

189 **2.2.8 In-House Capabilities**

190 The EMO has limited in-house research and special project capabilities due to a paucity of manpower.
191 The EMO staff will continue to look for opportunities to bring project and research in-house to maximize
192 funding. Currently, EMO uses GIS) as a powerful in-house research tool used to store and analyze data
193 on vegetation, wildlife populations, and range statuses. An upgrade to this system and its databases is in
194 progress and can be used to support future projects described in this INRMP.

195 The Intergovernmental Personnel Act of 1972 (IPA) allows the AZARNG to conduct research or obtain
196 personnel assistance from any state or federal agency. The IPA is a system allowing a state or federal
197 agency to borrow other state or federal agency personnel for a limited time period to do a specific job.
198 The agency pays the borrowed employee's salary and administrative overhead. There are two
199 advantages to using this system: 1) personnel are directly supervised by the associated funds manager
200 and 2) no manpower authorizations are required. Camp Navajo may use IPA agreements for assistance
201 with special projects. The most likely sources of this assistance are agencies that are partners for
202 implementation of this INRMP.

203 **2.3 MANAGEMENT PHILOSOPHY**

204 This INRMP will direct the Natural Resources Program at Camp Navajo and provide goals and objectives
205 to guide management activities. An integrated planning approach was used to develop the policies,
206 guidelines, and projects for each natural resource area within the plan. Implementation of this
207 management plan will support the installation's military mission while protecting Camp Navajo
208 ecosystems and their components. Plan expectations include the following:

- 209 • Provide guidance and continuity for existing and future natural resources management and
210 staff;
- 211 • Establish a framework for implementing natural resources programs and ecosystem
212 management;
- 213 • Provide centralized information on the Natural Resources Program;
- 214 • Identify environmental constraints so that military training can be synchronized with ecosystem
215 sustainability;
- 216 • Identify mission-related impacts to natural resources and options for conflict resolution;
- 217 • Serve as a baseline of existing environmental conditions for future environmental planning and
218 compliance projects;
- 219 • Assist installations in complying with environmental regulations;
- 220 • Identify, prioritize, and provide a timeline for long-term budget requirements; and
- 221 • Facilitate cooperation among the parties to the INRMP in implementing the plan.

222 The typical management programs addressed in an INRMP include training area management; land
223 management; forest management; aquatic and terrestrial habitat management; special natural area
224 management; fish and wildlife management; rare, threatened, and endangered species management;
225 pest management; wildland fire management; recreational resource and activity management; and
226 agricultural program management. The INRMP is a training-driven plan, created with a dual goal:

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- To allow for the conduct of appropriate military training at levels necessary to maintain a full readiness posture for national defense and civil missions; and
 - To provide for management of natural resources in an ecosystem-oriented, sustainable manner consistent with federal, state, and local regulations.

231 Benefits of the INRMP to the military mission include sustained use of Camp Navajo training lands,
232 better distribution of military activities, and integration of the military training mission with natural
233 resources management. The INRMP facilitates long-range, sustainable use of Camp Navajo and will
234 enhance mission readiness and realism with more training options. The INRMP will also provide natural
235 resources data, which can enable more intensive mission planning.

236 This INRMP emphasizes an ecosystem-based management approach to natural resources management,
237 consistent with DoD policies. Ecosystems extend beyond installation boundaries, and management of
238 Camp Navajo's natural resources will include development of partnerships with neighbors. Camp
239 Navajo's mission activities are integrated and consistent with federal stewardship requirements and
240 ensure the sustainability of quality training lands to accomplish Camp Navajo's military mission.

241 **2.3.1 Ecosystem-Based Management**

242 An ecosystem is the "sum of the plant community, animal community, and environment in a particular
243 region or habitat" (Barbour et al. 1987). Ecosystem-based management in the context of DoD
244 installations may be defined as "a goal-driven approach to managing natural and cultural resources that
245 supports present and future mission requirements; preserves ecosystem integrity; is implemented at a
246 scale comparable with natural processes; is cognizant of nature's timeframes; recognizes social and
247 economic viability within functioning ecosystems; is adaptable to complex and changing requirements;
248 and is realized through effective partnerships among private, local, state, Tribal, and federal interests"
249 (DoD Instruction 4715.3).

250 Natural resources at Camp Navajo will be managed using an ecosystem-based management approach.
251 Principles and guidelines of ecosystem-based management, per DoD Instruction 4715.03 (2018), state
252 that installations will:

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- Avoid single-species management and implement an ecosystem-based multiple species management approach, insofar as that is consistent with the requirements of the ESA.
 - Use an adaptive management approach to manage natural resources such as climate change.
 - Evaluate and engage in the formation of local or regional partnerships that benefit the goals and objectives of the INRMP.
 - Due to policy and fiscal implications, coordinate in advance partnerships involving external stakeholders or multiple military services through DoD component chains of command.
 - Include natural resources personnel in the planning and implementation phases of all resulting agreements.
 - Use the best available scientific information in decision-making and adaptive management techniques in natural resource management.
 - Foster long-term sustainability of ecosystem services.

265 DoD management strategy identifies the INRMP as the primary vehicle to implement biodiversity
266 conservation on military installations. The model process developed within the strategy includes the
267 following principles:

- 268 • Support the military mission;
- 269 • Use joint planning between NRMs and military operations personnel;
- 270 • Integrate biodiversity conservation into the INRMP and other planning protocols;
- 271 • Involve internal and external stakeholders up front;
- 272 • Emphasize the regional (ecosystem) context; and
- 273 • Concentrate on results.

274 Specific management practices identified in this INRMP have been developed in mutual agreement with
275 USFWS and AGFD to enhance and maintain biological diversity within the ecosystems at Camp Navajo.

276 **2.4 CONDITIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION**

277 **2.4.1 Implementation**

278 The EMO is responsible for directing the management of natural resources and for the development and
279 implementation of the INRMP. Successful implementation of the INRMP will require:

- 280 • Administrative and technical support;
- 281 • Agency cooperation and technical assistance;
- 282 • Funding;
- 283 • Priorities and scheduling;
- 284 • Production of project scopes and budgets; and
- 285 • The ability to amend and revise this document as necessary.

286 Where projects identified in the plan are not implemented because of lack of funding or other
287 compelling circumstances, the installation will review the goals and objectives of this INRMP to
288 determine whether adjustments are necessary.

289 **2.4.2 Effectiveness**

290 The primary measure of INRMP effectiveness is whether it helps prevent “net loss in the capability of
291 military lands to support the military mission.” The AZARNG is preserving Camp Navajo’s capability to
292 support training through its natural resource management practices outlined in this INRMP. The
293 AZARNG works with several partners to manage the forest, conserve sensitive areas, and practice
294 effective soil conservation. These activities are coordinated through on-going INRMP implementation.

295 Long-term management effectiveness is also evaluated through periodic inventories of species
296 populations, habitat quantity and quality, and habitat values through recurring planning-level surveys.
297 Trends can be used to indicate the degree of success. The AZARNG will evaluate these recurring data as
298 they become available.

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SECTION 3 INSTALLATION OVERVIEW

3.1 LOCATION AND AREA

Camp Navajo is located in north-central Arizona, 12 miles west of Flagstaff (population 73,964), 17 miles east of Williams (population 3,023), and adjacent to the small community of Bellemont (approximate population 300) located along I-40 (United States Census Bureau 2017) (**Appendix A, Figure 1**). The installation is located in a small topographic basin of the San Francisco Plateau within south-central Coconino County between the Coconino and Kaibab national forests (Ebasco 1990). The installation comprises approximately 28,413 acres which are used to support various National Guard training missions and the installation's munitions/missile storage mission. Approximately 28,397 acres of the installation is federal land, while the State of Arizona (AZDEMA) owns approximately 15 acres that encompass Bellemont Armory and the Facility Maintenance shop. An approximately 60-acre veteran's cemetery owned by the State of Arizona (Department of Veteran's Services) is within the Camp Navajo boundary. Approximately 916 acres are improved and include lawns, ball fields, parade and drill grounds, landscaped plantings, roads, buildings, and structures. Additionally, 1,752 acres are semi-improved and 25,745 acres are unimproved (**Appendix A, Figure 11**). The semi-improved grounds are those in the ammo storage area, security clear zone, and adjacent to utility lines. The unimproved grounds are woodlands, ponds, buffer areas, roadsides, and the areas surrounding storage facilities.

3.2 INSTALLATION HISTORY

Prior to military use, the land was used for homesteading, ranching, and logging. Lands for the installation were either purchased or taken from private landowners and added to lands that were transferred from the Kaibab and Coconino national forests. These combined lands formed the Navajo Ordnance Depot (NOD) in 1942. The site was selected based on its proximity to a major railroad with access to the west coast, 100 miles beyond the operational envelope of the Japanese carrier-based aircraft. The primary mission of the NOD was ammunition storage, with the original complex consisting primarily of storage and support facilities. The majority of the labor for the construction of buildings and ammunition storage units were supplied by the Navajo and Hopi Indian Reservations and other Native American workers. Construction was completed in 1943 (AZARNG 1993; Ebasco 1990).

In 1945, NOD's mission was expanded to include a prisoner of war camp for Austrian soldiers. This expanded mission continued until the end of World War II. Storage of chemical warfare service munitions, explosives, and ammunition continued throughout this time. NOD became a backup facility for the Erie Ordnance Depot in Ohio and later the Benicia Arsenal in California. Peak employment at NOD occurred in 1945 with 2,173 personnel (AZARNG 1993; Ebasco 1990).

Building continued into the late 1950s, during which time NOD stored a stockpile of chemical munitions. These chemical munitions were removed and disposed of in 1958. In 1967, the NOD was designated a Defense Supply Agency Depot. In 1971, it was renamed the Navajo Army Depot Activity (NADA) and placed under the command of the Pueblo Army Depot in Colorado. In 1982, the AZARNG assumed operational control of NADA and performed the Army Depot System Command's (DESCOM's) mission of receipt, storage, shipping, maintenance, and disposal of munitions to enhance the training of AZARNG units. In 1988, NADA was closed as a federally funded and controlled facility under the Base Realignment and Closure (BRAC) process but continued to store ammunition through 1992 using funding provided by DESCOM while the AZARNG used the installation as a training facility. In 1993, the

42 installation's name was shortened to Camp Navajo. Currently, the Camp Navajo mission includes
43 training AZARNG Soldiers, operating a storage depot, and providing an alternate site for state
44 emergency operations. A large portion of the land surrounding Camp Navajo is undeveloped and
45 managed by the USFS and ASLD (**Appendix A, Figure 1**). Public access is restricted to the majority of
46 Camp Navajo for security and safety reasons.

47 **3.3 MILITARY MISSION, FACILITIES, AND TRAINING**

48 **3.3.1 Military Mission**

49 Camp Navajo exists to support military training for the AZARNG. Camp Navajo is a major NGB training
50 area used primarily by Army and Air National Guard units (transportation, engineer, MP, aviation,
51 ordnance, medical, quartermaster, and other branches) for annual and weekend training. Additionally,
52 Camp Navajo serves as a training site for both the active and reserve component units of the armed
53 services. As an ARNG training area, Camp Navajo also supports the Arizona Regional Training Institute's
54 primary training programs: Non-Commissioned Officer Education System, Officer Candidate School, and
55 Military Occupational Specialty-Transitions schools.

56 Camp Navajo also conducts munitions and missile storage missions. A supplemental part of the
57 installation's mission continues to be the receipt, storage, shipping, and maintenance of various DoD
58 commodities, predominantly munitions and missile motors. Camp Navajo Ordnance Operations
59 Department bids for storage contracts from all branches of the DoD. Storage facilities consist of 788
60 ammunition igloos, general purpose warehouses, and a rocket motor transfer facility encompassed
61 within approximately 11,378 acres (40 percent of the installation) of the Ammunition Storage Area
62 (ASA). The rocket motor transfer facility is used to transfer rocket motors from rail and truck
63 transportation to intra-installation conveyances that transport rocket motors to long-term storage. The
64 igloos are used for long-term storage of conventional ammunition and missile components, while Y-
65 sites, located directly adjacent to igloos, are open air sites used to provide temporary or long-term
66 storage facilities for items that do not require covered storage.

67 **3.3.2 Facilities**

68 Camp Navajo can be roughly divided into four areas based on training, facilities present, and use
69 (**Appendix A, Figure 2**):

- 70 1. The Cantonment Area, which includes headquarters, training sites, the Field Maintenance Shop,
71 and a warehouse area.
- 72 2. The ASA, which stores various commodities, predominately munitions and missile motors.
- 73 3. Six Environmental Restoration Program sites totaling 2,131 acres contain residual contamination
74 from former Army depot operations (**Appendix A, Figure 12**). Due to human health and safety
75 concerns and in accordance with the Comprehensive Environmental Restoration, Compensation,
76 and Liability Act and the Restoration, Conservation, and Recovery Act, land use controls have
77 been implemented at these sites. The land use controls restrict access and limit activities which
78 may impact natural resource management projects in these areas.
- 79 4. The buffer area, which was designed to provide safe distances between storage facilities and
80 off-post land and is now used primarily for training. The small arms complex is located in the
81 buffer in northwestern corner (see Section 3.3.3).

82 3.3.2.1 Cantonment Area

83 Camp Navajo maintains 170 buildings, the majority of which are used for administration, maintenance,
84 operations, and general storage. A large number of the support buildings and facilities are located in the
85 north-central portion of the installation. Facilities include administration buildings, billeting, workshops
86 and work areas, motor pools, surveillance facilities, a fire and rescue facility, approximately 2.3 million
87 square feet of explosive and general-purpose warehousing, materials handling, loading/unloading,
88 transshipment facilities, and both rail and truck loading facilities for warehousing.

89 In 1993, a battalion-sized facility consisting of nine buildings was constructed in the installation's
90 Cantonment Area to provide accommodations for military units training at Camp Navajo. This 600-
91 person facility is also used for billeting of military personnel during non-training activities.

92 The AZARNG erected one 10-kilowatt wind turbine as a working demonstration project to illustrate the
93 application of wind energy and offset electrical consumption at Camp Navajo. The wind turbine tower is
94 a 100-foot-tall, guyed, lattice, tilt-up tower. The wind turbine was installed in the northern portion of
95 Camp Navajo within the Cantonment Area.

96 A more detailed description of these facilities, training ranges, and buildings are described in the *Camp*
97 *Navajo Real Property Development Plan* (November 2017).

98 3.3.2.2 Environmental Restoration Program Sites

99 The following six sites have land use controls in place due to health and safety concerns (**Appendix A,**
100 **Figure 12**). Natural resource management projects, especially intrusive activities, may be limited and
101 must be coordinated with the AZARNG EMO Restoration Program manager:

- 102 • The 701-acre Post-Closure Permit Area (PCPA), along with its 1,340-acre kick-out area (Solid
103 Waste Management Unit Munitions Response Work Area [SWMU MRWA] 02-02), is a former
104 open burn/open detonation (OB/OD) area. Munitions and explosives of concern (MEC) are
105 known to be present in surface and subsurface soil in the PCPA. No entry into the PCPA is
106 allowed without authorization from the garrison commander and without escort by explosive
107 ordnance disposal (EOD) or unexploded ordnance (UXO)-qualified personnel. Surface MEC were
108 removed from SWMU MRWA 02-02, but subsurface MEC may remain. No intrusive activities are
109 allowed in SWMU MRWA 02-02 without coordination with the AZARNG EMO Restoration
110 Program manager and UXO construction support if warranted.
- 111 • The 25-acre Old EOD Range, along with its 637-acre kick-out area (not shown on Figure 12 in
112 Appendix A), is also a former OB/OD area that was later used for training by AZARNG EOD units.
113 Surface MEC were removed, but subsurface MEC may remain in both areas. Non-intrusive
114 activities are allowed in both areas, but no intrusive activities are allowed in the Old EOD Range
115 without coordination with the AZARNG EMO Restoration Program manager and UXO
116 construction support if warranted.
- 117 • The 41-acre Former Pyrotechnic Range was used for surveillance testing of munitions. Surface or
118 subsurface MEC are not suspected to be present, but awareness of the possibility that MEC may
119 be present is maintained. If MEC is discovered at this site, the hazard will be re-evaluated.
- 120 • The 4-acre TNT Washout Facility was used for the refurbishing of military munitions. A perched
121 water-bearing zone located between 10 and 20 feet below the ground surface is contaminated

122 with explosives. No intrusive activities are allowed that would impact site conditions or damage
123 the groundwater monitoring wells.

124 • The 15-acre Former Sanitary Landfill was used for the disposal of household and industrial
125 wastes. It was capped and closed in 2001. To protect the integrity of the grass-covered
126 engineered cap, along with the associated surface water controls and groundwater monitoring
127 wells, no intrusive activities are allowed at this site.

128 • The 5-acre Construction Debris Landfill #5 was used to dispose of building debris from the
129 demolition of housing units in Indian Village. The landfill was removed, but low concentrations
130 of contaminants remain in the surface soil. Non-intrusive activities are allowed; however, no
131 intrusive activities are allowed within the footprint of the former landfill.

132 Prior to 1994, health and safety concerns prevented active management of the natural and cultural
133 resources in these areas. However, NGB and AZARNG worked closely with USFWS, AGFD, SHPO, and
134 local agencies to inventory the resources and mitigate potential impacts caused by the Army's
135 Environmental Restoration Program activities. Investigations, particularly within the PCPA, included the
136 following:

- 137 • Biological resources studies;
- 138 • Surveys for rare, threatened, and endangered plant and animal species (HEG 2005);
- 139 • Neotropical migrant birds, elk, and pronghorn studies;
- 140 • MSO surveys;
- 141 • Vegetation mapping;
- 142 • Reconnaissance-level tissue sampling at the OD pits;
- 143 • Cultural resource inventories;
- 144 • Soil sampling;
- 145 • Geological mapping;
- 146 • Geophysical surveys;
- 147 • Frost depth and frost heave study;
- 148 • Surface water and groundwater sampling;
- 149 • Human and ecological risk assessments;
- 150 • Soil excavation, biological treatment, and disposal; and
- 151 • MEC characterization, removal, and demolition.

152 While explosive and chemical hazards remain, non-intrusive monitoring of natural resources will
153 continue.

154 3.3.3 Training Areas and Activities

155 Camp Navajo is a major training facility for the AZARNG and other military and civilian
156 units/organizations to support readiness requirements and training missions. Under National Guard
157 Regulation 5-3 Camp Navajo is considered a Level III Garrison Training Center (formerly a Maneuver
158 Training Center-Light) meaning that it is a training installation that supports individual and collective
159 training for multiple battalions. Aviation, engineer, quartermaster, transportation, MP, and light infantry
160 units commonly train at Camp Navajo (AZARNG 1993), which provides a training experience that
161 simulates wartime conditions. Camp Navajo is divided into 14 training areas (**Table 1**). The land use
162 within each training area is depicted in **Appendix A, Figure 2**.

TABLE 1				
LAND USE WITHIN EACH AREA OF CAMP NAVAJO, BELLEMONT, ARIZONA				
Training Area	Location	Use	Acres	Number of Use Days Per Year*
Cinder Pit	Eastern portion, adjacent to ASA	Engineering and rock crushing operations, hunting	203	Military use ~12 days plus hunters
Tapen Springs	Eastern portion	Multi-use training areas for bivouac and limited tactical training as well as camping	351	Military use ~1,702 days plus hunters
Cantonment Area	Northern portion, near I-40 and railroad	Administrative buildings, classrooms, and multi-use	430	Regular use, daily
Railroad Tank	Southern portion, includes Volunteer Canyon	Multi-use training for bivouac, limited tactical training, and hunting	430	Military use ~156 days plus hunters
Cinder Pit	Western portion, adjacent to ASA	Engineer training area	1,595	Military use ~12 days plus hunters
Small Arms Complex	Western portion	Small arms training and hunting	330	Military use ~3,330 days plus hunters
Indian Village	Northern portion, near I-40 and railroad	In the past used for multi-use training for bivouac, limited tactical training, and hunting	419	Military use ~6,393 days plus hunters
Metz Tank Area	Southern portion	Multi-use training for bivouac, limited tactical training, and hunting	2,914	Military use ~171 days plus hunters
Land Navigation	Northwest portion, near I-40 and railroad	Land navigation course and common task training	735	Military use ~4,550 days
Neill Flat	Northeastern portion, near I-40 and railroad	Multi-use training area for bivouac and limited tactical training	1,313	Military use ~321 days
Logger's Camp	Southwestern portion, near Rogers Lake	Multi-use training area for bivouac and limited tactical training	2,033	Military use ~171 days
Jeep Trail	Western portion includes Volunteer Mountain	Multi-use training area for bivouac, limited tactical training, and hunting	3,539	Military use ~241 days plus hunters
Mickle Tank	Southwestern portion	Multi-use training area for bivouac, limited tactical training, and hunting	1,877	Military use ~156 days plus hunters
PCPA	South-central portion	No training or recreational use permitted; may be used as a small-arms range Surface Danger Zone in the future	701	Post-closure care ~30 days

TABLE 1				
LAND USE WITHIN EACH AREA OF CAMP NAVAJO, BELLEMONT, ARIZONA				
Training Area	Location	Use	Acres	Number of Use Days Per Year*
ASA	Central portion	Maintenance of igloos and hunting	11,378	Regular daily use, plus hunting

163 * Use Days = The equivalent of one person using the installation for 1 day.

164 The Small Arms Complex is in the northwest corner of Camp Navajo and is on approximately 330 acres
 165 (**Appendix A, Figure 2**). The complex consists of the following ranges:

TABLE 2		
SMALL ARMS RANGE COMPLEX		
Small Arms Complex	Area	Use
5.56-millimeter Semiautomatic Rifle (M16) Modified Record Fire Range	~68 acres	Live fire used to train and test individual Soldier's qualification requirements with the M16 and M4 rifles
Hand Grenade Qualification Course	~3 acres	Only practice grenades are used
Combat Pistol Qualification Course	~2 acres	Qualification requirements for the 9-millimeter, .38 caliber, and .45 caliber pistols
40-millimeter Grenade Launcher on M16 (M203)	~16 acres	Training and qualification requirements of the M203

166 3.3.4 Transportation System

167 Camp Navajo has about 75 miles of paved roads, 152 miles of cinder roads, and several miles of
 168 unimproved road throughout the training and storage areas. Access to the installation is from I-40 at Exit
 169 185 (AZARNG 2017). Camp Navajo also has access to the main line of Burlington-Northern and Santa Fe
 170 (BNSF) Railway's railroad and railhead operations.

171 Camp Navajo has a helipad used exclusively by the AZARNG that is located east of the vehicle entrance
 172 gate in the Cantonment Area. The closest airport to Camp Navajo is Pulliam Municipal Airport, located
 173 11 miles east of the installation off I-17 south of Flagstaff.

174 3.3.5 Wastewater Treatment Plant Reuse Area

175 The AZARNG developed a wastewater treatment facility, which is connected to the existing plant.
 176 Completed in 200, the facility improves wastewater treatment and increases treatment capacity. An
 177 effluent reuse area was established as part of the new facility. The 20-acre reuse area southeast of Pond
 178 1 has been graded, leveled, and seeded with native grasses and forbs. Reclaimed water is applied to the
 179 surface in vegetated areas designed to recycle the wastewater in an evapotranspiration process.

180 3.4 REGIONAL LAND USE

181 A large portion of the land surrounding Camp Navajo is undeveloped and managed by USFS, ASLD, and
 182 private holdings, with the Kaibab and Coconino national forests lands being the predominant land

183 holders (**Appendix A, Figure 1**). The BNSF Railroad forms the northern boundary of the installation,
184 beyond which lies the small town of Bellemont and I-40. The Kaibab National Forest is interspersed with
185 small tracts of private property and bounds Camp Navajo on the west. The east side of the installation is
186 bordered by Arizona State Trust Land managed by the ASLD, mixed with a few privately held parcels.
187 The southern boundary of Camp Navajo is adjacent to the Coconino National Forest, along with some
188 small tracts of private land.

189 The urbanized limits of the City of Flagstaff are approximately 5 miles from the Camp Navajo boundary.
190 Within the rural boundary are primary residences and second homes. Public lands in this area attract
191 recreation and tourism. Both private and public lands surrounding the installation are used for cattle
192 and sheep grazing. Industrial land use also occurs in this area. The forested areas have very little timber
193 value, although there have been attempts to develop markets for small-diameter ponderosa pine (*Pinus*
194 *ponderosa*). The current and potential sales of State Trust Lands around Camp Navajo could greatly
195 increase encroachment in the area, thus increasing the potential for conflicts with Camp Navajo's
196 mission. The Coconino County Parks and the Open Space Program have identified several sections of
197 State Trust Lands along the eastern boundary of Camp Navajo, which are also part of NAU's Centennial
198 Forest. These lands qualify for open space acquisition and are part of the Camp Navajo ACUB Program
199 (Section 3.6), but as of the date of this plan, adequate funds are not available.

200 **3.5 LOCAL AND REGIONAL NATURAL AREAS**

201 Within 10 miles of the Camp Navajo Boundary, there are several natural areas that attract various forms
202 of recreational use. The USFS, Coconino and Kaibab national forests lie adjacent to portions of Camp
203 Navajo and are the nearest natural areas to the installation. The San Francisco Peaks lie to the northeast
204 and encompass the Kachina Peaks Wilderness Area, Lamar Haines Memorial Wildlife Area, and
205 Humphreys Peak, the highest point in Arizona (12,633 feet). The popular Oak Creek Canyon and
206 Sycamore Canyon/Sycamore Canyon Wilderness lie to the south and exemplify the variation in
207 landscape and vegetation found in the spring-fed riparian systems that occur within the Colorado
208 Plateau. True tundra occurs at and above the tree line on the San Francisco Peaks. High-elevation forest
209 communities vary and include meadows and mixed conifer, broadleaf deciduous, aspen, and pine-oak
210 communities. Lower elevations in the region include oak and pinyon-juniper woodlands that grade into
211 interior chaparral and grassland communities in Oak Creek Canyon near Sedona. Additional natural
212 areas within 10 miles of Camp Navajo include Walnut Canyon National Monument, Rogers Lake County
213 Natural Area, Fort Tuthill County Park, and the 959 Pumphouse County Natural Area, all of which are
214 east of Camp Navajo.

215 **3.6 ARMY COMPATIBLE USE BUFFER**

216 The AZARNG at Camp Navajo participates in the ACUB Program. The Camp Navajo ACUB proposal was
217 approved on 16 January 2015. A successful ACUB Program will protect and sustain the National Guard
218 training mission as well as the munitions storage mission at Camp Navajo (now and into the future). The
219 AZARNG is currently working with the Central Arizona Land Trust to protect land adjacent to Camp
220 Navajo. For more information please see the *Army Compatible Use Buffer proposal (Maneuver Training*
221 *Center, Camp Navajo, Arizona* proposal, July 2013) which can be accessed in the Administrative Record,
222 available at the EMO at Camp Navajo.

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SECTION 4 PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT

4.1 CLIMATE

The climate of north-central Arizona is semiarid and characterized by cold winters, mild summers, and low humidity. The majority of days and nights are clear to partly cloudy. Prevailing wind direction is south-southwest, with an average speed of 7.4 miles per hour (Ebasco 1990). The mean annual temperature is 46.3 degrees F (Fahrenheit), with extremes (recorded in Flagstaff) of 97 degrees F and -30 degrees F (NOAA 2014). Annual average precipitation is 22 inches. There are two wet seasons, a winter wet season and a monsoon season, that occur during the months of December to March and July to September, respectively (NOAA 2014). Snowfall typically occurs between October and May. Snow and rain can co-occur. Average annual snowfall totals 102 inches; however, some winters have recorded less than 12 inches (NOAA 2014). Because of the dry climate, evaporation is significant, causing losses of 60 inches of water per year from exposed water surfaces (Ebasco 1990).

The wildfire season typically begins in early spring, when winter precipitation and snowpack dissipate. A dry spring and summer period typically precede the monsoons that begin in July. Lightning and rain during monsoon storms (July to September) can affect the end of wildfire season and the prescribed fire program. The primary source of fire ignition at this time is lightning; however, humans commonly ignite wildfires on the surrounding public lands (Westerling et al. 2003). To reduce the likelihood of fire caused by military activities, restrictions have been placed on certain training enhancers when fire danger levels are heightened, such as the use of tracers, smoke grenades, and other flame-producing devices. These items can be used without restriction during times of low fire danger.

Changes in climate patterns have the potential to affect local ecosystems on Camp Navajo and may require new approaches to land management. Through continued research on Camp Navajo, the AZARNG, with assistance from cooperating groups (e.g., USFWS and AGFD) will continue to amass information on the species and ecosystems on and around Camp Navajo. This information will be used to develop and refine land management practices in response to changes in climate patterns, while fulfilling the AZARNG's requirement to maximize training opportunities available at Camp Navajo.

4.2 LANDFORMS

Camp Navajo is in the Grand Canyon section of the Colorado Plateau physiographic province and within the San Francisco volcanic field. The topography is characterized by a basin-like valley of flat prairies, with a border of rolling forested hills extending around the basin that is interspersed with canyons, washes, and several volcanic cones (**Appendix A, Figure 3**). The average elevation of the installation is 7,100 feet above mean sea level (AMSL) in the northern and central portions, while the peaks and ridges of the east, south, and west average 7,500 feet AMSL. The highest point on Camp Navajo is Volunteer Mountain (8,047 feet AMSL), and the lowest point is located in the southwest corner where Volunteer Canyon (6,770 feet AMSL) crosses the western installation boundary.

The steep slopes of Volunteer Mountain and Volunteer Canyon prevent the use of vehicles for training maneuvers at these sites. The area's most suitable for training are in the western and eastern portions of the installation (Indian Village, Neill Flat, ASA, and Metz Tank).

39 **4.3 GEOLOGY AND SOILS**

40 **4.3.1 Geology**

41 Camp Navajo is underlain by a thin veneer of Quaternary and Tertiary unconsolidated materials, volcanic
42 rocks, and a thick sequence of Permian and older sedimentary rocks (**Appendix A, Figure 4**). The
43 unconsolidated materials consist of aprons and fans of colluvium and alluvium adjacent to the lower
44 flanks of some cinder cones and along ephemeral washes. Thirteen volcanic vents and associated lava
45 flows were extruded onto the Permian Kaibab Formation. Below the Kaibab Formation are the Permian
46 Toroweap Formation, Coconino Sandstone, Schnebly Hill Formation, Supai Formation, and the
47 Mississippian Redwall Limestone (Wolfe et al. 1987).

48 **4.3.2 Soils**

49 The Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) (USDA NRCS 2000) identified 17 soil units on Camp
50 Navajo (**Appendix A, Figure 5**). Eighty-five percent of the soils on Camp Navajo consist of Cabezon and
51 Huachuca very stony loams; Mento very gravelly loam; Nibley gravelly loam; and the Nibley-Huachuca,
52 Thimble-Kellypoint, and the Vitrandic Haplustalfs-Vitrandic Haplustolls families' complexes. These soils
53 are derived from the decomposition of the underlying bedrock and unconsolidated materials, and vary
54 in depth and proportions of sands, silts, and clays (soil texture) (USATHAMA 1979).

55 Movement throughout the installation can be restricted because of soil conditions. When soils become
56 saturated, vehicular movement off established roads and trails becomes difficult. To protect the soils
57 and their native plant communities, vehicle use is confined to designated roads and trails during the
58 winter and spring when the ground is wet.

59 4.3.2.1 Soil Erosion, Frost Heave, and Soil Expansion

60 Erosion is not a significant problem on Camp Navajo because snowmelt and rainfall are seldom great
61 enough to generate erosion (NADA 1987a). Many areas have a thick duff cover that protects the soil.
62 Roads are the largest source of soil erosion on the installation, and several roads in the southeast
63 section of the installation have lost their shallow topsoil. Re-vegetation of exposed surfaces helps
64 reduce and can prevent erosion. Vegetation loss from repeated military use, especially at commonly
65 used bivouac sites, can result in the loss of soil from rainfall, runoff, and wind erosion. Camp Navajo's
66 Forest Management Plan (**Appendix E**) specifically avoids timber harvest operations or removing cover
67 in areas having greater than 30-percent slopes due to equipment limitations and to minimize erosion.

68 Due to the high elevation and cold winter temperatures, the soil is prone to freezing. The Camp Navajo
69 soils freeze up to 2 feet in depth, with numerous freeze/thaw cycles throughout the winter. Freezing
70 causes the soil to loosen and expand, making it more prone to erosion. Freezing may also heave gravel,
71 stones, and other dense objects such as MEC. The intensity of frost heave varies according to soil type
72 and water content. Bare soil is more susceptible to freezing than soil insulated by snow or duff (Young
73 and Springer 2005).

74 **4.4 WATER RESOURCES**

75 **4.4.1 Surface Water**

76 Camp Navajo has approximately 100 acres of potentially regulated water bodies (Mauney et al. 2001).
77 Surface water can be found at several small wetland areas, ephemeral streams and washes, marshy

78 meadows, small perennially spring-fed man-made ponds, several small springs, and earthen water tanks
79 (Ebasco 1990) (**Appendix A, Figure 6**). Surface water is limited and there are no permanent, naturally
80 occurring streams or lakes on the installation. See *Section 4.4.3 Wetlands* for further discussion of
81 wetlands on Camp Navajo.

82 Annual runoff averages less than 1.25 inches, with spring runoff providing the majority of stream flow
83 (AZARNG 1993; Ebasco 1990). The intermittent runoff from Volunteer Wash drains into Sycamore
84 Canyon and subsequently into the Verde River (**Appendix A, Figure 6**) (Ebasco 1990). Approximately 19
85 of the 131-square-mile Volunteer Canyon Watershed fall within the installation (USATHAMA 1979).
86 From 1966 to 1980, peak annual runoff in Volunteer Wash ranged from 0 to almost 2,300 cubic feet per
87 second (Ebasco 1990). Runoff in Volunteer Wash has not been measured since 1980; therefore, current
88 measurement are not available.

89 The majority of Camp Navajo's surface water flow does not leave the installation as runoff (Ebasco
90 1990). Contributing factors include the interruption of surface flow, the detention of runoff, and the
91 existence of earthen water tanks and sink holes. Rapid infiltration and recharge of the groundwater
92 occurs in areas with very porous or fractured basalt; whereas areas with clay soils tend to absorb more
93 water (USDA NRCS 2000).

94 Three springs (two perennial and one intermittent) located north of the building complexes in the
95 ammunition workshop area produce relatively low and variable yields of water (USATHAMA 1979).
96 Overflow from the water pumped from the natural spring is stored in Pond 1 (5.9 acres), Pond 2 (1.5
97 acres), and Pond 3 (0.5 acre).

98 Fourteen earthen water tanks, manmade ponds, are located throughout the buffer area and provide
99 water for wildlife. Atherton Lake (Stan's Pond) south of the ASA is part of an ephemeral sinkhole
100 complex that usually dries up each summer by August.

101 **4.4.2 Groundwater Resources**

102 The Coconino aquifer is the primary water source for the City of Flagstaff and southern Coconino
103 County, including Camp Navajo. This regional unconfined aquifer (C-aquifer) is approximately 1,500 feet
104 below ground surface (bgs) (Ebasco 1990) and is comprised of the Coconino Sandstone and Supai
105 Formation.

106 Groundwater occurs in small perched water-bearing zones associated with fractured lava flows and the
107 Kaibab Formation, a layer of unconsolidated volcanic ash thought to be a former lake bed. This lake bed
108 underlies the uppermost lava flow west of the Cantonment Area and coincides with the nearby cluster
109 of springs at Ponds 1, 2, and 3. The clay found in this layer can create a solid impermeable space, or
110 aquiclude, which appears to be responsible for the perched water table in the area.

111 The Kaibab Formation limestone is locally fractured and jointed along the Bellemont fault, creating karst
112 features such as sinkholes that may act as conduits for rapid water infiltration to the regional aquifer
113 (Akers 1962; Akers et al. 1964; Montgomery and Dewitt 1974; Scott 1974).

114 A deeper regional aquifer, with water levels approximately 1,400 to 1,500 feet bgs, was first tapped in
115 2003 and now ensures a dependable backup water supply during periods of drought. However, local
116 faults and sinkholes may provide conduits between the surface and the regional aquifers. The regional

117 “C-aquifer” and the deeper “R-aquifer” are the primary municipal drinking water sources throughout the
118 Bellemont and Flagstaff areas. They also discharge to springs as far away as Verde Valley to the south
119 and Grand Canyon to the north. Camp Navajo is near the groundwater divide and its largely undisturbed
120 lands act as an important recharge area (Wilkinson 2000). Water quality of the regional aquifer wells on
121 Camp Navajo and some wells in Bellemont are monitored as a condition of the Arizona Hazardous Waste
122 Management Act Post-Closure Care Permit (ADEQ 2017).

123 The water supply for the installation is obtained from springs in a shallow perched water table and from
124 a regional aquifer well located north of Pond 1 (**Appendix A, Figure 6**). All water sources in use have
125 been permitted by the Arizona Department of Environmental Quality (ADEQ) potable water and are
126 subject to the Safe Drinking Water Act (SDWA). The AZARNG conducts all monitoring required by
127 regulations promulgated under the SDWA by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and ADEQ.
128 Droughts can severely impact the water supply, and thus, the mission at Camp Navajo. The maximum
129 potable water production available to the installation is 246,000 gallons per day (AZARNG 1993). This
130 water production supports the domestic requirements of 1,480 people at a rate of 150 gallons per
131 person per day, as well as the installation fire suppression system. In 2002, the AZARNG developed a
132 2,080-foot-deep well north of the wastewater treatment plant to provide supplemental water to the
133 installation.

134 The water distribution system was installed in 1942 and consists of a network of pipes ranging in
135 diameter from 4 to 12 inches. The majority of the piping is cast iron, with a few sections constructed
136 from galvanized steel or asbestos cement. The layout of the water distribution system contains
137 numerous looped networks. This layout provides the ability to isolate a section of the system without
138 disrupting the water supply to other areas. Planned upgrades and replacements to the existing water
139 distribution system are scheduled as needed and as funding is made available.

140 Water storage capacity on the installation includes 3 spring-fed water reservoirs (Ponds 1, 2, and 3) that
141 hold a total of approximately 26 million gallons. In addition, the installation has 3 storage tanks: a
142 1,000,000-gallon capacity tank, a 250,000-gallon clear well, and a 500,000-gallon elevated tank. The
143 elevated tank is primarily used for the installation’s daily water supply and includes fire suppression
144 capacity for some buildings equipped with sprinklers. Additionally, Camp Navajo has 9 railroad tanker
145 cars: two 7,000-gallon, two 11,000-gallon, and five 20,000-gallon capacity tanker cars. These are placed
146 strategically throughout the ASA’s existing rail system to support fire-fighting activities.

147 **4.4.3 Wetlands**

148 To estimate the extent of wetlands and other potential Waters of the United States (WOTUS) on Camp
149 Navajo, a planning-level survey was conducted in April of 2015 by SWCA Environmental Consultants
150 (SWCA 2015). The planning-level survey located approximately 100 acres (0.35 percent) of wetlands and
151 shallow water habitats in the classes of palustrine/open water (35 acres) and palustrine/emergent and
152 upland mosaic (25 acres) wetlands and 35 miles of stream class riverine/intermittent (R4SB) (**Appendix
153 A, Figure 6**). All of these areas are potentially regulated as WOTUS under Section 404 of the Clean Water
154 Act (CWA) (SWCA 2015). See Section 5.2.2.7 for additional information with regards to the vegetation
155 found within these wetlands.

156 4.4.4 Floodplains

157 There are several areas designated as 100-year floodplains by the Federal Emergency Management
158 Agency. Sites meeting the criteria for 100-year floodplain are concentrated in two areas located near the
159 Cantonment Area. These include areas near Atherton Lake, Pipe Springs, and along ephemeral streams
160 flowing toward Volunteer Canyon (**Appendix A, Figure 6**). Flooding is rarely a problem on Camp Navajo
161 due to the extensive network of open ditches, culverts, and storm sewer piping system adequate to
162 accommodate current surface runoff. Flooding has occurred occasionally in the past due to clogged
163 culverts. With the changing climate, rain events in Arizona are less frequent and occasioning more
164 intense. There is a potential with the extreme rain events for flooding to occur more frequently. Future
165 planning for building and infrastructure will consider those effects prior to construction.

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SECTION 5 ECOSYSTEMS AND THE BIOTIC ENVIRONMENT

5.1 ECOSYSTEM CLASSIFICATION

Under the National Hierarchical Framework of Ecological Units, Camp Navajo falls into the White Mountains–San Francisco Peaks section of the Arizona–New Mexico Mountains Semi desert–Open Woodland–Coniferous Forest–Alpine Meadow Province, under the Tropical/Subtropical Steppe Mountains Regime of the Dry Domain (Bailey 1995). This ecoregion covers 50,200 square miles of Arizona and New Mexico. This classification implies that the cool, dry climate of the region has a direct role in the formation of its physical geography and that the interplay of both climate and the regional landscape are the driving forces that determine biotic communities.

The vegetative characteristics of Camp Navajo place the area predominately in the Rocky Mountain (Petran) Montane Conifer Forest biome (122.3 in Brown [1994] classification) (**Appendix A, Figure 7**). Some areas contain plants characteristic of the Great Basin Shrub–Grassland biome (142.2 in Brown [1994] classification) (CEMML 1997; Moore and Covington 1998; TRIES 1996).

5.2 VEGETATIVE COVER

5.2.1 Vegetative Cover

Camp Navajo has approximately 19,018 acres of forest and 9,395 acres of grassland on the installation. Forested areas are predominantly ponderosa pine or pine/oak. Mixed conifer stands are associated with Volunteer Mountain or Volunteer Canyon and occupy approximately 602 acres. Aspen occurs infrequently on Camp Navajo and in small stands, generally less than 3 acres in size.

The present condition of forest stands on the installation is very different from pre-Euro-American settlement condition. Forest structure has changed from an open forest dominated by relatively large, mature trees to a dense forest characterized by relatively small, young trees (Fulé et al. 1997). Increased tree density and dead woody biomass has resulted in decreased herbaceous ground cover. In addition, grasslands have been reduced from historic level due to encroachment by ponderosa pine (**Appendix A, Figure 8**).

Changes in forest structure can be attributed to the suppression of a naturally occurring fire regime that began in the late 1800s for the purpose of protecting livestock grazing, roads, and other infrastructure (Covington and Moore 1994). The mean pre-settlement fire interval on Camp Navajo between 1637 and 1883 was between 3.7 to 6.5 years (Fulé et al 1997). Since 1883, fire has been suppressed and excluded from the area. As a result, forest density has increased from an average of 60 trees/acre in 1883 to 512 trees/acre by 1995, turning a once open forest dominated by relatively large ponderosa pines into a dense forest characterized by relatively small and young trees. Species composition has also changed, shifting away from the more frequent fire-adapted ponderosa pine and towards a less adapted Gambel oak (*Quercus gambelii*), conifers (e.g., white fir [*Abies concolor*] and Douglas fir [*Pseudotsuga menziesii*]). The comparison shows that the contemporary forest is well above the range of pre-settlement variability in forest density, and both live and dead fuel structures have developed that can support high-intensity wildfire (Fulé et al. 1997).

The AZARNG contracted NAU in 1993 to develop a vegetation community map based upon forest community types as part of the Forest Ecosystem Restoration Project. This vegetation community map was updated by NAU in 2012 (**Appendix A, Figure 7**).

41 5.2.2 Plant Communities

42 Surveys have been conducted to identify and locate different plant communities on Camp Navajo. The
43 surveys are the initial step in the protection and maintenance of diverse ecosystems. These botanical
44 surveys were started in 1992 when the Center for Environmental Management of Military Lands
45 conducted a botanical survey of 46 acres on the east side of the ASA. A total of 118 taxa were collected.
46 Asteraceae (sunflower family) was the most common plant family, with 32 taxa collected. Poaceae
47 (grass family) was second, with 20 taxa collected (Douglas et al. 1993). Seventeen plants listed as
48 protected by the Arizona Native Plant Law (ANPL) are found on Camp Navajo (see **Table 4**).

49 An installation-wide floral survey was completed in 1995 and updated in 2012 (NAU 2012; TRIES 1996).
50 The surveys identified plants from 72 families, 261 genera, 405 species, and 493 subspecific taxa. Five
51 non-native invasive species were found during the survey: field bindweed (*Convolvulus arvensis*),
52 common purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*), spotted knapweed (*Centaurea maculosa*), Dalmatian toad flax
53 (*linaria dalmatica*), and Scotch thistle (*Onopordum acanthium*). These plants are considered Prohibited,
54 Regulated, and Restricted Noxious Weeds by the Arizona Department of Agriculture and occupied areas
55 may be controlled and quarantined to prevent further spread (State of Arizona Noxious Weed
56 Regulations R3-4-244; Arizona Administrative Code R3-4-244). Ten species were considered undesirable
57 by the NRM: sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*), flannel mullein (*Verbascum thapsus*), longflower
58 rabbitbrush (*Chrysothamnus depressus*), Canada thistle (*Cirsium arvense*), dandelion (*Taraxacum*
59 *officinale*), Johnson grass (*Sorghum halepense*), cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*), field brome (*Bromus*
60 *avensis*), filaree (*Erodium cicutarium*) and salsify (*Tragopogon species*) (AZARNG 2012; TRIES 1996)
61 (**Appendix D**).

62 5.2.2.1 Dominant Forest Communities

63 Ten of the 14 vegetation communities found on Camp Navajo are classified as forest, with the dominant
64 forest type being pure ponderosa pine. Other forest types include ponderosa pine–Gambel oak and
65 mixed conifer, including areas dominated by Douglas fir and blue spruce (**Table 3**) (McHugh 1996).

66 The eastern section of the buffer area is a mixture of grasslands and ponderosa pine forest. Forest
67 structure on the east side of the buffer area is mainly dense even-aged stands of ponderosa pine with
68 few openings. Logged areas were seeded with grasses and legumes, and trees were allowed to
69 regenerate naturally (NADA 1987a). The western and southwestern boundaries, excluding Volunteer
70 Mountain and Volunteer Canyon, are dominated by ponderosa pine and Gambel oak. The southeast and
71 east portions of the buffer area also contain dense areas of saplings and poles. Pre-commercial thinning
72 and pulp and timber harvests have opened a few of the stands. The ASA chiefly contains a dense
73 ponderosa pine community with some Gambel oak and small quaking aspen (*Populus tremuloides*)
74 groves. Grass species include Arizona fescue, blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*), Fendler threeawn (*Aristida*
75 *purpurea*), and squirreltail (*Elymus elymoides*).

76 The ponderosa pine-Gambel oak mature forest (122.323 in Brown [1994] classification) on Camp Navajo
77 is structurally diverse. Open areas in the forest exist naturally and from prior forest thinning and burning
78 activities. Other areas are dense with ponderosa pine, Gambel oak, New Mexico locust (*Robinia*
79 *neomexicana*), and white fir. Douglas fir and junipers (*Juniperus* spp.) are also present but are less
80 abundant (Fulé et al. 1995; NAU 1996). Some areas in the buffer area contain open stands of ponderosa
81 pine, with Arizona fescue (*Festuca arizonica*) and mountain muhly (*Muhlenbergia montana*) as dominant

82 understory species. Forest inventory that followed thinning procedures show a forest density similar to
 83 that during the historical surface fire regime, with 96 trees/acre and 75 square feet/acre (Stephens et al.
 84 2013). This vegetative community (ponderosa pine-Gambel oak) is the most common on Camp Navajo,
 85 with many smaller forest communities also identified throughout the installation (McHugh 1996).

Dominant Overstory Species	Dominant Understory Species	Overstory Associates	Understory Associates
Douglas fir	Rocky Mountain snowberry	Gambel oak	Not Available (N/A)
Colorado blue spruce Ponderosa pine	N/A	N/A	N/A
Gambel oak New Mexico locust	N/A	ponderosa pine	N/A
Alligator juniper	N/A	Gambel oak ponderosa pine	Rocky Mountain snowberry
Ponderosa pine Gambel oak	N/A	alligator juniper	squirreltail mountain muhly
Ponderosa pine	Arizona fescue	N/A	N/A
Ponderosa pine	Arizona fescue	N/A	mountain muhly
Ponderosa pine	New Mexico locust	Gambel oak alligator juniper	White Mountain sedge squirreltail
Ponderosa pine	Arizona fescue	Utah juniper rocky mountain snowberry	blue grama mountain muhly
Arizona fescue	N/A	mountain muhly	N/A
Rabbitbrush	Arizona fescue	N/A	blue grama
Rabbitbrush	Arizona fescue	N/A	N/A
Ponderosa pine	New Mexico locust	N/A	N/A

86 5.2.2.2 Other Forest Communities

87 The north slope of Volunteer Mountain is dominated by Douglas fir (122.31 in Brown [1994]
 88 classification) with Gambel oak as the dominant overstory associate and Rocky Mountain snowberry
 89 (*Symphoricarpos rotundifolius*) as the dominant understory associate species. Some white fir and
 90 subalpine fir are also present. This area contains stands of pine, spruce, and juniper with little to no
 91 evidence of previous forest thinning. Some areas are very dense as a result of fire suppression (NADA
 92 1987a). The slopes of the canyon are dominated by mature blue spruce with an herbaceous understory
 93 while more open aspects within the canyon have a mix of ponderosa pine with an herbaceous
 94 understory.

95 A mixed forest community of Gambel oak (123.32 in Brown [1994] classification) and New Mexico locust
 96 occurs on slopes with a west and northwest aspect on the west side of the installation. Scattered
 97 ponderosa pine occurs throughout, although pine is less abundant in this community than in other

98 mixed forest types found on Camp Navajo. The upper and lower canopies are very thick, and few
99 understory herbaceous species are present. On other west-facing slopes, pine and oak are the dominant
100 tree species, with alligator juniper (*Juniperus deppeana*) interspersed. New Mexico locust is the
101 dominant woody understory species, and White Mountain sedge (*Carex geophila*) and squirreltail are
102 the dominant understory herbaceous species (McHugh 1996).

103 In drier forested areas, alligator juniper is the dominant overstory species, with a mixture of oak,
104 ponderosa pine, and Rocky Mountain snowberry associates. These areas are more open, with scattered
105 ground cover throughout (McHugh 1996).

106 5.2.2.3 Upland Grasslands

107 Grasslands and mountain meadows (141.41 in Brown [1994] classification) are also found on Camp
108 Navajo. Grasslands are the second most common vegetation community and cover approximately 9,455
109 acres. Some of the grasslands are dominated by Arizona fescue with mountain muhly as a common
110 associate. Other grasslands and meadows contain several fescue species, mountain muhly, pine
111 dropseed (*Blepharoneuron thricholepis*), blue grama, western wheatgrass (*Pascopyrum smithii*),
112 common wolftail (*Lycurus phleoides*) and cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*), scattered with rabbitbrush
113 (*Chrysothamnus nauseosus consimilis*), legumes, and forbs (Horncastle et al. 2011; NADA 1987a).

114 5.2.2.4 Lowland Grasslands

115 Several areas identified in the Range and Training Land Assessment (RTL) Program survey (CEMML
116 1997) were marshy meadows or marshy meadows dominated by grasses with scattered pine (242.4 in
117 Brown [1994] classification). Non-grass species within these wet areas include aspen onion (*Allium*
118 *bisceptrum*), shortspike watermilfoil (*Myriophyllum sibiricum*), sleeping popcorn flower (*Plagiobothrys*
119 *scouleri*), near navarretia (*Navarretia intertexta*), Mexican dock (*Rumex salicifolius*), Platte River
120 cinquefoil (*Potentilla plattensis*), and several species of sedge.

121 5.2.2.5 Chaparral

122 Drier communities also are found within Camp Navajo. Chaparral (133.3 in Brown [1994] classification)
123 are found on some south and west slopes on the west side of Camp Navajo. Alder-leaf mountain
124 mahogany (*Cercocarpus montanus*), cliffrose (*Cowania mexicana*), scrub oak (*Quercus turbinella*), and
125 buckbrush (*Ceanothus fendleri*) are common.

126 5.2.2.6 Turf and Landscaped Areas

127 The only area on Camp Navajo that has been landscaped is within the Cantonment Area. A mixture of 60
128 percent Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis*) and 40 percent fescue (*Festuca* spp.) was used to establish
129 and replant lawns on the installation. This mixture appears to be the best adapted for this area,
130 providing a green lawn for the longest period (NADA 1987a). The earth-covered storage magazines
131 (igloos) were planted with introduced grasses such as wheat grasses (*Pascopyrum* spp.), perennial rye
132 (*Elymus* spp.), and orchardgrass (*Dactylis glomerata*). All future reseeding in other areas, on igloos and
133 damaged areas, will be done with native vegetation.

134 5.2.2.7 Wetland plant communities

135 As noted in Section 4.4.3, a delineation of wetlands and regulated waters was conducted in 2015 that
136 identified 100 acres of wetland and shallow water habitats on Camp Navajo. Eight plant species were

137 identified, which include common yarrow (*Achillea millefolium*), northern water plantain (*Alisma*
138 *trivale*), pointed broom sedge (*Carex scoparia*), willowherb (*Epilobium brachycarum*), Rocky Mountain
139 iris (*Iris missouriensis*), Mexican rush (*Juncus mexicanus*), seep monkeyflower (*Mimulus guttatus*), and
140 little bluestem (*Schizachyrium scoparium*) (**Appendix D**).

141 **5.3 AGRICULTURAL OUTLEASING**

142 There are currently no crops or horticulture on Camp Navajo; however, grazing has been permitted in
143 the past. Livestock grazing is currently suspended.

144 **5.3.1 Grazing History**

145 Grazing has been allowed on Camp Navajo from 1942 until 2002. Lessees were granted grazing
146 privileges on the land from USFS. When the Army acquired the land, grazing privileges were retained.
147 Between 1942 and 1961, sheep and cattle were grazed on the installation, and from 1962 to 1965, only
148 sheep were grazed on the installation. Because 60 percent of the grazing land was overgrazed by 1965,
149 the land was rested between 1966 and 1968. At that time, the United States Army Corps of Engineers
150 (USACE) restricted sheep grazing on the installation to prevent overgrazing. On May 15, 1969, a 5-year
151 grazing lease was established that allowed cattle grazing. In 1985, a second grazing lease was signed that
152 allowed cattle grazing in each of the three grazing units. In 1991, a fence was constructed to prevent
153 cattle from entering the PCPA (old OB/OD Area). The land was again rested from 1994 to 1996 while a
154 grazing feasibility study was conducted. Cattle were re-introduced on the installation in 1998. All leases
155 were approved by the USACE district engineer or their authorized representative, in accordance with
156 Army Regulation (AR) 450-08. Grazing leases were under evaluation with assistance from AGFD to
157 determine appropriate grazing levels. Grazing leases ran from 15 May to 15 October on 5-year leases
158 that expired on 15 November 2002. Livestock grazing has not occurred on the installation since that
159 time, and many of the grazing unit boundary fences have been removed. Initially, grazing leases were
160 stopped to rest the land and have not been allowed since due to ecological and economic
161 considerations.

162 **5.4 FISH AND WILDLIFE**

163 The AZARNG coordinates with a variety of other agencies and interested parties to identify and manage
164 wildlife on Camp Navajo. Agencies and universities involved are USFWS, AGFD, USFS, ASLD, the
165 University of Arizona, and NAU. Results of previous and on-going studies will be used to manage wildlife
166 on Camp Navajo in order to maintain the land for military training. The results from these studies allows
167 the EMO to recommend management decisions regarding land use and training in a timely manner.

168 Significant progress has been made in identifying and inventorying non-game species on the installation.
169 Installation-wide surveys have been conducted for mammals, birds, fish, amphibians, reptiles, insects,
170 crustaceans, and mollusks (**Appendix D**).

171 Surveys for small mammals and birds were conducted on RTLA plots established in 1992. Additional
172 surveys were conducted from 1995 to 1999 (TRIES 1996). Breeding bird surveys were conducted in the
173 west buffer of Camp Navajo from 1996 to 1998. Songbird surveys have also been conducted by AGFD in
174 2006, 2008, and 2011 to 2013. Biennial MSO surveys are conducted throughout the installation by base
175 biologists. Surveys for northern goshawks were conducted in 2000, 2004, and 2010 on portions of Camp

176 Navajo (Ingraldi 2000; Nabel 2004; Lynn 2010). Bat surveys were conducted from 2004 to 2016
177 (Diamond 2016; Horncastle et al. 2007, 2009).

178 Prior to RTLA surveys, fauna inventory and monitoring were primarily for wildlife game species. The
179 AGFD is responsible for the inventory and monitoring of game species in the state. Camp Navajo's NRM
180 and other personnel assist AGFD in surveying wildlife populations on the installation. From inventory
181 and monitoring efforts, the AGFD and the AZARNG have identified special habitat areas for game species
182 on the installation, such as pronghorn and deer fawning grounds and elk calving grounds.

183 **5.4.1 Mammals**

184 Mammals from 13 families, 24 genera, and 29 species inhabit Camp Navajo (**Appendix D**). Common
185 forest species include squirrels (*Sciurus* spp., *Spermophilus* spp., and *Tamiasciurus* spp.), chipmunk
186 (*Eutamias cinereicollis*), brush mice (*Peromyscus boylii*), deer mice (*Peromyscus maniculatus*), Mexican
187 woodrat (*Neotoma mexicana*), porcupine (*Erethizon dorsatum*), and several bat species, including
188 myotis (*Myotis* spp.), pallid bat (*Antrozous pallidus*), big brown bat (*Eptesicus fuscus*), and the hoary bat
189 (*Lasiurus cinereus*) (**Appendix D**).

190 Gunnison's prairie dogs (*Cynomys gunnisoni*) are common in the prairie areas. Prairie dog towns exist
191 west of Railroad Tank and in the ASA. Other species found on the installation include Botta's pocket
192 gopher (*Thomomys bottae*), desert cottontail rabbit (*Sylvilagus auduboni*), black-tailed jack rabbit (*Lepus*
193 *californicus*), long-tailed weasel (*Mustela frenata*), coyote (*Canis latrans*), raccoon (*Procyon lotor*),
194 badger (*Taxidea taxus berlandieri*), striped skunk (*Mephitis mephitis*), bobcat (*Felis rufus*), and gray fox
195 (*Urocyon cinereoargenteus*) (TRIES 1996).

196 Three species of tree squirrel were identified on Camp Navajo during RTLA surveys (TRIES 1996). Abert's
197 squirrel (*Sciurus aberti*) is widely distributed throughout the ponderosa pine forest. The Arizona gray
198 squirrel (*Sciurus arizonensis*) was noted as uncommon, observed only in old-growth ponderosa pine
199 habitat above the ASO Tank #2 (**Appendix A, Figure 6**). The red squirrel (*Tamiasciurus hudsonicus*) is
200 found in blue spruce (*Picea pungens*) trees in upper Volunteer Canyon, a habitat that typifies the species
201 (Hoffmeister 1986). Squirrel densities within the western buffer of Camp Navajo were surveyed for 2002
202 and 2003 (Bayless and Ingraldi 2006) and again in 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2011, and 2012 (Gist et
203 al. 2014).

204 Camp Navajo provides important habitat for woodpeckers and cavity-nesting birds and bats, which roost
205 in snags. Snags on surrounding areas are often removed as firewood. The protection of snags provides a
206 unique opportunity to maintain these birds and bats at a relatively high density which can be beneficial
207 to populations in surrounding areas as well as Camp Navajo.

208 5.4.1.1 Bats

209 Bats in northern Arizona are generally found in ponderosa pine, ponderosa pine-oak forests, or riparian
210 broadleaf forest areas. Snags provide important roosting habitat, and riparian areas, forest fragments,
211 and meadows provide foraging habitat. Roosting habitat (snags and trees with peeling bark) are typically
212 near a water source. Bats are opportunistic foragers, feeding on concentrations of insects and
213 arthropods (e.g., moths, beetles, and other nocturnal, soft-bodied insects). Bat studies have been
214 conducted primarily within the western portion of Camp Navajo, which is mainly comprised of
215 ponderosa pine forest with Gambel oak and New Mexican locust understory. These studies were driven

216 by three separate forest restoration treatments. Ten bat species have been captured on Camp Navajo,
217 and an additional five species are known to occur within the vicinity of Camp Navajo (AGFD 2018;
218 Horncastle et al. 2007, 2009).

219 Studies from 2005 to 2016 (Diamond 2016; Horncastle et al. 2007, 2009) found that common species
220 such as the big brown bat and Arizona myotis responded positively to timber management practices, the
221 combined thin and burn method being the most effective. This positive response only lasted for six
222 years, as use continually declined before equaling deferred treatment levels. Burning treatments had a
223 lag affect, with spikes in occurrence observed four years following treatment. Our long-term study
224 suggested that timber management practices have a dynamic impact to tree roosting bat ecology, with
225 observable impacts that vary by species and time since forest treatment (Diamond 2016).

226 5.4.1.2 Big Game

227 Camp Navajo is used seasonally by a number of different big game species such as Rocky Mountain elk
228 (*Cervus elaphus nelsoni*), mule deer (*Odocoileus hemionus*), pronghorn and Merriam's turkey.
229 Maintaining suitable travel corridors is essential for population viability.

230 In the past, elk, deer, and pronghorn populations were usually higher on the installation than
231 surrounding forested lands. These higher populations were attributed to reduced hunting pressure on
232 the installation, and the movement of game from the Sycamore Canyon wilderness area onto the
233 installation via Volunteer Canyon (NADA 1987b). Elk, pronghorn, and deer use Camp Navajo during the
234 spring, summer, and fall. Habitat for these species is in good condition on the installation.

235 Hunting pressure has increased on the installation in general to keep game species at sustainable levels
236 The ASA (**Appendix A, Figure 2**) on Camp Navajo experiences less hunting pressure than other areas of
237 the installation. The PCPA is closed to hunting due to safety concerns.

238 5.4.1.2.1 Elk

239 During the warm seasons, elk are found in the coniferous forests and mountain meadows of the buffer
240 area, ASA, and PCPA. Western sections of the buffer area containing Gambel oak may serve as calving
241 grounds (Luedeker 1997). Summer population counts, usually conducted in August, estimate 700 to
242 1,000 elk on the installation. A smaller number stay and use the lower woodlands, mixed conifer forest,
243 and grassland as winter range. The preferred foods of elk are grasses, sedges, and aspen. They also use
244 many of the understory shrub species such as service-berry (*Amelanchier* spp.), rabbitbrush, Rocky
245 Mountain snowberry, and several other species (Hoffmeister 1986).

246 Elk show both daily and seasonal movements and tend to leave Camp Navajo when snow cover is
247 moderate to heavy. Major game trails are found running north and south of the Volunteer Mountain. An
248 east-west movement of elk off and onto the installation occurs in the southeast buffer area adjoining
249 Rogers Lake and a north-south movement at Metz Tank up through the Cantonment Area (Loeser and
250 Sisk 2005). The outer perimeter fence has 30 elk crossings that allow movement between the Kaibab
251 and Coconino national forests and Camp Navajo. Many elk travel from the Sycamore Wilderness area
252 north through Volunteer Canyon into the forested buffer area (NADA 1987b).

253 5.4.1.2.2 Mule Deer

254 Mule deer occur throughout the installation. In the pine forest, they feed on shrubs and some grasses
255 and sedges. They prefer to forage on small shrubs and herbaceous plants depending on the season and
256 frequent the PCPA to feed on the abundant grasses and browse species. Most of the population stays on
257 Camp Navajo year-round.

258 5.4.1.2.3 *Pronghorn*

259 Pronghorn are located throughout Camp Navajo's open areas from April to October. Female pronghorn
260 are on Camp Navajo during the fawning period (1 April to 15 June). A movement study conducted on
261 Camp Navajo indicated that pronghorn move among openings on or near Garland Prairie, Camp Navajo,
262 and Rogers Lake. Pronghorn are migratory and make numerous movements between Camp Navajo and
263 adjoining areas to lower elevations when weather, primarily snow, prompts movement (Waddell et al.
264 2005). AGFD GPS monitoring results of pronghorn movements from Camp Navajo suggested they are
265 moving through several access corridors.

266 5.4.1.2.4 *Merriam's Turkey*

267 In Arizona, Merriam's turkey is typically associated with ponderosa pine forests adjacent to montane
268 meadows. Merriam's turkeys prefer un-grazed meadows and mature, unlogged stands of pine and oak
269 with forbs and grass cover. The mixed-forb grass understory or meadows containing Arizona fescue,
270 mountain muhly, wild bromes, and pine dropseed are important for survival of young (Brown 1989).

271 Merriam's turkeys are found throughout Camp Navajo. The ponderosa pine/Gambel oak forests provide
272 suitable turkey habitat. Pines are used as roosting habitat, and foraging areas tend to have higher basal
273 area of Gambel oak. Gambel oak acorns and alligator juniper berries are an important food source for
274 turkeys during early and late winter (Wakeling and Rogers 1995). Meadows, drainages, and stream sides
275 are used by hens and poults. Toms prefer foraging throughout the forest.

276 An essential component of turkey habitat in Arizona is water. In the summer, turkeys will normally be
277 found at watering areas in the early morning or late afternoon. By fall, when water is scarce, they are
278 found closer to a water source and will visit these areas in midday (Brown 1989).

279 In summer, the sexes normally remain separate. Hens and poults inhabit meadows and streamsides.
280 They feed on greens and insects such as grasshoppers, crickets, stoneflies, and leaf beetles. Males feed
281 on pine seed and forbs throughout the forest. When water becomes scarce in the fall, turkeys will stay
282 near any major source. Turkey will stay in the pine areas until heavy snowfall, then retreat to the lower
283 elevations where they feed on juniper berries, grass seeds, pinyon pine seeds, and other available food
284 sources (Brown 1989). Camp Navajo contains the necessary components for prime warm-season turkey
285 habitat.

286 5.4.1.2.5 *Other Large Game Mammals*

287 Other large game mammals found on Camp Navajo include black bear (*Ursus americanus*) and mountain
288 lion (*Felis concolor*). Camp Navajo has an abundance of prey species for mountain lion, which chiefly
289 include deer, pronghorn, rabbit, porcupine, and javelina (*Tayassu tajacu*). A population of javelina is
290 known to inhabit Sycamore Canyon and may eventually move north up Volunteer Canyon.

291 5.4.2 Birds

292 See **Appendix D** for a detailed list of bird species that occur on Camp Navajo (TRIES 1996). RTLA surveys
293 identified seven species of woodpecker (Family *Picidae*), two hummingbirds (Family *Trochilidae*), and 56
294 passerines (Order Passeriformes), most of which use woodland areas. Breeding bird inventories in the
295 northwest portion of the buffer area documented 53 breeding passerine bird species within ponderosa
296 pine habitat (Lesh and Rosenstock 1999). Passerine bird densities within the western buffer of Camp
297 Navajo were surveyed from May to July in 2008 to 2015. (Frery et al. 2009; Gwinn et al. 2015).
298 Shorebirds are common at the earthen water tanks throughout the installation and over 20 species have
299 been identified (TRIES 1996). Many species that require grasslands, brushy areas, and open woodlands
300 also occur on Camp Navajo.

301 From 2000 to 2003, annual winter raptor surveys were conducted in 8 square miles along the northern
302 boundary to establish a benchmark for long-term monitoring on the installation (Bayless and Ingraldi
303 2005). Since 2010 EMO NRMs began conducting these surveys annually from November to March,
304 expanding the route to encompass additional areas on the installation.

305 Although Camp Navajo does not support large wetlands, many species of waterfowl (Family *Anatidae*)
306 use the installation during migration. Atherton Lake in the ASA is used by waterfowl when water is
307 present. Waterfowl also use Ponds 1, 2, and 3 and many of the earthen water tanks. Seventeen species
308 of duck and two species of goose have been identified on the installation since 1993 (AZARNG 1993;
309 TRIES 1996). The meadow and spring restoration projects are expected to have minimal effects on these
310 bird species, as work is planned outside the breeding season.

311 5.4.3 Fish

312 There are no permanent streams or lakes on Camp Navajo, and no native fish species in the existing
313 aquatic environments. Recreational fishing, when made available, is provided by stocking Pond 1 in the
314 ASA with rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). In the past, Pond 1 was stocked with brown trout,
315 (*Salmo trutta*), grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon Idella*), and smallmouth bass (*Miropterus dolomieu*).
316 Catfish (*Ictalurus* spp.), green sunfish (*Lepomis cyanellus*), and bluegill (*Lepomis macrochirus*) have been
317 caught in Pond 1 but were not officially stocked.

318 Ponds 2 and 3 are concrete-lined structures that were stocked in the past but are now closed to
319 recreational fishing. Pond 3 was stocked with smallmouth bass and channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*)
320 in 1987. In the fall of 1995, both ponds were closed to fishing because they were close to a sensitive
321 military area. No future stocking will occur in Pond 2 and 3, which will be maintained as back-up
322 reservoirs.

323 Johnson Tank and Quarry Tank are remnants of cattle tanks and quarry activity and have been stocked
324 with fish in the past. Johnson Tank is located in the northwestern quadrant of the installation near the
325 Small Arms Range Complex (**Appendix A, Figure 6**). Quarry Tank is in the ASA, below Atherton Lake
326 (**Appendix A, Figure 6**). Largemouth bass (*Micropterus salmoides*) were added to both tanks in 1994. In
327 1995, fathead minnows (*Pimephales promelas*) were added to Johnson Tank as a food source for the
328 bass. These areas are no longer stocked or open to fishing.

329 During the 1995 RTLA survey, largemouth bass were collected from both tanks and a fathead minnow
330 was collected from Johnson Tank. Shiners (*Notropis* spp.) were collected from the rifle range tanks, and
331 cutthroat trout (*Oncorhynchus clarki*) were found in Ponds 1 and 2 (TRIES 1996).

332 **5.4.4 Amphibians and Reptiles**

333 Field surveys for reptiles and amphibians were not conducted on Camp Navajo until the RTLA surveys in
334 1995. The RTLA surveys identified four amphibian species and five reptile species. The non-native
335 American bullfrog (*Rana catesbeiana*) has also been observed within Camp Navajo but was not
336 encountered during these surveys. In 2006, AGFD conducted amphibian surveys from 24 April to 17
337 August 2006 at 41 water sources on the Camp Navajo (Wilcox and Partridge 2007). Additionally, a
338 planning-level survey was completed in 2016 and 2017 using trap arrays, visual encounter surveys, and
339 acoustic monitoring. Amphibians encountered on Camp Navajo during the most recent planning-level
340 survey included barred tiger salamander (*Ambystoma mavortium*), Arizona treefrog (*Hyla wrightorum*),
341 western chorus frog (*Pseudacris triseriata*), Mexican spadefoot (*Spea multiplicata*), and plateau lizard
342 (*Sceloporus tristichus*). An Arizona toad (*Anaxyrus microscaphus*) was found during RTLA surveys in 1994
343 on a bank of Volunteer Canyon. It had been dislodged from the soil by animal traffic (TRIES 1996; Wilcox
344 and Partridge 2007). The Arizona toad is a Tier 1 species of greatest conservation need (SGCN) (AGFD
345 2012). For a completed list of herpetofauna found on Camp Navajo see **Appendix D**.

346 **5.4.5 Insects**

347 Over 236 invertebrate species have been identified on Camp Navajo (**Appendix D**). Surveys identified
348 four species of springtails (Order Collembola), six species of dragonflies and damselflies (Order
349 Odonata), 11 grasshoppers and cricket species (Order Orthoptera), 14 species of true bugs (Order
350 Hemiptera), and 14 species of cicada, hopper, aphid, and scale (Order Homoptera). Forty-one species of
351 beetles (Order Coleoptera) were identified, along with 36 species of flies (Order Diptera) and 65 species
352 of moths, skippers, and butterflies (Order Lepidoptera). Twenty-three species of wasps, hornets, bees,
353 and ants (Order Hymenoptera) were also identified. The other 22 species found are in other various
354 orders (**Appendix D**). Over 100 of these species were found in Volunteer Canyon. Various tanks around
355 the installation also provide suitable habitat for many invertebrates. Several invertebrate species inhabit
356 the entire installation and are not limited to a particular habitat type (NAU 1996).

357 **5.4.6 Mollusks and Crustaceans**

358 Four mollusk species and one crustacean species were identified during RTLA surveys (**Appendix D**).
359 Mollusks included eared pond snails (*Radix auricularia*), marsh pond snails (*Stagnicola* spp.), orb snails
360 (*Helisoma* spp.), and pouch snails (*Physella zionis*). An additional inventory was conducted in 2012 at
361 Tappen Springs, Elsie Springs, and Pipe Springs; no new mollusks or crustaceans were found. Only the
362 marsh pond snails are native to the area. Camp Navajo and AGFD cooperatively introduced crayfish
363 (*Cambarus* spp.) into Ponds 1, 2, and 3 to control aquatic vegetation and restocked them as needed
364 through 1987. Crayfish were also stocked in Elsie and Tappen springs in 1990 to control aquatic
365 vegetation. The project was successful in Pond 1 but less effective in both springs. Crayfish are no longer
366 stocked in any ponds or spring areas within Camp Navajo. Mollusks and crustaceans are an important
367 food source for shorebirds and waterfowl.

368 5.5 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES

369 Special status species include federally Listed Threatened, Listed Endangered, and SC, as well as state
 370 SGCN, and protected state plant species. Also included are eagles protected by the Bald and Golden
 371 Eagle Protection Act (BGEPA). Federal and state special status species known to occur on or near Camp
 372 Navajo are discussed in more detail below and listed in **Table 4**.

373 Threatened and endangered species are federally protected plants and animals that are in danger of
 374 becoming extinct without protection. These species may be rare because of specialized habitat needs,
 375 habitat modification, or habitat destruction. The Federal ESA of 1973 protects listed species against
 376 killing, harming, harassment, or any action that may damage their habitat.

377 The National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) of 2004 made a significant revision to the ESA of 1973:
 378 “The Secretary [of the Interior] shall not designate as critical habitat any lands or other geographical
 379 areas owned or controlled by the DoD, or designated for its use, that are subject to an INRMP prepared
 380 under Section 101 of the SAIA (16 USC 670 (a) *et seq.*), if the Secretary determines in writing that such
 381 plan provides a benefit to the species for which critical habitat is proposed for designation.” Hence,
 382 under the 2004 NDAA, a military installation may have its INRMP remove the need for critical habitat
 383 designation if the INRMP provides a benefit to listed species and manages for the long-term
 384 conservation of the species. However, at the time of the designation of MSO critical habitat in 2004,
 385 there was not a qualified INRMP in place at Camp Navajo.

386 The State of Arizona does not have an ESA for plants or animals, and therefore abides by federal listings.
 387 However, AGFD identifies elements of concern in Arizona and consolidates information about their
 388 status and distribution via the state’s Natural Heritage Program. “An element of concern can be, but is
 389 not limited to, an animal or plant with special status at the federal, tribal, or state level, or a specific
 390 habitat necessary for its survival” (AGFD 2012).

TABLE 4 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES DOCUMENTED ON OR WITHIN 5 MILES OF CAMP NAVAJO, BELLEMONT, ARIZONA			
Scientific Name	Common Name	Federal Status ¹	State Status ²
<i>Accipiter gentilis</i>	Northern goshawk	SC	SGCN
<i>Agave utahensis</i> var. <i>utahensis</i>	Utah agave		SR
<i>Allium bisceptrum</i> var. <i>palmeri</i>	Patis onion		SR
<i>Allium cernuum</i> var. <i>obtusum</i>	Nodding onion		SR
<i>Allium geyeri</i> var. <i>geyeri</i>	Geyer’s onion		SR
<i>Anaxyrus microscaphus</i>	Arizona toad	SC	SGCN
<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	Golden eagle	BGEPA	SGCN
<i>Aquilegia chrysantha</i>	Golden columbine		SR
<i>Aquilegia desertorum</i>	Mogollon columbine ³		SR
<i>Buteo regalis</i>	Ferruginous hawk	SC	SGCN
<i>Calochortus nuttallii</i>	Sego lily		SR

TABLE 4 SPECIAL STATUS SPECIES DOCUMENTED ON OR WITHIN 5 MILES OF CAMP NAVAJO, BELLEMONT, ARIZONA			
Scientific Name	Common Name	Federal Status ¹	State Status ²
<i>Clematis hirsutissima</i>	Arizona clematis		HS
<i>Cynomys gunnisoni</i>	Gunnison's prairie dog	SC	SGCN
<i>Echeandia flavescens</i>	Torrey's crag lily		SR
<i>Echinocereus triglochidiatus</i> var. <i>melanacanthus</i>	Kingcup cactus		SR
<i>Falco peregrinus anatum</i>	American peregrine falcon	SC	SGCN
<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>	Bald eagle	SC, BGEPA	SGCN
<i>Hedeoma diffusa</i>	Flagstaff false pennyroyal ³		SR
<i>Idionycteris phyllotis</i>	Allen's lappet-browed Bat	SC	SGCN
<i>Lithobates pipiens</i>	Northern leopard frog		SGCN
<i>Maianthemum racemosum</i>	Western Solomon's seal		SR
<i>Maianthemum stellatum</i>	Starry false Solomon's seal		SR
<i>Microtus mexicanus</i>	Navajo Mexican vole		SGCN
<i>Myotis evotis</i>	Long-eared myotis	SC	SGCN
<i>Myotis occultus</i>	Arizona myotis	SC	SGCN
<i>Myotis thysanodes</i>	Fringed myotis	SC	
<i>Myotis volans</i>	Long-legged myotis	SC	
<i>Nyctinomops macrotis</i>	Big free-tailed bat ³	SC	
<i>Opuntia macrorhiza</i> var. <i>pottsii</i>	Twistpine prickly pear		SR
<i>Phacelia serrata</i>	Cinder phacelia ³	SC	
<i>Pheneranthus validulus</i>	Tusayan flameflower ³	SC	SR
<i>Prosartes</i> or <i>Disporum trachycarpum</i>	Roughfruit fairybells		SR
<i>Strix occidentalis lucida</i>	Mexican spotted owl	LT	SGCN
<i>Tadarida brasiliensis</i>	Brazilian free-tailed bat ³		SGCN
<i>Zigadenus elegans</i>	Mountain death camas		SR

391 ¹ Federal Status Definitions:

392 **LT Listed Threatened.** Species protected under the ESA as being in imminent jeopardy of
393 becoming endangered.

394 **SC Species of Concern.** The terms "Species of Concern" or "Species at Risk" should be considered
395 as terms-of-art that describe the entire realm of taxa whose conservation status may be of
396 concern to the USFWS, but neither term has official status (generally all former C2 species).

397 **BGEPA Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act.** Eagles are federally protected under this Federal Act.

398 ² State Status Definitions:

- 399 **SGCN** **Species of Greatest Conservation Need.** Species that the AGFD identified as most in need of
400 conservation actions in the state.
- 401 **HS** **Highly Safeguarded.** Arizona native plants whose prospects for survival in Arizona are at risk,
402 as described by the ANPL (1993). Included are those species of native plants and parts of
403 plants, including the seeds and fruit, whose prospects for survival in this state are in jeopardy
404 or which are in danger of extinction throughout all or a significant portion of their ranges, and
405 those native plants which are likely within the foreseeable future to become jeopardized or in
406 danger of extinction throughout all or a significant portion of their ranges. Collection is only
407 allowed with a permit.
- 408 **SR** **Salvage Restricted.** Arizona native plants whose prospects for survival in Arizona are at risk, as
409 described by the ANPL (1993). Included are those native plants which are not included in the
410 HS category but are nevertheless subject to a high potential for damage by theft or vandalism
411 Collection is only allowed with a permit.

412 ³ Within species range, but never recorded on the installation

413 Sources: HEG 2001, 2005a, and 2005b; Springer et al. 2011; AGFD 2018

414 **5.5.1 Federal Special Status Species (Fauna)**

415 5.5.1.1 Mexican Spotted Owl (LT, SGCN)

416 This INRMP is intended to provide a benefit to the MSO and its critical habitat. Actions that result in a
417 benefit to the MSO and its habitat are addressed in this plan. In the future, this INRMP may be used to
418 obtain an exemption from any proposed re-designation of critical habitat for the MSO or critical habitat
419 designation for other species on Camp Navajo per Section 101 of the SAIA.

420 Due to alteration and fragmentation of their habitat and the threat of high-severity and stand-replacing
421 forest fires to old growth forest, MSO have experienced declines across their occurrence range. In
422 response to these declines in MSO populations, the species was federally listed as threatened
423 throughout its range on 16 March 1993 (USFWS 1993). The most recent critical-habitat designation for
424 the species was published on 31 August 2004 (USFWS 2004). The MSO recovery plan, which outlines
425 steps to recover the species, was approved in 1995 and updated and reapproved 2012 (USFWS 1995a,
426 2012). The 2012 recovery plan recommended that land managers work to reduce the primary threat to
427 the species: catastrophic wildfire.

428 The recovery plan identifies five Ecological Management Units (EMUs), based mainly on recognized
429 physiographic provinces and biotic regimes within the species range. Camp Navajo is within the Upper
430 Gila Management Zone (UGM) EMU, which is primarily on the Upper Gila Mountain Forest Province
431 (Bailey 1995) but also includes the southern end of the Colorado Plateau Ecoregion. This UGM includes
432 the largest concentration of MSO in Arizona (Ward et al. 1995).

433 In addition to critical habitat, other types of important MSO habitat are Protected Activity Centers
434 (PACs) and recovery habitat. A PAC is delineated around known owl sites. A PAC is a minimum of 600
435 acres (243 hectares) that includes the best nesting and roosting (i.e., resting) habitat in the area. Within
436 each PAC, the USFWS recommends that land managers delineate a 100-acre “activity center” around
437 the nest/roost grove(s) used during the breeding season. Recovery habitat provides additional areas

438 appropriate for nesting, roosting, foraging, dispersal, and other life history needs. Recovery habitats
439 include unoccupied areas in mixed-conifer, pine-oak, and riparian forests and/or rocky canyons.

440 Currently there are four designated PACs on Camp Navajo. In 1997 the Volunteer Canyon PAC (No.
441 040211) was established just south of Camp Navajo by the Coconino National Forest in accordance with
442 recovery plan guidelines (USFWS 1995b). Designated critical habitat associated with the Volunteer
443 Canyon PAC includes 2,037 acres within the southern portion of Camp Navajo (**Appendix A, Figure 10**).
444 The critical habitat extends south of Camp Navajo and is part of the UGM EMU.

445 In 2003 the Volunteer Canyon PAC was modified in response to data provided from Coconino National
446 Forest and the AZARNG survey data. In 2018, the Volunteer Canyon PAC was split into the Blue Spruce
447 PAC (Camp Navajo) and the Volunteer Canyon PAC (Coconino National Forest). The split occurred in
448 response to confirmation of two separate MSO pairs, one located on Camp Navajo and the other on
449 Coconino National Forest. The Blue Spruce PAC boundary currently extends onto Coconino National
450 Forest (**Appendix A, Figure 10**) and is managed cooperatively between the Coconino National Forest,
451 NGB, and the AZARNG. The 2012 surveys identified a pair of MSO on Volunteer Mountain, resulting in a
452 600-acre PAC designation. In 2014, a pair was located in the east buffer and the Tappen Springs PAC was
453 designated. Finally, in 2016, a pair was located south of Volunteer Mountain and the Jeep Trail PAC was
454 designated (**Appendix A, Figure 10**).

455 5.5.1.2 Bald Eagle (BGEPA, SC, SGCN)

456 The bald eagle is categorized by the USFWS as a SC, by the AGFD as state wildlife of special concern, and
457 by the USFS as a sensitive species. It also remains protected under the BGEPA. Bald eagles are found
458 near lakes, reservoirs, and perennial rivers and streams throughout central Arizona (Corman and Wise-
459 Gervais 2005). Wintering eagles occur throughout the state, with the majority found along the Mogollon
460 Rim eastward through the White Mountains. Between 220 and 325 eagles winter in Arizona every year
461 (AGFD 2011a; McCarty et al. 2018).

462 Bald eagles are present on Camp Navajo throughout the year (Bayless and Ingraldi 2004; TRIES 1996).
463 AGFD has documented a pair nesting on Whitehorse Lake approximately 7 miles southwest of Camp
464 Navajo. Bald eagles are not known to breed on Camp Navajo. In 2005 three bald eagles fitted with solar-
465 powered GPS satellite transmitters were documented utilizing 69 day locations and 15 night locations
466 within the Camp Navajo boundary (Bayless et al. 2007). In 2009 another three eagles were fitted with
467 transmitters and their movements were tracked. Additional night and roosts were identified in 2009 and
468 2012 using the same transmitter data by two NAU graduate student researchers (Joshi 2009; Zyllo 2012).

469 5.5.1.3 Golden Eagle (BGEPA)

470 The golden eagle is protected under the BGEPA and is categorized by the AGFD as state wildlife of
471 special concern. Golden eagles are normally found in open country, especially in hilly and mountainous
472 regions. In Arizona they nest on rock ledges, cliffs, or in large trees at elevations between 4,000 to
473 10,000 feet (AGFD 2002).

474 Golden eagles are known to be present on Camp Navajo, although they are found infrequently and in
475 low numbers. They are normally identified during the annual winter raptor surveys.

476 5.5.1.4 Northern Goshawk (SC, SGCN)

477 The northern goshawk is listed by the USFWS as an SC, by the AGFD as state wildlife of special concern,
478 and by the USFS as a sensitive species. The northern goshawk in Arizona is most commonly found in
479 ponderosa pine forests along the Mogollon Rim and on the Kaibab Plateau and in the southeastern
480 mountains (AGFD 2003a). Northern goshawks occasionally breed in oak forests at elevations as low as
481 4,900 feet in the southeastern portion of the state (Glinski 1998).

482 Northern goshawks generally forage in the lower portions of the canopy zone of forests that have high
483 canopy cover. Birds are their primary prey, but mammals are also eaten. Northern goshawks commonly
484 take prey as large as band-tailed pigeons and cottontails (AGFD 2003a).

485 The AGFD conducted a northern goshawk inventory according to the USFS Southwestern Region's
486 northern goshawk inventory protocol (Joy et al. 1994; Kennedy and Stahlecker 1991) of approximately
487 4,900 acres of forested areas within Camp Navajo in 2000 (Ingraldi 2000). AGFD located one active
488 historical nesting territory along the western boundary on the installation near Volunteer Mountain, and
489 two male northern goshawk nestlings were banded. One northern goshawk nesting territory was
490 documented on the installation's southern boundary in the designated critical habitat for the MSO. The
491 proximity of the nest to the Coconino National Forest/Camp Navajo boundary suggests the range of this
492 nesting pair likely includes lands under jurisdiction by both the AZARNG and the USFS.

493 During surveys in July 2005, a juvenile responded to broadcast begging calls, and an active nest was
494 located approximately 655 feet west of the installation boundary in the Kaibab National Forest (Nabel
495 2005). Surveys were conducted in 2010 and 2011 at historical nest sites, Post-fledging Family Areas
496 (PFA), and nearby potential habitat. No northern goshawks were detected within historical nest sites,
497 PFAs, or within the western portion of the installation. An adult male goshawk was detected in 2010
498 within the ponderosa pine forest along the eastern portion of the installation.

499 5.5.1.5 Ferruginous Hawk (SC, SGCN)

500 The ferruginous hawk is found primarily at elevations of 3,500 to 6,000 feet. In Arizona, they use open
501 scrublands and woodlands, grasslands, agricultural lands, and semi-desert grassland in the northern and
502 southeastern parts of the state. Breeding populations are found in northern Arizona on the Colorado
503 Plateau (AGFD 2003a). During winter, they select similar areas. Hunting areas are typically open
504 grasslands, preferably those dotted with suitable low hills or short trees, which serve as perches (Hall et
505 al. 1988). The ferruginous hawk is listed by the USFWS as an SC and by the USFS as a sensitive species.
506 This species has been recorded on Camp Navajo during winter raptor surveys in the open grasslands
507 (AZARNG 2011).

508 5.5.1.6 American Peregrine Falcon (SC, SGCN)

509 The American peregrine falcon is found near steep cliffs that support sufficient prey. In urban settings,
510 they choose to roost high up on tall buildings where abundant food is present (e.g., pigeons and doves).
511 Prey items also occasionally include bats. Arizona's peregrines are being found in areas that would have
512 formerly been considered marginal, suggesting that populations may have reached levels saturating the
513 optimal habitat available, and new breeding pairs are forced to breed in sub-optimal areas (AGFD
514 2003a). The American peregrine falcon is listed by the USFWS as an SC and has been recorded at Camp
515 Navajo during winter months (AZARNG 2011).

516 5.5.1.7 Arizona Toad (SC, SGCN)

517 The Arizona toad is found in primarily in east and west central Arizona with populations found in
518 canyons and flood plains near the Mogollon Rim. Habitat includes rocky streams and canyons in pine-
519 oak forest types. The Arizona toad is a USFWS SC, and a single individual was recorded in Volunteer
520 Canyon (TRIES 1996) in 2004.

521 5.5.1.8 Mexican Vole (SGCN)

522 The Mexican vole (*Microtus mexicanus*) is found in dense thickets of a variety of shrubs that provide
523 cover, high litter, and bare ground as well as in dry, grassy areas adjacent to ponderosa pine forests at
524 elevations from 3,800 to 9,700 feet (AGFD 2003b). Reproductive activities occur throughout most of the
525 year, but peak breeding occurs from May through October (AGFD 2003b). The Mexican vole is
526 categorized by the AGFD as state wildlife of special concern. This species occurs at Camp Navajo (TRIES
527 1996).

528 5.5.1.9 Gunnison's Prairie Dog (SC, SGCN)

529 Gunnison's prairie dogs (*Cynomys gunnisoni*) are found in open grasslands and shrub lands at elevations
530 from 6,000 to 12,000 feet. Gunnison's prairie dogs are considered a keystone species because they
531 create habitat, provide food, and help keep the soil and plant communities healthy. Gunnison's prairie
532 dogs are categorized by the USFWS as an SC and by the AGFD as state wildlife of special concern. This
533 species occurs at Camp Navajo (TRIES 1996) and established colonies are found within the PCPA, ASA,
534 and small arms range complex.

535 5.5.1.10 Allen's lappet-browed bat (SC)

536 Allen's lappet-browed bat (*Idonycteris phyllotis*) is found most often in ponderosa pine, pinyon-juniper,
537 Mexican woodland, and riparian areas with sycamores (*Platanus* spp.), cottonwoods (*Populus* spp.), and
538 willows (*Salix* spp.) from 1,320 to 9,800 feet (AGFD 2001). Allen's big-eared bats are often found along
539 streams or over ponds where they may be seeking insects, water, or both. Allen's big-eared bats feed
540 primarily on soft-bodied insects, with small moths being their primary food. Prey is gleaned from
541 surfaces or pursued and taken in flight (AGFD 2001). They have been known to roost in caves,
542 abandoned mine shafts, near cliffs, lava tubes, and under tree bark of large ponderosa pine snags (AGFD
543 2011a–e; Hoffmeister 1986; Rabe et al. 1999). This species is known to occur on Camp Navajo.

544 5.5.1.11 Long-eared Myotis (SC, SGCN)

545 The long-eared myotis (*Myotis evotis*) is found in coniferous forests along the Kaibab Plateau, Mogollon
546 Plateau, and Chiricahua Mountains. They have been known to roost in hollow trees, behind loose slabs
547 of bark, among the timbers of an unused railroad trestle, in caves, mines, fissures in cliffs, abandoned
548 buildings, and sink holes. This species usually roosts in caves during cold weather (AGFD 2011b). Long-
549 eared myotis typically feed on moths and other soft-bodied insects.

550 5.5.1.12 Arizona Myotis (SC, SGCN)

551 The Arizona myotis (*Myotis occultus*) is found at elevations from 6,000 to 9,200 feet in ponderosa pine
552 and oak-pine woodlands near water. They also may be found along permanent water or in riparian
553 forests in some desert areas (AGFD 2011c). Colonies of these bats have been found in buildings and in
554 crevices and between timbers of highway bridges (AGFD 2011c). The Arizona myotis generally forages

555 over water and eats flying insects, including mosquitoes and midges. These bats generally roost near a
556 water source (Hoffmeister 1986).

557 5.5.1.13 Fringed Myotis (SC)

558 The preferred habitat of the fringed myotis (*Myotis thysanodes*) is oak woodland/ponderosa
559 pine/pinyon-juniper vegetation at elevations from 4,000 to 8,437 feet, from which they forage in a
560 variety of other habitats from chaparral to ponderosa pine forests (Hoffmeister 1986). Fringed myotis
561 tend to roost in the open in tightly packed groups within buildings and also have been found in caves,
562 mine tunnels, rock crevices, and ponderosa pine and Douglas fir snags (AGFD 2011d). Reproducing
563 females have been found roosting in ponderosa pine and Douglas fir snags within the Coconino National
564 Forest (Rabe et al. 1999). Fringed myotis eat mostly beetles, but moths also are taken.

565 5.5.1.14 Long-legged Myotis (SC)

566 The long-legged myotis (*Myotis volans*) is found in conifer forests from elevations of 6,000 to 10,000
567 feet, but it also uses riparian and desert habitats (AGFD 2011e). The long-legged myotis is active most of
568 the night, and it commonly forages 10 to 15 feet over water and in openings in woods. It most often
569 consumes moths but also takes flies, termites, lacewings, wasps, small beetles, and other insects (AGFD
570 2011e). This species utilizes a variety of roosts, including abandoned buildings, cracks in the ground,
571 crevices in cliff faces, and spaces behind exfoliating tree bark. Caves and mine tunnels are used as
572 hibernacula (AGFD 2011e).

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SECTION 6 MISSION IMPACTS ON NATURAL RESOURCES

6.1 CURRENT AREAS OF IMPACT

The existing conditions of Camp Navajo serve as the basis to evaluate potential environmental impacts from future mission training. Affected environments that warrant analysis include cultural, biological, geological, soil, surface water and groundwater, air quality, solid, hazardous and special wastes, noise, and public health and safety. As Camp Navajo is primarily a training and munition storage facility, natural resource management of the installation focuses on increasing the diversity of habitats for training and mitigating the risk of catastrophic events that may cause interruptions to trainings or munition storage. Therefore, management has and will continue to focus on tailoring the installation in beneficial ways to accomplish these goals. The paragraphs to follow describe how the current management of Camp Navajo's natural resources is shaped by the needs and operations of Camp Navajo and detail some of the impacts associated with this need.

6.1.1 Geology and Soils

6.1.1.1 Geology/Mineral Resources

Geological materials are currently used to generate roads and buildings in Camp Navajo. Cinders and limestone have been mined and used as building materials. One limestone pit (~ 10 acres) and one cinder pit (~12 acres) are located in the ASA. One cinder pit (~30 acres) is located within the western buffer area. Material from the cinder pits are mainly used for road maintenance.

6.1.1.2 Soils

Seventeen soil units were identified on Camp Navajo (**Appendix A, Figure 5**). Soils have been subject to compaction and erosion in the highly disturbed portions of Camp Navajo. Soils associated with live fire ranges may have been contaminated with lead from ammunition. The DoD utilizes the Operational Range Assessment Program to monitor soil contaminants, including sub-surface migration. Range closure protocols at Camp Navajo are in accordance with the Military Munitions Response Program. This program provides remediation resources and stipulates collaboration with ADEQ for potential soil contaminants, in situ or migratory, within a given range's footprint or surface danger zone (Wilkinson 2013).

6.1.2 Water Resources

Currently there have been minimal effects to Camp Navajo's water resources, and water resources are minimally managed to avoid impacts other than through the implementation of general best management practices (BMPs) such as check dams and spill management plans around the installation.

Several ephemeral streams, natural springs, and wetlands are found on Camp Navajo (**Appendix A, Figure 6**). As these areas have the potential to be protected under the CWA (see Section 4.4.3) and contain unique plants and habitat for wildlife (see Section 7.5.4) many are identified and protected from disturbance when possible. Specifically, Pond 1, Johnson Tank, and Atherton Lake are maintained for fish and waterfowl habitat. To limit contamination to these ecologically important resources, which is most likely to come from vehicles and equipment used for training and road maintenance, Camp Navajo follows the spill prevention and control procedures which are detailed in the Camp Navajo Spill

39 Prevention Control and Countermeasure Plan (SPCCP) (AZARNG 2019) as required by the Title 40 Code
40 of Federal Regulations (CFR) §112.

41 **6.1.3 Biological Resources**

42 Camp Navajo takes a variety of steps to minimize impacts on biological resources while supporting the
43 INRMP. Particularly, certain regions around the installation are targeted for management or avoided in
44 order to best facilitate ecological resiliency and Camp Navajo's mission. This scientifically informed and
45 targeted management of Camp Navajo land serves the installation in two ways: 1) targeted treatment
46 allows for better enhancement of the ecosystem health and 2) creating a variety of habitats better
47 facilitates its ability to provide more diverse training opportunities for troops.

48 6.1.3.1 Vegetation

49 The AZARNG identified four significant vegetation communities within Camp Navajo. Management of
50 these communities aims to maintain and improve the sustainability and biological diversity of terrestrial
51 ecosystems while supporting sustainable economies, human use, and the environment required for
52 realistic military training. The four significant vegetation communities on the installation are forested
53 stands, meadows/grasslands, Volunteer Canyon, and Volunteer Mountain. The forested stands in the
54 east and west buffer areas are managed for training, wildlife habitat, and forest restoration. Natural
55 resource management for the meadows/grasslands in the buffer areas is focused on training and wildlife
56 habitat. The Volunteer Canyon and Volunteer Mountain are managed for wildlife habitat.

57 Camp Navajo's forest restoration treatments (mechanical thinning and prescribed burns) occurred
58 primarily in the west buffer (2005 to 2020) but will expand to the ASA and east buffer in the future.
59 These treatments are targeted to reduce stand density, reduce ladder fuels, increase canopy gaps, and
60 restore historical frequent but low-intensity fire regimes. The meadows/grasslands area is set to be
61 restored in future projects, primarily through prescribed burns and seeding of native vegetation. Natural
62 resource managers will coordinate with training operations to minimize any conflicts.

63 Disturbances to these vegetation communities have typically come from bivouac sites, road
64 improvements, and training maneuvers, which increase the potential for the establishment and spread
65 of invasive and noxious weed species. Invasive plants act as aggressive colonizers where native
66 vegetation has been disturbed or displaced, resulting in a loss of plant diversity. If noxious weeds are
67 found, control and eradication measures will be implemented as outlined in the IPMP (AZARNG 2013a).
68 Mitigation measures will be implemented when needed to decrease the loss of vegetation, especially
69 areas with sensitive plant species (See Section 5.5).

70 6.1.3.2 Wildlife

71 Camp Navajo has conducted a variety of surveys and studies on the effects of their operations and
72 management strategies on wildlife. Though minimal restrictions are present to limit operations in
73 regards to the studied species (such as tree roosting bats, tassel-eared squirrels, and Gunnison's prairie
74 dog), research has resulted in the implementation of BMPs to reduce the effects on wildlife when
75 possible and thus minimize the overall effect of training and management practices on the ecosystems.
76 The implementation of mitigation measures to reduce harm to wildlife usually involve avoiding select
77 areas, protecting individual resources, and installing certain features that do not regularly alter troop
78 mission training.

79 Fencing around Camp Navajo is one example of Camp Navajo's efforts to simultaneously address
80 mission needs and wildlife management. Camp Navajo needs fences for safety and security purposes.
81 Fences restrict the movement of larger mammals such as elk, deer, and pronghorn and can lead to
82 animals getting trapped. To reduce the impact of these fences on wildlife migration patterns, numerous
83 elk jumps have been installed in the outer perimeter on the east, south, and west sides of the
84 installation. Wildlife-friendly fences are installed when repairing or replacing existing fences. Elk and
85 deer attempt to cross the railroad tracks and I-40 highway north of the installation. Fences in this area
86 have no wildlife crossings because of potential security threats from this heavily traveled installation
87 boundary.

88 6.1.3.3 Special Status Species

89 Camp Navajo avoids disturbances to MSO PACs during breeding season (**Appendix F**). When possible,
90 Camp Navajo has also set up restrictions to operations near the roosts and nests of migratory birds and
91 bald eagles to minimize harm and comply with federal laws. These specific restrictions are discussed
92 further in Section 7.

93 Eleven special status species were identified by AGFD and USFWS databases that are known to occur in
94 the vicinity of Camp Navajo (**Table 3**). Additional information on plant and wildlife SC is found in *Section*
95 *5.5 Special Status Species*.

96 **6.2 POTENTIAL FUTURE IMPACTS**

97 Based on Camp Navajo's previous utilization of its natural resources and its management plans, this
98 section discusses the potential environmental impacts of future missions on local and regional natural
99 areas and threatened and endangered species habitat. Future impacts include projected changes in
100 missions, BRAC activities, and activities outlined in the AZARNG Camp Navajo Vision Plan (2017).

101 **6.2.1 Soils**

102 Travel on military roads/trails, troop movement, and use of staging areas and bivouac sites are part of
103 the military mission at Camp Navajo. These activities could result in increased soil damage and
104 vegetation loss as operations expand in addition to natural soil losses from rainfall, runoff, and wind
105 erosion. Roads are the largest source of soil erosion on the installation while most of the installation's
106 future plans outlined in the AZARNG Camp Navajo Vision Plan (2017) include road improvements and
107 expansions. Maintenance of existing roads/trails associated with mechanical thinning operations is
108 expected to improve drainage features and reduce soil erosion. Soil may also become contaminated
109 from unintended, accidental, or uncontrolled releases of chemicals used for pest management, vehicles,
110 and/or mechanical equipment. BMPs, as detailed in the IPMP and Camp Navajo SPCCP, are currently
111 being used to mitigate releases to the environment (AZARNG 2019). Lead will continue to accumulate
112 and contaminate soils within firing ranges.

113 BMPs for soil and water conservation are routinely incorporated into site-specific project plans,
114 including forest and grassland treatments. Project-specific BMPs are developed from a variety of
115 sources, including the USFS and the Arizona Department of Transportation, which identify standard
116 practices (ADOT 2012; USDA 4FRI 2010). Specific BMPs used by the installation can be found in
117 **Appendix J**.

118 **6.2.2 Water Resources.**

119 Future water contamination on the installation is most likely to occur from soil erosion or from
120 chemicals used in pest control or vehicles and mechanical equipment. Accumulation of polluted
121 stormwater or sewage water and point-source and non-point-source pollutants may threaten water
122 tables and potable water sources.

123 Water resources have potential to be impacted from the forest thinning and burning operations due to
124 the increase of erosion during forest operations; however, over the long term these operations would
125 have a positive effect on water resources as well as overall ecosystem health by reducing the potential
126 for catastrophic wildfires.

127 Camp Navajo is in an arid region with a growing human population; well construction and ground water
128 pumping both on and off the installation may reduce the quantity of Camp Navajo's groundwater
129 resources. The numerous BMPs that the installation implements to reduce effects on water resources
130 will help minimize some of these issues.

131 **6.2.3 Biological Resources**

132 Current and future operations focus on adapting the Camp Navajo biological environment in a way that
133 maximizes troop usability while promoting environmental sustainability. The main driver behind most of
134 these actions is the need to minimize catastrophic wildland fire impacts on Camp Navajo operations.
135 Current and future projects, particularly those addressed in **Appendix E**, **Appendix F**, and **Appendix G**,
136 are intended to decrease overall wildland fire risk and thus, minimize interruptions to Camp Navajo
137 operations. Per the USFS's definition, forest treatments, or mechanical treatments, involve "reducing
138 the amount of vegetation which has built up to dangerous levels, or changing the arrangement of these
139 fuels in the environment." Forest treatments such as mechanical thinning and prescribed burning will
140 continue to be used to accomplish this goal, targeting areas that are commonly used for training (such
141 as the west buffer area) and have high forest densities. Overall, fire behavior models run in conjunction
142 with the proposed action estimated an 88 percent decrease in predicted active crown fire, a 41 percent
143 decrease in passive fire, and a 23 percent increase in surface fire (Horncastle et al. 2011). Treating these
144 areas is anticipated to decrease large-scale fire in the area and increase forest resiliency and stability,
145 protecting the environmental and human usages of Camp Navajo. Restoration of meadows/grassland
146 areas on the property will be used to create open spaces for troop maneuvering while also restoring
147 historic tree patterns. The proposed forest treatments will help facilitate Camp Navajo's goals of
148 providing a varied training ground while increasing forest resiliency and function. Treated areas would
149 experience temporary reductions in herbaceous ground cover resulting from disturbance associated
150 with mechanical harvesting equipment and burning operations on 18,652 acres. Disturbances from
151 forest treatments would have the indirect impact of increasing the potential for the establishment and
152 spread of invasive and noxious weed species. BMPs would be implemented to reduce the level of
153 temporary disturbance. As **Appendix F** describes, burning and thinning operations will be implemented
154 after detailed burn plans are developed, thus future treatments can likely be coordinated around
155 training and installation needs.

156 Military training and construction activities may affect biological resources through displacement, the
157 movement of wildlife away from a habitat. As training and construction activities occur only
158 intermittently on Camp Navajo, short-term impacts to wildlife are likely minimal. Wildlife typically move

159 back into disturbed areas shortly after training ceases and thus, training activities appear to cause little
160 or no long-term impact to wildlife (NADA 1987b). Other unfavorable effects from military use include
161 noise disturbance from vehicular and aircraft use, weapon discharge during training activities, and troop
162 movement. Noise disturbance likely has the greatest effect during the spring, during the bird breeding
163 season and the calving season for elk and pronghorn.

164 **6.2.4 Air Quality**

165 Generation of air pollution may occur through wind erosion, ground disturbance, exhaust from vehicles,
166 off-road machinery, internal combustion engines, demolition/renovations, facility equipment, and
167 smoke emissions (Particulate Matter less than 2.5 microns in diameter [PM_{2.5}]) from prescribed fires.
168 Additional dust, PM_{2.5}, and chemical emissions occur from the detonation of ordinance and arms fire.
169 Generation of PM_{2.5} pollutants from wildfire (on-site and off-site) is both unpredictable and likely to
170 affect Camp Navajo in the future.

171 **6.3 NATURAL RESOURCES NEEDED TO SUPPORT THE MILITARY MISSION**

172 Realistic training lands and sustainable, functional ecosystems are essential to the military mission. The
173 17,000-acre training-area portion of Camp Navajo contains a variety of flora and climatic conditions that
174 mimic many natural field conditions that may be found upon troop deployment. The components
175 needed to maintain the functional military training landscape are defined on many levels; like all
176 biological organisms, troops need clean drinking water, clean air, food, and shelter. Soldiers require
177 training lands to support proficiency and living quarters free from risk of chemical and radiation
178 contamination and from dangerous pests and disease.

179 Natural structural diversity is essential to offer the full array of training, from open areas for vehicle and
180 troop maneuvers and firing ranges, to areas of dense vegetation for concealment. Stable soils are
181 needed to keep dust to a minimum during maneuvers as well as to maintain the integrity of roads and
182 trails used to transport troops and equipment across the installation. Degraded ecosystems may lose
183 their functionality and result in a loss of training realism. Degradation of ecosystems conflicts with the
184 military's commitment to the "no net loss in the capability of training lands to support the military
185 mission" policy. The future of Camp Navajo and its military mission depend on maintaining functional
186 ecosystems.

187 Per Camp Navajo's 2017 Vision Plan, the installation's infrastructure needs are not expected to change
188 excessively in a way that would require severe alteration of its natural resources. Most future expansion
189 and improvements are slated around enhancement of the Cantonment Area, the most developed area,
190 with select other improvements around the site, particularly of note being road enhancements around
191 Camp Navajo to facilitate travel to training sites. Two new training facilities are proposed for the
192 southeast quadrant of the installation, an Infantry Squad Battle Course and a Multi-Purpose Machine
193 Gun facility, both of which would involve live firing. The location of both facilities is anticipated to be
194 outside the MSO PACs and other notable natural constraints and, per the 2013 Noise Operational
195 Management Plan, likely would not lead to a significant increase in disruptive noise at the installation.

196 **6.4 NATURAL RESOURCE CONSTRAINTS TO MISSIONS AND PLANNING**

197 **6.4.1 Special Status Species**

198 There are both spatial and temporal constraints to the future military mission planning due to special
199 status plant and animal species being present on the installation (**Appendix A, Figure 14**) (Section 7.4.3).
200 In most cases it is easier and more cost-effective to limit the use of special areas to minimize damage or
201 disturbance than to mitigate damage, thus Camp Navajo trends toward avoiding areas of special
202 consideration.

203 Regions such as Volunteer Canyon, Volunteer Mountain, the wildlife migration corridor along the
204 eastern boundary (**Appendix A, Figure 14**), and special areas such as meadows, ephemeral streams,
205 natural springs, and wetlands provide a variety of benefits to the ecosystems of Camp Navajo; therefore,
206 Camp Navajo follows specific restrictions in their usage. More details on the current restrictions to their
207 access can be found in Section 7, though Camp Navajo overall attempts to limit disturbance to these
208 regions as much as possible.

209 As detailed in AZARNG Camp Navajo's 2017 Master Plan, these areas of biological importance and other
210 resource constraints such as waterways are mapped out and were considered in the development and
211 choosing of where future projects can occur.

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SECTION 7 NATURAL RESOURCES PROGRAM MANAGEMENT

7.1 NATURAL RESOURCES PROGRAM MANAGEMENT

Camp Navajo implements a variety of management strategies and techniques to protect and manage its natural resources in compliance with regulations and keeping in line with the installation's mission. Camp Navajo conducts wildlife surveys and studies to inform management and subsequent mitigation measures and BMPs. These efforts help the installation protect and utilize their natural resources. A summary of Camp Navajo's management plans and strategies ranging from Integrated Training Area Management (ITAM), wildlife management, fire management, forest management, and endangered species management strategies can be found in the sections below.

7.1.1 Integrated Training Area Management

The ITAM Program is one of two core programs in the Army's Sustainable Range Program (SRP) under the direction of the Headquarters Department of the Army Military Operations Training Simulation Division. ITAM was designed to achieve optimum, sustainable use of training by implementing a uniform land management program to ensure no net loss of training capabilities. Program proponentcy for ITAM within the NGB resides with the Army Training Division. Program support is provided by the NGB ARE and the NGB Army Installations Division. The POTO is the proponent for ITAM at the headquarters of the AZARNG. ITAM personnel prepare the Range Complex Master Plan (RCMP), which depicts an installation's current range and training land assets, general siting of future range complex project requirements, and requirements and constraints that may impact ranges and training lands. It also describes restrictions to training, shortfalls of training land, throughput capacity, funding, and infrastructure downrange. The purpose of the RCMP is to guide the actions of ITAM in support of the military mission. The RCMP is reviewed annually and requires input from other organizations as well as the EMO. ITAM is responsible for repairing any damage done to natural resources through training and for all vegetation management required to support training. ITAM will continue to coordinate with the EMO on natural resource projects associated with the RCMP in order to maintain training areas and to protect sensitive areas. ITAM project matrix is found in **Appendix L**.

7.2 WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT AND THEIR HABITATS

The goal of wildlife management within Camp Navajo is to conserve and protect wildlife while supporting the multiple uses of the training installation. The wildlife management program will ensure that the management of wildlife populations and their habitats are consistent with acceptable scientific principals and are in compliance with the ESA and other applicable laws and regulations. Wildlife management includes habitat improvement projects (i.e., forest thinning, prescribed burning, and meadow restoration), habitat protection, special status species surveys, research on effects of human disturbance on special status species, and population trends (**Appendix A, Figure 14 and Figure 15**).

The AZARNG will focus on an ecosystem management approach for special status species at Camp Navajo. Management of these species will be proactive in preserving and maintaining populations. Maintaining a functional ecosystem will decrease the chances that these species and others will be become threatened or endangered from within their natural habitat ranges.

39 **7.2.1 Vegetation Community Map**

40 Vegetation community maps are one of the tools used by NRMs to maintain, protect, and improve
41 environmental quality, aesthetic values, and ecological relationships while supporting military missions
42 on installations. The AZARNG has developed a forest inventory map (**Appendix E**) of Camp Navajo based
43 on aerial photo interpretations along with ground-truthing of plant communities. The forest inventory
44 was completed installation wide. The map is used for mission siting, wildlife management, and forest
45 management throughout the installation and is updated as needed.

46 **7.2.2 Native Plants**

47 No single floristic survey is likely to produce a comprehensive list of species currently found within Camp
48 Navajo and therefore, continued floristic surveys will provide a method to periodically update the plant
49 species known or suspected to occur within Camp Navajo. Site-specific floral surveys will continue as
50 needed and populations of state protected native plants (**Table 1**) will be recorded using a GPS unit for
51 accurate locations to aid management of known populations.

52 **7.2.3 Fish and Wildlife Management Program**

53 Camp Navajo contains the necessary habitat components to maintain wildlife diversity and abundance.
54 Present management guidelines will maintain habitat diversity for the many species of wildlife found on
55 the installation. On-going research projects will provide real-time information to assist the AZARNG in
56 managing special areas and the species that inhabit them. When sensitive species are identified,
57 management requirements will be reviewed and modified as necessary to protect species and their
58 habitats while meeting critical military mission needs.

59 7.2.3.1 Mammals

60 A variety of small mammals occur throughout Camp Navajo. The process of identifying special areas
61 used by small mammals within the installation, and avoiding disturbance or causing minimum
62 disturbance, will maintain the integrity of these habitats. Following habitat management guidelines,
63 such as maintaining understory vegetation and woody debris, will maintain small mammal habitat.

64 In spring 2004, the AZARNG and AGFD began research on the influence of forest restoration treatments
65 on tree roosting bat communities. The research was completed in the western portion of the installation
66 where two different forest restoration treatments occurred. Artificial bat roosts were placed within two
67 forest treatment areas and in one untreated area. Bats were mist-netted at roost sites and near earthen
68 water tanks or water sources. Bat species were captured, marked, and identified (Horncastle et al.
69 2005). Information gathered from this research is used to determine bat species diversity and
70 abundance before and after forest treatments. Data also has been used to determine preferred roost
71 areas and foraging habitat within the installation. On-going monitoring will occur when funding is
72 available because of the potential negative effects of the forest treatments on bats.

73 The AZARNG and AGFD also researched the effects of forest restoration on the Abert squirrel, a key
74 species of the ponderosa pine ecosystem. This research determined the abundance (population density)
75 of Abert squirrels within forest restoration treatments and compared their abundance between restored
76 and unrestored forest areas. Squirrel counts began in 2002 to 2003 and were continued from 2006 to
77 2010 (Bayless and Ingraldi 2006).

78 In 2002, the AZARNG funded a base-wide mapping survey of Gunnison's prairie dog colonies of Camp
79 Navajo conducted by NAU. Between 2003 and 2006, the AZARNG funded research that investigated
80 Gunnison's prairie dog behavior and colony expansions or contractions. Results from this study
81 concluded the Gunnison's prairie dog behavior is not negatively affected by the use of current firing
82 ranges and/or other disturbances (i.e., construction) (Drickamer and Martz 2006). In 2013 the AZARNG
83 NRM located and surveyed the Gunnison's prairie dog colonies on Camp Navajo. The survey information
84 from 2013 was used to relocate the prairie dog population at the firing range using methods approved
85 by the Humane Society of the United States.

86 7.2.3.2 Bat Species

87 Bat species will be monitored to protect them from human disturbance and maintain suitable foraging
88 habitat under present forest management guidelines. Forest treatment plans at Camp Navajo will
89 incorporate management recommendations taken from Rabe (1997) which are compatible with, but
90 subordinate to, the conservation measures outlined for MSO (**Appendix A, Figure 14**). Two primary
91 management strategies for protecting roosting habitat are:

- 92 1. Preserve all large snags with exfoliating bark; and
- 93 2. Ensure proper forest management to provide sufficient numbers of roost sites for future use.

94 7.2.3.3 Game Management

95 Habitat for these species is in good condition on the installation. Volunteer Canyon will be maintained as
96 a wildlife area to ensure a safe travel corridor (**Appendix A, Figure 14**); other wildlife corridors on Camp
97 Navajo include areas along the eastern boundary, southern boundary, and the eastern buffer area
98 (Section 7.4.3).

99 Ground surveys for big game (elk, deer, and pronghorn) are conducted with wildlife managers from
100 AGFD and Camp Navajo NRM biennially prior to the opening of hunting season. Population trend
101 estimates and recommendations for the following years hunt are made from these counts. When
102 possible, ARNG helicopters provide support for these aerial surveys on the installation when available
103 which also provides tactical training for AZARNG pilots. Additional monitoring surveys will be conducted
104 as needed and when equipment and personnel are available.

105 Fencing is being upgraded around the perimeter of the installation and ASA. Fencing can be very
106 restrictive to the migration and movement of elk, pronghorn, and deer. To help alleviate this problem,
107 the current perimeter fence contains approximately 33 elk crossings. Additional wildlife crossing areas
108 will be identified and may be upgraded to wildlife friendly fencing using the AGFD fencing guidelines,
109 when security allows.

110 7.2.3.3.1 Hunting Program

111 Camp Navajo currently has a hunting and fishing program operated through the Department of Army's
112 (DA's) Morale Welfare and Recreation as well as the Conservation Reimbursable and Fee Collection
113 Programs Fish and Wildlife Conservation Fund (21X5095). Restrictions based on population trend
114 estimates and mission training are placed on the numbers of hunting permits and hunters allowed to
115 hunt on the installation. The training mission takes precedence over hunting. Hunting areas are subject

116 to closure during times of training. This process can prevent hunting from being used to its full potential
117 as a management tool in controlling game animal populations.

118 The AGFD and the AZARNG at Camp Navajo will meet on an annual basis to agree upon harvest
119 objectives, permit numbers, season dates, weapon types, and allocation of permits/access for elk,
120 pronghorn, mule deer, and turkey.

121 Camp Navajo lies within state Game Management Unit 6B. Camp Navajo hunting permits are offered in
122 four categories: DoD Military (defined as current or honorably retired uniformed military service
123 members), Wounded Warrior (defined as recipients of the Purple Heart or enrollees in the military's
124 Wounded Warrior Program), Disabled Veteran (defined as persons with 50 percent or greater service-
125 connected disability, as certified by the Veteran's Administration), and Other (all eligible applicants
126 including non-military and military personnel).

127 In order to hunt on the installation, individuals must apply for and receive a hunt permit for Camp
128 Navajo through the AGFD, show proof of the completion of a hunter safety course, sign a waiver of
129 liability, and receive a required safety and environmental awareness brief. The majority of hunting on
130 the facility is for the following species: elk, pronghorn (archery only), mule deer (archery only), and
131 turkey. Mountain lion hunting will be allowed for authorized hunters while actively hunting for other big
132 game. Rifle and muzzleloader hunting is allowed within the buffer area and archery-only hunting is
133 allowed within ASA. No hunting is allowed in the PCPA. Because the installation is an ammunition
134 storage depot, only current or honorably retired uniformed military service members are authorized to
135 hunt within the ASA boundary. Updated hunting policies, hunting restrictions, dates, and tag numbers
136 can be found online ([https://dema.az.gov/army-national-guard/camp-navajo/garrison-
137 operations/camp-navajo-hunting-information](https://dema.az.gov/army-national-guard/camp-navajo/garrison-operations/camp-navajo-hunting-information)). Conservation fees will continue to be collected in
138 accordance with AR 200-1. These fees are used for protection, conservation, and management of fish
139 and wildlife, including habitat improvement and related activities in accordance with Section 101 of the
140 SAIA.

141 7.2.3.3.2 *Pronghorn Harvest*

142 Based on aerial surveys, approximately 30 pronghorn forage on Camp Navajo. Pronghorn (bucks only)
143 hunting has occurred on the installation since 1994. Pronghorn spend the majority of their time in the
144 ASA on Camp Navajo; therefore, only current or honorably retired uniformed military service members
145 are authorized to hunt pronghorn.

146 7.2.3.3.3 *Mule Deer Harvest*

147 Archery hunting for mule deer has been allowed since 1994. There have been no mule deer rifle hunts
148 on Camp Navajo since 2002. Hunting opportunity for mule deer is typically offered as archery only with
149 an over-the-counter non-permit deer tag. Demand for this hunting opportunity on Camp Navajo has
150 been low. To the extent that access must be limited for archery mule deer hunting, access is allocated to
151 the following categories: Military, Wounded Warrior, Disabled Veteran, and Other. If the demand for
152 this hunting opportunity remains low the AGFD and Camp Navajo may, through mutual agreement,
153 allocate access to the various classifications of hunters such that it matches demand for the opportunity.

154 7.2.3.3.4 *Elk Harvest*

155 There is a large elk population on the installation. Approximately 700 to 900 animals use habitat on
156 Camp Navajo and only leave to go below the snow line when forage is no longer available. The elk
157 population size has remained constant over time and appears to be within the carrying capacity for the
158 installation. The current hunt structure features several stratifications for legal animals, including “Any
159 Elk” and “Antlerless Elk” seasons for general, muzzleloader, and archery-only weapon types. The
160 strategy currently emphasizes harvest of the female portion of the population. A Disabled Veteran elk
161 hunt was initiated in 1995. Archery has a regular season and a late season was added in 1996. A
162 muzzleloader season on bull elk was added in 1997. Tags are allocated among the following categories
163 of hunters: Military, Wounded Warrior, Disabled Veteran, and Other. The majority of tags are allocated
164 to military categories of hunters. An average of 75 elk per year were harvested from 2009 to 2018.

165 7.2.3.3.5 *Turkey Harvest*

166 The spring hunt is preferred by hunters, but it interferes with military training. Hunters are advised that
167 hunts may be severely restricted or entirely prevented by training activities. Fall archery hunts have
168 been allowed since 1996. Spring shotgun shooting shot tags and fall archery-only tags are allocated
169 among the following categories of hunters: Military, Wounded Warrior, Disabled Veteran, and Other.
170 The majority of tags are allocated to military categories of hunters. Hunting opportunity for fall turkey is
171 typically offered archery-only with an over-the-counter non-permit tag. Demand for this hunt
172 opportunity on Camp Navajo has typically been low. If demand for this hunt opportunity remains low,
173 AGFD and Camp Navajo may, through mutual agreement, allocate access to the various classifications of
174 hunters such that it matches demand for the opportunity.

175 7.2.3.3.6 *Small Game Harvest*

176 Small game species hunted on the installation include Abert’s squirrel, Arizona gray squirrel, red squirrel,
177 and desert cottontail. Hunting pressure is minimal for these species.

178 7.2.3.4 Fisheries Management

179 The fishing program is administered and operated through DA's Morale Welfare and Recreation. Pond 1
180 is periodically stocked with rainbow trout. AGFD issues a stocking permit and the fish are tested for
181 various parasites and viruses by the supplier according to the Arizona Department of Agriculture and
182 AGFD standards. Once a satisfactory certificate of analysis is received and approved, the fish are allowed
183 to be stocked. Because these fish are purchased with funds generated by the Morale, Welfare, and
184 Recreation funds, a state fishing license is not required to fish on the installation.

185 Due to its location within the ASA, fishing access at Pond 1 is subject to closure at any time if in conflict
186 with the military mission. Access is controlled on the installation and records are kept of those entering
187 and exiting the installation for fishing. Fishermen are required to fill out a survey and creel surveys are
188 conducted on each individual fisherman prior to leaving the facility. Information gathered includes
189 number of people fishing, hours fished, and the number of fish caught. Information from the net
190 sampling and creel surveys is used to set stocking rates.

191 7.2.3.5 Amphibians and Reptiles

192 Though past management guidelines have not addressed reptiles and amphibians specifically, resource
193 managers recognize the importance of including these species in management requirements. Beginning

194 in 2006, all water impoundments on Camp Navajo and a surrounding 1-mile area were surveyed for
195 amphibians and introduced predators, such as crayfish and nonnative fish. Several amphibian and
196 reptile species are found in and near earthen water tanks maintained by installation personnel. Johnson
197 and Quarry Tanks, the Rifle Range Tanks, "L" Tank, and Elsie Springs provide habitat for tiger
198 salamander, treefrog, and midland chorus frog. The western terrestrial garter snake and regal horned
199 lizard also were found around water bodies. The dead and downed woody debris found throughout the
200 forested areas provide habitat for reptiles such as the many-lined skink (TRIES 1996).

201 Management guidelines for the MSO and northern goshawk also ensures sufficient dead and downed
202 woody debris remains throughout forested areas for the benefit of reptiles. The AZARNG will maintain a
203 portion of earthen water tanks on Camp Navajo to manage for amphibians. There are no plans within
204 the next five years for spring development. If it is decided that springs are to be developed, NEPA
205 documentation will be completed addressing affects to amphibians and reptiles. Restoration activities
206 are planned for areas such as Tappen Spring, Pipe springs, Metz Tank, Mickle Tank, and Pyrotechnic
207 Tank. Restoration activities include returning areas and hydrology to natural conditions. Additionally,
208 vegetation control will be limited or avoided around water bodies (see **Appendix J** for general BMPs that
209 will be implemented).

210 7.2.3.6 Pest Species Management

211 The IPMP for the AZARNG outlines the pest species management activities performed by and for the
212 AZARNG (AZARNG 2013b).

213 7.2.3.7 Federally Protected Species

214 To ensure continued habitat conservation and biodiversity for these raptors and compliance with DoD
215 directive, management guidelines from the USFWS and AGFD were reviewed and incorporated into the
216 INRMP. Management recommendations for the bald eagle were compiled from the AGFD document
217 *Conservation Assessment and Strategy for the Bald Eagle in Arizona* (AGFD 2006).

218 7.2.3.7.1 Bald Eagle

219 Wintering bald eagles have been found within Camp Navajo, but no nesting has been observed.
220 Potential bald eagle nesting and wintering sites have been monitored annually for use during winter
221 raptor surveys. The AZARNG, in cooperation with AGFD, reviews potential research projects related to
222 habitat use and nesting activities within Camp Navajo.

223 To ensure that continuing activities on Camp Navajo do not jeopardize bald eagle use of the installation,
224 management guidelines from *Conservation Assessment and Strategy for the Bald Eagle in Arizona* (AGFD
225 2006) will be followed. A summary of the guidelines can be found in the following paragraphs. These
226 include guidelines for:

- 227 • Initiating standardized surveys;
- 228 • Establishing an Integrated Sighting Reporting System;
- 229 • Procedures following discovery of New Breeding Areas (NBAs);
- 230 • Managing NBAs; and
- 231 • Managing winter roosts.

232 **a. Establish Standardized Surveys**

233 The Southwestern Bald Eagle Management Committee (SWBEMC) directs surveys and monitoring of
234 bald eagle nests as well as winter counts of bald eagles. The Camp Navajo NRM has coordinated with
235 SWBEMC to establish standardized winter survey routes within the installation. Wintering bald eagle
236 counts are conducted and coordinated with the statewide effort. Information on eagle numbers, age
237 classes, and habitats discovered on Camp Navajo is recorded and reported to SWBEMC.

238 **b. Guidelines Following Discovery of New Breeding Areas**

239 There are currently no known breeding nests at Camp Navajo. If NBAs or alternate nests are discovered,
240 the following measures to ensure protection of the breeding cycle will be implemented by the NRM:

- 241 1. Contact USFWS biologists to ensure all management requirements are followed.
- 242 2. Notify other primary cooperators (SWBEMC and AGFD) of the discovery.
- 243 3. Enter the location into AGFD's Heritage Data Management System.
- 244 4. Investigate the NBA on the ground to examine potential conflicts with current land use.

245 **c. Management of New Breeding Areas**

246 Three buffer zones will be established around all known nests to protect breeding attempts from
247 adverse effects of human activities. Any activity in these zones will be stopped if a negative impact to a
248 breeding pair becomes apparent. If an NBA is located near existing recreation centers, roads, or
249 occupied buildings, the primary cooperators will modify the following guidelines to best manage the
250 area.

- 251 1. Zone 1 is a 500-foot radius around a nest where breeding eagles are most sensitive to human
252 activity and the greatest degree of protection is needed. During the breeding season (1
253 December to 30 June), no activity will occur in this zone. During the non-breeding season, no
254 landscape-altering activities (e.g., building construction, timber harvesting) will occur. Low
255 impact activities of a short duration (such as fence building) may be permitted.
- 256 2. Zone 2 is a 500- to 1000-foot radius around a nest. During the breeding season, only brief
257 activities (e.g., driving or walking through) will be permitted in this zone. During the non-
258 breeding season, no landscape-altering activities will occur. Low impact activities of a short
259 duration may be permitted. Furthermore, between 15 August and 30 November, maintenance
260 activities (e.g., selective thinning of timber stands or repairs to existing buildings and roads) may
261 be permitted.
- 262 3. Zone 3 is a 1000- to 2,500-foot radius around a nest. In this area, limited activity can occur year-
263 round. During the breeding season, low impact activities of a short duration (e.g., fence building)
264 may be permitted. During the non-breeding season, no landscape-altering activities will occur in
265 this zone. Maintenance activities (such as selective thinning of timber stands or repairs to
266 existing buildings and roads) may be permitted. Most other activities may be permitted during
267 this time, provided they do not directly or permanently impact known bald eagle perching,
268 roosting, or foraging sites.

d. Management of Winter Roosts

269 Management guidelines for wintering habitat are difficult because the species winters statewide. Thus,
270 identification, protection, maintenance, and recruitment of roost trees are essential. Dargan (1991)
271 described the characteristics of winter roost trees in Coconino National Forest as large (mean diameter
272 at breast height of 28.3 inches and 93 feet tall), in loose groups (5- to 40-acre stand size, mature clumps
273 of 5 to 10 trees per acre), on a 5- to 10-percent slope with a 50- to 80-percent canopy closure, and
274 within 1 mile of a food source. Winter roosts have been identified on Camp Navajo and will be protected
275 when possible. Road building will be minimized and activities causing disturbance to roosting bald eagles
276 will be avoided when possible from 15 October to 15 April. Silvicultural treatments to promote growth
277 of large roost trees within this zone will be encouraged.
278

7.2.3.7.2 Migratory and Breeding Birds

280 There is nationwide concern over declining numbers of neotropical bird populations. Many neotropical
281 birds migrate through northern Arizona and are protected under the Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA).
282 The MBTA prohibits illegal take, possession, sale, transport, and shipment of any part of migratory birds
283 or their nest.

284 Incidental taking of migratory birds is regulated in 50 CFR 21, Migratory Bird Permits. Part 21.15,
285 Authorization of Take Incidental to Military Readiness Activities, effective 28 February 2007, allows
286 incidental take by DoD in the course of military readiness activities under certain conditions specified in
287 Paragraph (a) Take Authorization and Monitoring:

288 *“Except to the extent authorization is withdrawn or suspended pursuant to paragraph (b) of this*
289 *section, the Armed Forces may take migratory birds incidental to military readiness activities*
290 *provided that, for those ongoing or proposed activities the Armed Forces determine may result in*
291 *a significant adverse effect on a population of a migratory bird species, the Armed Forces must*
292 *confer and cooperate with the Service to develop and implement appropriate conservation*
293 *measures to minimize or mitigate such significant adverse effects.*

294 *When conservation measures implemented under paragraph (a)(1) of this section require*
295 *monitoring, the Armed Forces must retain records of any monitoring data for five years from the*
296 *date the Armed Forces commence their action. During INRMP reviews, the Armed Forces will also*
297 *report to the Service migratory bird conservation measures implemented and the effectiveness of*
298 *the conservation measures in avoiding, minimizing, or mitigating take of migratory birds.”*

299 It is DoD policy to promote and support a partnership role in protection and conservation of migratory
300 birds and their habitat by protecting vital habitat, enhancing biodiversity, and maintaining healthy and
301 productive natural systems on DoD lands consistent with the military mission. The Partners in Flight (PIF)
302 program is an umbrella network of which DoD's bird conservation program is a vital part. DoD works
303 with the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation to develop cooperative programs and projects with other
304 federal, state, and non-governmental organizations.

305 Several research projects have been conducted on Camp Navajo that helped to identify management
306 guidelines for bird species. Most focused on analyzing the connection of bird species to the ponderosa
307 pine forest ecosystem and the effect of forest treatments on bird species survival in this environment.

308 The results of these projects enable the AZARNG to set management guidelines to protect bird habitat.
309 The NRMs at Camp Navajo have established a working relationship with PIF to further management
310 efforts for birds on the installation. All neotropical migratory bird and winter raptor surveys on Camp
311 Navajo are conducted according to PIF criteria.

312 Winter raptor surveys have been conducted by AZARNG staff from 2010 to the present and will continue
313 on an annual basis. Results from this research will be used to evaluate the effects of on-going and future
314 projects on sensitive raptor species. Overall, Camp Navajo will follow the BMPs for wildlife management
315 detailed in **Appendix J** of this document. Nest surveys and winter raptor surveys will also continue
316 throughout the installation when possible.

317 **7.3 MANAGEMENT OF THREATENED AND ENDANGERED SPECIES AND HABITATS**

318 **7.3.1 Native Plants**

319 The USFWS SC includes two native plants documented within 5 miles of Camp Navajo. None of these
320 species are known to occur on Camp Navajo. The Tusayan flame flower is listed as a SC with the USFWS
321 and as SR under the ANPL. No populations have been found on Camp Navajo, but suitable habitat occurs
322 on the installation. These areas will be identified and surveyed when funding is available. If populations
323 are found, they will be protected from disturbance and monitored.

324 **7.3.2 Threatened and Endangered Species**

325 The AZARNG recognizes that actions included in this INRMP may affect candidate, listed, or other
326 protected species (e.g., migratory birds, bald eagles, and golden eagles). The AZARNG will work with the
327 USFWS prior to implementation of any action that may affect these species or their habitats.

328 7.3.2.1 Mexican Spotted Owl

329 One federally threatened species, the MSO, occurs within Camp Navajo. The AZARNG will continue to
330 consult with both USFWS and AGFD to minimize the impacts of on-going and future actions to this
331 species. Surveys for MSO were conducted in 1997, 1998, 2000 to 2004, and biennially starting in 2006.
332 Camp Navajo has 2,037 acres of designated critical habitat and four PACs contained within the
333 installations. Management guidelines require minimal disturbance within the PAC during the MSO
334 breeding season from 1 March through 31 August. The AZARNG will ensure that management guidelines
335 for critical habitat and PACs established by the USFWS will be followed. The AZARNG will continue to
336 implement the reasonable and prudent measures found in both the 2005 and 2015 BO (**Appendix H**).

337 *7.3.2.1.1 Protected Activity Centers*

338 PACs encompass a minimum of 600 acres surrounding known owl nest/roost sites and include high
339 quality owl habitat. The following outlines some of the measures used by NRM to reduce disturbance
340 near PACs. More detailed and general BMPs for Camp Navajo can be found in **Appendix J**.

- 341 • All activities are coordinated with the USFWS office.
- 342 • No mechanical or prescribed fire treatments occur within PACs or Nest/Roost Core Areas during
343 breeding season unless non-breeding is inferred or confirmed that year per the accepted
344 protocol.

- 345 • Removal of hardwoods, downed woody debris, snags, or other key habitat variables only occur
346 when compatible with owl habitat management objectives and is documented through
347 reasoned analysis.
- 348 • Road or trail maintenance, repair, and building in PACs or Nest/Roost Core Areas will continue
349 to be undertaken during the non-breeding season (1 September to 28 February) to minimize
350 disturbance to owls unless non-breeding is inferred or confirmed or the AZARG demonstrates
351 that noise disturbance using acoustic monitoring is less 90 A-weighted decibels and consults
352 with USFWS.
- 353 • Light burning of surface and low-lying fuels maybe allowed following careful review by biologist
354 and fuel management specialist. These burns will be done during non-breeding season.
- 355 • If mechanical treatments are needed to reduce fire risk to owl nest/roost habitats and may
356 enhance owl habitat the 2012 Recovery Plan will be used to guide those treatments.
- 357 • If a stand-replacing fire occurs within a PAC, timber salvage plans will be evaluated in
358 coordination with USFWS on a case-specific basis.
- 359 • Limit human activity and noise disturbance in PACs and Nest/Roost Core Areas during the
360 breeding season (1 March to 31 August), unless AZARG can demonstrate that noise disturbance
361 using acoustic monitoring is less 90 A-weighted decibels and consult with USFWS.
- 362 • All required permits will be obtained from USFWS for any research projects as well as surveys
363 and monitoring of the PACs and Nest/Roost Core Areas.

364 7.3.2.1.2 *Recovery Habitat*

365 Recovery habitat is primarily ponderosa pine-Gambel oak, mixed-conifer, and riparian forest that either
366 currently is, or has the potential for becoming, nest/roost habitat or does/could provide foraging,
367 dispersal, or wintering habitats.

368 Recovery Nest/Roost Habitat:

- 369 • Areas will continue to be managed for nest/roost replacement habitat.
- 370 • Stands will continue to not be treated in such a way as to lower stand conditions below
371 thresholds in the 2012 Recovery Plan.
- 372 • Prescriptions will continue to be written to retain key owl habitat elements (e.g., large trees,
373 snags, large logs, and hardwoods).

374 Recovery Foraging/Non-breeding Habitat:

- 375 • Emphasize large hardwoods, where appropriate.
- 376 • Retain key owl habitat elements (e.g., large trees, large snags, large logs, and hardwoods).
- 377 • Minimize tree removal.

378 When activities conducted in conformance the above MSO habitat management standards and
379 guidelines may adversely affect other threatened, endangered, or sensitive species or may conflict with
380 other established recovery plans or conservation agreements, the AZARNG will consult with the USFWS
381 to resolve the conflict.

382 Management will be based on ecosystem management following three principles: old growth areas will
383 be maintained, silvicultural practices will favor selection over regeneration cuts, and sustainable
384 conditions will be maintained across the landscape that fall within the natural range of variation
385 **(Appendix E).**

386 **7.4 WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT**

387 The AZARNG complies with applicable federal, state, and local regulations to protect water resources,
388 including wetlands, estuaries, watersheds, and groundwater at Camp Navajo by managing point source
389 and non-point source discharges. The AZARNG takes actions to reduce natural soil erosion and thereby
390 protect nearby water quality. Land-based environmental degradation eventually affects water quality
391 and aquatic ecosystems that are dependent upon good water quality. Because clean water is essential
392 to all living things, maintaining water quality at Camp Navajo is a priority.

393 **7.4.1 Clean Water Act: Section 404**

394 Section 404 of the CWA is administered by the USACE, regulates impacts on navigable waters, and:

395 *“establishes a program to regulate the discharge of dredged and fill material into waters of the*
396 *US, including wetlands. Activities in waters of the US that are regulated under this program*
397 *include fill for development, water resource projects (such as dams and levees), infrastructure*
398 *development (such as highways and airports), and mining projects.” (EPA 2017).*

399 Camp Navajo plans to protect its current water resources whenever possible and feasible.

400 **7.4.2 Wastewater Management**

401 Domestic and pre-treated industrial wastewater generated at Camp Navajo is discharged to a 60,000-
402 gallon-per-day capacity wastewater treatment plant authorized by the State of Arizona Aquifer
403 Protection Permit No. P-101528 and operated by Camp Navajo. Best available demonstrated control
404 technology consists of nitrification/denitrification, clarification, chlorine disinfection, and de-
405 chlorination. Recovered sludge from the treatment process is treated in an aerobic digester and
406 removed for off-site disposal. Treated effluent is discharged from the treatment plant to holding ponds
407 south of plant for evaporation. Effluent in excess of the capacity of the holding ponds can be applied to a
408 permitted re-use site consisting of approximately 25 acres of native species of grass, non-native forage
409 grass (tall fescue), and pine trees. The treatment system is designed such that there is no direct
410 discharge to surface water or groundwater.

411 Discharge is monitored for flow, fecal coliform, total nitrogen, metals, and volatile organic compounds.
412 Groundwater monitoring is not required.

413 **7.4.3 Water Quality Protection**

414 Because water quality reflects environmental pollution, including erosion, maintenance of high-quality
415 water is a goal of this INRMP. To do this, the AZARNG limits damage or alteration to existing or natural
416 drainage patterns, minimize soil erosion, and minimize the potential for unintentional, accidental, or
417 uncontrolled releases. The AZARNG minimizes these threats through the implementation of BMPs and
418 by increasing Soldier environmental awareness.

419 Camp Navajo has a combined aggregate oil storage capacity greater than 1,320 gallons. Because of this,
420 Camp Navajo meets the criteria stipulated in the Title 40 CFR §112 and must prepare and implement a
421 SPCCP. Camp Navajo has identified oil-handling practices and in-situ storage systems, control
422 procedures, and necessary countermeasures to minimize the potential for discharges and to prevent
423 discharges from negatively impacting navigable WOTUS and to surface water bodies. The majority of
424 drainage is surface water run-off to roadside ditches or natural conveyances. Ultimately, this run-off
425 discharges into Volunteer Canyon and flows off-site. The AZARNG has prepared and implements an
426 SPCCP (AZARNG 2019) to respond to unanticipated discharges.

427 **7.4.4 Groundwater**

428 Groundwater is one of Camp Navajo's most valuable natural resources. Camp Navajo was located to
429 take advantage of natural spring discharge from the Wild Bill Hill aquifer. However, the discharge rate is
430 highly variable and has occasionally been insufficient to meet the needs of the installation. The water
431 quality is good, but the shallow aquifer is influenced by surface water and may be vulnerable to
432 pollution.

433 **7.4.5 Water Resources for Wildlife and Plants**

434 Pond 1 will be maintained for fish habitat (Section 7.3.4.4) and is stocked with trout when funding is
435 available. Ponds 2 and 3 will remain closed to fishing and are not be stocked. The AZARNG will work with
436 AGFD to ensure that potential modifications to these and other water sources do not adversely affect
437 wildlife resources on the installation.

438 **7.5 WETLANDS MANAGEMENT**

439 NEPA requires projects to be evaluated for possible environmental impacts and is the primary means by
440 which threats to wetlands on Camp Navajo are identified. The AZARNG contracted the United States
441 Army Engineer Research and Development Center, Waterways Experiment Station to conduct a wetland
442 delineation project on Camp Navajo in 2001 (Mauney et al. 2001). The wetland delineation project was
443 updated in 2015 by SWCA Environmental Consultants (SWCA 2015). The wetlands delineated during the
444 surveys are potential WOTUS and subject to regulatory requirements under Section 404 of the CWA
445 (WES 2001). Projects with the potential to affect a wetland will be in compliance with Section 404 of the
446 CWA. In addition, impacts on wetlands that are not classified as the WOTUS will be avoided whenever
447 possible.

448 **7.6 SOILS**

449 The goal of soil management is to control sources of dust, runoff, silt, and erosion to prevent damage to
450 land and water resources, installation equipment, facilities, and adjacent properties. The AZARNG
451 implements BMPs to control erosion and sediment in Camp Navajo and maintains vegetative cover over
452 all compatible areas. When bare ground is required for accomplishing mission objectives, other soil
453 conservation measures (e.g., check dams, wind breaks, and diversions) are used to control dust, erosion,
454 and sedimentation. To minimize land maintenance expenditures and ensure environmental compliance,
455 physically intensive land-disturbing activities are sited on the least erodible lands (those requiring the
456 least cover for erosion control).

457 Historically, soil erosion has not been a large problem at Camp Navajo, and surveys were completed in
458 2000 (USDA NRCS 2000). In coordination with ITAM and OOD, roads/trails will continue to be

459 maintained with V-ditches and culverts, and vegetation will be maintained at roadway edges to protect
460 soil from erosion.

461 **7.7 FOREST MANAGEMENT**

462 The Camp Navajo Forest Management Plan (**Appendix E**) defines the direction and guidelines for
463 implementation of ecologically based forest and grassland management (**Appendix A, Figure 15**). Forest
464 management is needed to restore forest resiliency and function and achieve the Soldier training and
465 storage mission at Camp Navajo. Resiliency increases the ability of the forest to survive disturbances
466 such as insect, disease, fire, and climate change.

467 The necessity for rigorous and realistic training requires that AZARNG units periodically use large,
468 diverse natural areas, as well as urbanized terrain, for maneuver and range training. Current forest
469 conditions on Camp Navajo are prone to catastrophic wildfires and pose a threat to fulfilling this
470 requirement and to the overall future of Camp Navajo.

471 Research performed at Camp Navajo indicates that prior to European settlement there were
472 approximately 60 trees per acre with a frequent low intensity fire interval. Current data indicates
473 approximately 512 trees per acre exist in forested areas. The overall forest structure and composition on
474 the landscape at Camp Navajo is predominantly dense, homogenous, young to mid-aged forest lacking
475 structural diversity. This described forest structure is at high risk of stand-replacing wildfire (Fulé et al
476 1997). Excess tree density currently limits the availability of suitable bivouac sites, drop zones, landing
477 zones and maneuver areas. There is a need to treat forest vegetation to create a diversity of forest
478 conditions for Soldier training and to reduce the risk of high-intensity crown fire originating from
479 training activities (e.g., smoke grenade use, pyrotechnics, and artillery simulators) and other ignition
480 sources (lightning and other human causes). Forest thinning is needed to develop the footprint of
481 planned bivouac sites, drop zones, and landing zones and to improve conditions for Soldier training.
482 Open areas are needed to provide for maneuver training and dense areas are needed for concealment.

483 ARs for protection and enhancement of the environment require accounting of forest products and
484 completion of commercial harvests before starting any construction activities that may impact forest
485 resources (AR200-1; 4-3; d8 [p]). A detailed schedule of proposed forest and grassland treatments is
486 included in the Camp Navajo Forest Management Plan (**Appendix E**) and in Section 8.2.1 of this INRMP.

487 **7.7.1 Personal Use Firewood Cutting**

488 Current Camp Navajo employees, AZARNG personnel, and all active and retired military are authorized
489 to obtain woodcutting permits from the NRM. Wood offered for sale and cutting includes pine and oak
490 (species that are abundant). Individuals are authorized to cut and remove dead standing and dead and
491 downed trees with certain diameter restrictions. Oak cutting season is generally 1 June to 1 October.
492 Cutting is restricted to designated areas, which are determined by the NRM. No woodcutting will be
493 allowed within the Volunteer Canyon and Volunteer Mountain MSO PAC during the MSO breeding
494 season, though removal of hardwoods, downed woody debris, snags, or other key habitat variables is
495 generally allowed when deemed compatible with owl habitat management objectives and documented
496 through reasoned analysis. Pine cutting season is year-round, from 1 January to 31 December, when
497 weather and road conditions permit. There is a charge per cord for cutting oak (AR200-1). When

498 firewood proceeds are collected, they will be deposited into the federal treasury forestry reimbursable
499 account.

500 **7.8 FIRE MANAGEMENT**

501 Southwestern ponderosa pine forests were historically shaped by frequent, low-intensity surface fires,
502 varying climate cycles, infrequent regeneration pulses, and insect outbreaks. Fire exclusion and grazing
503 activities over the last 120 years have altered the overall structure and composition of ponderosa pine
504 forests in the Flagstaff area. Current conditions include decreased competition from grass species,
505 increased survival of tree seedlings, an invasion of trees into grasslands, and an accumulation of litter on
506 the forest floor. All these changes in forest conditions have compromised the long-term health and
507 integrity of forest resources and significantly increased the potential of stand-replacing crown fires.
508 Crown fires are more likely to burn at higher intensities and cause more ecological damage. As the
509 conditions at Camp Navajo are conducive to these higher damage fire scenarios, the risk for catastrophic
510 impact to operations and natural resources from wildfire is high.

511 **7.8.1 Integrated Wildland Fire Management Plan**

512 The overall plan for fuels reduction and reintroduction of fire at Camp Navajo can be found in **Appendix**
513 **F**. The Integrated Wildland Fire Management Plan (IWFMP) was developed by the AZDEMA FMO EMO.
514 Individual planned fuels reduction and prescribed burning projects are also listed in the Project Matrix
515 (**Appendix G**) and the Camp Navajo Forest Management Plan (**Appendix E**). The IWFMP was developed
516 to reduce wildfire potential, effectively protect and enhance valuable natural resources, integrate
517 applicable state and local permit and reporting requirements, and implement ecosystem management
518 goals and objectives. The IWFMP is reviewed and updated annually and revised at a minimum of once
519 every five years. The IWFMP directly supports installation missions and is consistent with installation
520 emergency operations plans. The IWFMP integrates with this INRMP, and the installation's fire
521 emergency services plan. The IWFMP ensures integration by including organizations having fire
522 responsibility on the installation in its development. The IWFMP coordinates with installation mission
523 operations and other appropriate installation organizations.

524 Camp Navajo is a party to the Ponderosa Fire Advisory Council; parties to the agreement have agreed to
525 provide mutual aid to all other parties. Other signatories to this agreement include the ASLD, Arizona
526 Department of Forest and Fire Management, City of Flagstaff, Highlands Fire District, Mormon Lake Fire
527 District, Pinewood Fire District, Ponderosa Fire District, Sedona Fire District, and Summit Fire District.

528 **7.8.2 Wildfire Prevention and Suppression**

529 The goal of wildfire prevention and suppression is to mitigate fire hazards and control vegetative growth
530 to the degree essential for the safety of the installation and its natural and cultural resources. The
531 AZARNG monitors land use activities within Camp Navajo for fire hazards and adjusts them, including
532 suspending activities, to avoid high hazard areas and/or periods when the fire danger rating is high. The
533 AZARNG also will consider developing a plan to manage naturally occurring fires (e.g., lightning) under
534 specific prescribed natural fire conditions to meet resource objectives (**Appendix F**); however, at this
535 time, no naturally caused wildfires (resource benefit fires) will be treated as prescribed fires and allowed
536 to burn. The AZARNG will consult with USFWS and AGFD personnel prior to implementing changes in fire
537 prevention activities to ensure the protection of sensitive wildlife and their habitats.

538 Fire protection on the installation is focused in three areas that include prevention, preparedness, and
539 suppression. Fire prevention, preparedness, and suppression clauses are included in logging contracts.
540 These clauses give specific instructions on warming fires, smoking, and spark arresters on equipment.

541 The current high risk of active crown fire has necessitated a well-developed wildfire prevention and
542 suppression program (**Appendix F**).

543 7.8.2.1 Prevention

544 Fire prevention not only protects from a loss of natural resources, but also reduces the cost of fire
545 suppression. When possible, installation personnel will remove vegetation, weeds, brush from around
546 buildings, storage igloos, and fence lines to create firebreaks. Slash from thinning or logging operations
547 is removed or piled by the operator and burned by the installation's fire department or contracted
548 agency when conditions are appropriate.

549 Volunteer Canyon and Volunteer Mountain are both prime areas for fire prevention activities. Steep
550 slopes and past protection from fire have created large thickets of oak and various shrubs that are highly
551 prone to fire. Clearing or thinning a portion of the thickets in these areas to improve habitat for turkeys
552 and to reduce fuel loads will occur as resources are made available. Clearing will be done mostly by hand
553 to reduce damage to other natural resources. Where the situation warrants, other means of clearing,
554 such as controlled burns, or mechanical methods will be used. Prior to conducting fire suppression
555 activities on Volunteer Mountain or in Volunteer Canyon, the AZARNG will consult with USFWS to
556 ensure that activities are not likely to adversely affected the MSO or its critical habitat.

557 Both the Kaibab and the Coconino national forests have highly defined fire management plans. Because
558 Camp Navajo is located between the two forests, it is affected by these plans and is working to adopt
559 the preventative measures included within them. The wildfire preventive measures within these plans
560 include:

- 561 • Prescribed burnings when deemed necessary.
- 562 • Outreach programs to educate the public on wildfire prevention.
- 563 • Thinning where possible (mostly removing smaller trees).
- 564 • Facilitate cutting to reduce locust (a highly flammable tree/shrub) spread after prescribed burns
565 and thinning.

566 Five USFS lookout towers have visibility of Camp Navajo. Each lookout tower manned by USFS personnel
567 is capable of seeing smoke on the installation. During fire season, daily air patrols over USFS land
568 adjacent to Camp Navajo are currently conducted by Coconino and Kaibab national forests, while
569 ground patrols are performed by AZDEMA personnel.

570 7.8.2.2 Suppression

571 Fire suppression on Camp Navajo is handled by the installation's Fire Department. There are three
572 causes of fire on Camp Navajo: natural ignitions (e.g., lightning strikes), military activities (detonation of
573 ammunition and firing activities), and non-military activities (campfires, vehicles, hunting, etc.).
574 Although there is not much data recorded, most of the fires in forested areas of the installation have
575 been caused by lightning strikes in snags (standing dead or dying tree). Measures for prevention and
576 quick suppression of wildfire include the following:

- 577 • Forest fuel treatment projects designed to restore forest resiliency;
- 578 • Regulating the net explosive weight used during detonations based on potential fire conditions;
- 579 • Monitoring climatic conditions, so detonation occurs only when humidity levels are high and air
- 580 temperatures are low;
- 581 • Requiring the presence of Fire Department personnel and suppression equipment during
- 582 detonations;
- 583 • Restricting certain operations (e.g., logging, welding, campfires, etc.) during increased fire risk;
- 584 • Requiring an open-flame permit for all campfires and warming fires;
- 585 • Requiring all vehicles entering the ASA to have a fire extinguisher; and
- 586 • Smoking being allowed outside the ASA, but only within vehicles or areas free of combustibles.

587 The Camp Navajo Fire Chief oversees fires that occur on Camp Navajo. The fire station, located within
588 the Cantonment Area, has fire crews available to assist outside agencies in fire suppression. Fire-fighters
589 are cross-trained so they are proficient in fighting structural fires as well as range and forest fires.

590 There were approximately 58 miles of firebreaks in place on Camp Navajo, which occurred primarily
591 along existing roads. These firebreaks have not been maintained in recent years and are not expected to
592 be effective under the current heavy fuel loading (primarily live fuels). There are no current plans to
593 create other fuel breaks, though the current firebreaks are planned to be maintained as long as funding
594 and personnel are available. Forest thinning treatments are needed to reduce fire risk under current fuel
595 loads. If new firing ranges are established, forest thinning will occur around the perimeters. Water for
596 fire suppression is available from the five railroad tanker cars (within the ASA) as well as springs and
597 ponds located throughout Camp Navajo.

598 **7.8.3 Wildland Fire and Proposed Fire Treatment Impacts on Natural Resources**

599 The most significant impact from wildfire on natural resources is the loss of woody vegetation, which
600 consequently affects the diversity of forest conditions for Soldier training, wildlife habitat, and the entire
601 ecosystem. Sensitive species most affected by large-scale, high-intensity wildland fire are the MSO,
602 northern goshawk, bald eagle, and occult little brown bat. Many of the sensitive plants found on Camp
603 Navajo require ponderosa pine or other overstory forest habitat. Loss of vegetation also increases
604 potential for soil erosion.

605 Overall, fire behavior models run in conjunction with proposed treatments as reflected in the Forest
606 Management Plan showed an estimated 88 percent decrease in predicted active crown fire, a 41
607 percent decrease in passive fire, and a 23 percent increase in surface fire (Horncastle et al. 2011).
608 Treatments are expected to reduce the risk of large-scale, high-intensity wildfire and associated adverse
609 effects while maintaining the military mission.

610 **7.8.4 Inventory of Snags**

611 The AZARNG intends to monitor stands for snags on an annual basis and monitor benchmark snags
612 every 3 years. The AZARNG, in cooperation with AGFD, conducted an initial inventory of snags on Camp
613 Navajo in 2007 (Partridge et al. 2007). The purpose of this project was to survey snags within the
614 ponderosa pine forest, identify benchmark snags, and permanently tag a representative sample for long-
615 term monitoring. This inventory provided the AZARNG with baseline information about snag density and

616 age prior to implementing forest management treatments. It will be used to assess decay rates and
617 retention rates over time via its comparison against future monitoring efforts. The monitoring efforts
618 informed by this initial study (planned for 2020 onward) will help the AZARNG assess the effects of
619 forest management treatments on snag recruitment. This information, combined with wildlife surveys,
620 will provide insight to long-term effects that forest management may have on wildlife species in the
621 ponderosa pine community.

622 **7.8.5 Outreach**

623 The IWFMP (**Appendix F**) includes outreach to inform the media and public of wildfire incidents and
624 prescribed burning activities. Activities associated with wildland fire and forest management will be
625 incorporated into the installation and public awareness programs.

626 **7.9 INTEGRATED PEST MANAGEMENT**

627 **7.9.1 Integrated Pest Management Plan**

628 The AZARNG IPMP delineates pest management methodologies available to the NRM at Camp Navajo
629 and details the methods of mechanical, cultural, biological, and chemical controls (AZARNG 2013b). In
630 addition, the BMP of washing vehicle undercarriages to prevent the spread of noxious and invasive
631 weeds (spotted knapweed, scotch thistle, Dalmatian toadflax, field bindweed, and cheatgrass) is
632 mandated in natural resources management operations. Further goals and objectives for the control of
633 noxious weeds and invasive are delineated in Section 8.1.1 *Forest Management Goals and Objectives*.

634 **7.10 OUTDOOR RECREATION**

635 The goal of maintaining public access to Camp Navajo supports natural resources-based recreation and
636 education while maintaining military readiness. The AZARNG allows sustainable public use of Camp
637 Navajo's natural resources to the extent that the use does not conflict with the requirements necessary
638 to ensure safety and military security and is not inconsistent with the needs of wildlife resources.
639 Outdoor recreation can contribute to quality of life for the surrounding community. The ability of the
640 land to support natural resources-based recreation is sufficient and has remained relatively unchanged
641 in recent years.

642 **7.10.1 Military Mission Considerations**

643 The military mission has priority over outdoor recreation. The United States Army has been training
644 Soldiers for over a century while providing quality recreational opportunities for Soldiers, their families,
645 employees, and the general public. The AZARNG has determined that there is no conflict between these
646 goals at Camp Navajo.

647 **7.10.2 Public Access**

648 Since Camp Navajo stores munitions and missiles, the security requirements are very high. High levels of
649 security and explosive site safety requirements limit the amount of public access that can be provided
650 without impacting the military mission. DoD Directive 4715.03, *Natural Resource Conservation Program*,
651 18 March 2011, states,

652 *"The principal purpose of DoD lands and waters is to support mission-related activities. Those*
653 *lands and waters shall be made available to the public for educational or recreational use of*

654 *natural and cultural resources when such access is compatible with military mission activities,*
655 *ecosystem sustainability, and other considerations such as security, safety, and fiscal soundness.*
656 *Opportunities for such access shall be equitably and impartially allocated.”*

657 Paragraph 4-3 of AR 200-1, *Land Resources*, states that the United States Army will

658 *“Provide for controlled recreational access where feasible at Army installations containing land*
659 *and water areas suitable for recreational use. (LD: 16 USC 670a).”*

660 This regulation further states that hunting, fishing, and trapping plans will be included in the INRMP for
661 installations that have such programs. The public is allowed access to the Camp Navajo buffer areas if
662 they have received MEC Awareness training and possess a Camp Navajo hunting license or woodcutting
663 permit.

664 **7.10.3 Camping**

665 Camping is well regulated and has little to no effect on Camp Navajo resources. Current and retired
666 AZARNG members, Camp Navajo employees, as well as their dependents and guests are allowed to
667 camp on the installation in the Tappen Springs area or the RV park (**Appendix A, Figure 2**). Civilians are
668 allowed to camp within the RV park within the Cantonment Area (**Appendix A, Figure 2**) if they have a
669 valid hunting permit. No open fires are allowed; fires require a permit from the installation Fire
670 Department and must be contained in designated fire pits. Smoking must be done in a vehicle or area
671 free of combustible materials. Outdoor cooking must be done on a grill. Campers are prohibited from
672 dumping untreated wastewater (gray water and black water) on the ground at Camp Navajo. Traveling
673 in the buffer area at night is prohibited. Parties wishing to use the installation for camping must check in
674 daily with Camp Navajo Security and/or the campground host. With these restrictions in place and
675 enforced, adverse impacts to natural resources are mitigated.

676 **7.10.4 Off-Highway Vehicles**

677 Vehicles commonly used as off-highway vehicles (OHVs) that have a four-wheel chassis and are licensed
678 may be used on Camp Navajo for hunting. Vehicle operators shall remain on designated trails and roads,
679 with the only exception being to recover harvested game. This exception applies only when the
680 operation can ensure that the vehicle will not damage archeological sites or a wetland area.

681 **7.11 ENFORCEMENT**

682 **7.11.1 History and Authority**

683 The AZARNG employs security personnel who serve Camp Navajo 24 hours a day. Security personnel
684 have military authority only. Non-military incidents are handled by the appropriate agency—AGFD,
685 Coconino County Sheriff, or the Arizona Department of Public Safety. Security personnel are involved in
686 natural resources protection, have the authority to deal with wildlife law enforcement, and have
687 received the appropriate training. They collect recreation information by performing game checks, creel
688 surveys, and hunter interviews. AGFD has the responsibility for enforcing and administering State of
689 Arizona Fish and Wildlife laws and regulations at Camp Navajo.

690 7.11.2 Jurisdiction

691 Camp Navajo is under concurrent jurisdiction. Natural resources laws on the installation can be enforced
692 by officers with federal or state commissions, but wildlife enforcement is the responsibility of AGFD.
693 Citations written by AGFD are adjudicated by the State of Arizona court system. AZARNG members and
694 employees observing suspicious hunting activities are encouraged to call the Operation Game Thief
695 hotline at 1-800-352-0700 and/or report it to Camp Navajo Security.

696 7.11.3 Enforcement Problem Areas

697 Nationwide, hunting and fishing programs require the most enforcement within natural resource
698 programs. Camp Navajo permits hunting and fishing as outdoor recreational activities; these activities
699 require enforcement personnel oversight. Though these restrictions are in place, some users access the
700 installation illegally. Such entry can be the precursor to illegal activities at Camp Navajo. Most of these
701 illegal activities either directly or indirectly impact efforts to protect natural resources. Illegal entry into
702 the installation is sometimes difficult to prevent, as limited manpower makes it difficult for the
703 boundary of Camp Navajo to be patrolled. Camp Navajo is currently fenced, but the fence is susceptible
704 to vandalism. Damage to the fence provides easy access to Camp Navajo's buffer area. The current
705 fence along Camp Navajo's boundary is a four-strand fence, with barbed wire as the three upper strands
706 and smooth wire as the lower strand.

707 7.11.3.1 Poaching

708 Arizona state hunting licenses are issued by AGFD. Hunters wishing to hunt on Camp Navajo must also
709 obtain a Camp Navajo-specific permit and are subject to additional restrictions (including where hunting
710 can occur and what weapons can be used). Hunters must check in with Security before and after
711 hunting. Security ensures that everyone entering the installation has permission and that hunters leave
712 the installation daily or are camping or staying in on-site billeting. Security is responsible for checking
713 that wildlife kills are properly tagged. Illegal kills that are discovered are turned over to AGFD for
714 prosecution.

715 7.11.4 Natural Resources Enforcement

716 The current enforcement system is responsive to the protection of natural and cultural resources at
717 Camp Navajo. The current system appears to be fully capable of continuing the same standard of
718 enforcement for Camp Navajo.

719 7.11.5 Enforcement of Fish and Wildlife Laws

720 USFWS has the responsibility to enforce federal fish and wildlife laws and regulations. AGFD has the
721 responsibility to enforce state fish and wildlife laws and regulations. AGFD manages the fish and wildlife
722 resources for the State of Arizona through hunting and fishing permits. These responsibilities include the
723 hunting program at Camp Navajo.

724 7.12 CULTURAL RESOURCE PROTECTION**725 7.12.1 Cultural Resource Management**

726 Cultural resources on Camp Navajo are managed and protected through historic preservation laws,
727 regulations, and other provisions including but not limited to the National Historic Preservation Act
728 (NHPA), the American Indian Religious Freedom Act, the Archaeological Resources Protection Act, the

729 Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA), and AR 200-4 Cultural Resource
730 Management.

731 **7.12.2 Consultation**

732 The AZARNG consults with SHPO to determine eligibility of sites for listing on the NRHP and Arizona
733 Register of Historic Places in accordance with the NHPA of 1966 and its implementing regulations (as
734 amended 36 CFR PART 800). In accordance with the NHPA and the Annotated DoD American Indian and
735 Alaska Native Policy, the AZARNG also consults with federally recognized Tribes whose traditional
736 territories may have overlapped Camp Navajo, including the Pueblo of Zuni, Navajo Nation, Yavapai-
737 Apache Nation, Hualapai Tribe, Hopi Tribe, Havasupai Tribe, Fort Mojave Indian Tribe, the Fort
738 McDowell Yavapai Nation and San Carlos Apache.

739 **7.12.3 Regulations**

740 The AZARNG is working to update the Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan and agreements
741 with SHPO and interested Tribes. These agreements will address protection of these archaeological
742 resources and management of all cultural resources within Camp Navajo. The procedure for inadvertent
743 discovery will follow 36 CFR 880.12 and Interim Procedure Plan until the Programmatic Agreement is in
744 place (**Appendix K**).

745 **7.12.4 Human Remains**

746 Any human remains and associated funerary objects that exceed 50 years in age discovered on Camp
747 Navajo are protected NAGPRA (25 USC 3002 (d) and NAGPRA regulations (43 CFR 10). If Native American
748 remains or funerary objects are identified during project activities, work in the immediate area will be
749 halted and AZARNG shall take all reasonable steps necessary for the protection of the remains and
750 objects.

751 **7.12.5 Section 106**

752 All requirements under Section 106 of the NHPA will be followed for all natural resources management
753 activities, including all ground disturbing activities associated with forest management (such as
754 harvesting activities), habitat management (e.g., physical soil preparation for food plots and over
755 plantings), pond and wetland construction, cantonment area management, soil surveys, land
756 rehabilitation, and maintenance (e.g., terrain modification for erosion control and restoration). AZARNG
757 will continue to follow its Interim Procedure Plan (Section 7.12.6) regarding Section 106 compliance until
758 the Programmatic Agreement is finalized (Appendix K).

759 **7.12.6 Interim Procedures Plan**

760 The AZARNG CR Program Manager receives notification of pending of Federal Undertakings activities.
761 The AZARNG CR program manager reviews and/or sends to AZARNG CR contractors for review. This
762 review includes a Class I cultural resources inventory to assess whether the Area of Potential Effect
763 (APE) has been subject to previous Class III cultural resources inventory, and whether any known
764 cultural resources are present within the APE.

- 765 • If the APE HAS been subject to previous Class III inventory that meets current Arizona State
766 Museum (ASM) and SHPO standards and NO cultural resources are present within 30 meters of the

767 APE, then the AZARNG CR program manager and/or the CR contractors shall prepare a SHPO
768 Survey Report Summary Form (SRSF) with the results of the Class I inventory.

769 • If the APE HAS been subject to previous Class III inventory that meets current ASM and
770 SHPO standards and NRHP-eligible or unevaluated cultural resources are present, then the AZARNG
771 CR program manager will work with AZARNG commanders to revise the training effort, if possible,
772 to avoid NRHP-eligible and unevaluated cultural resources.

773 ○ In order to ensure avoidance, the AZARNG CR program manager and/or CR contractor
774 may mark the site boundaries for avoidance. Additionally, monitoring may be conducted
775 to ensure either the avoidance or minimization of any adverse effects. In most cases,
776 monitoring shall be done during implementation of the training exercise; however, there
777 could be instances due to timing, safety, and/or security when monitoring during training
778 implementation is not possible. In these cases, the AZARNG CR Manager and/or CR
779 contractor shall conduct post-training implementation monitoring. Either a memo report
780 or full technical cultural resources monitoring report of all monitoring efforts and results
781 shall be prepared as appropriate.

782 • If the APE HAS NOT been subject to previous inventory or the previous inventory is deemed to
783 not meet current standards, then if time permits, the AZARNG CR Manager and/or CR contractors
784 will conduct a Class II or Class III inventory of the APE as appropriate in order to identify and
785 evaluate historic properties.

786 ○ If NO cultural resource sites, structures, buildings, or districts are identified during the
787 Class III inventory, then an SRSF shall be prepared.

788 ○ If cultural resource sites, structures, buildings, or districts are identified, then a Class III
789 cultural resources inventory technical report shall be prepared to ASM and
790 SHPO standards.

791 ○ If cultural resources that the AZARNG CR Program Manager determines that cultural
792 resources that are ELIGIBLE for listing in the NRHP and/or cultural resources of
793 indeterminate NRHP-eligibility are identified during the Class II or Class III survey, then the
794 AZARNG CR Program Manager and/or CR contractor may mark the site boundaries for
795 avoidance and/or conduct monitoring to ensure either the avoidance or minimization of
796 any adverse effects. Monitoring and subsequent reporting shall be implemented as
797 described above.

798 • Due to the sensitivity and necessary timeframes of the anticipated AZARNG training efforts,
799 there may be occasions when the completion of a Class II or Class III inventory of the APE is not
800 feasible prior to training implementation. In these cases, the AZARNG CR Program Manager and/or
801 CR contractors shall conduct monitoring either during the training activities or conduct a post-
802 training inspection to assess any effects of the training on cultural resources. Subsequent reports of
803 these monitoring and post-training assessment activities shall be prepared as described above.

804 • The AZARNG shall submit all reports described above to SHPO and other consulting parties for
805 review and comment. Every effort shall be made to provide SHPO and other consulting parties a
806 30-day review and comment period; however, given the national security nature of these training

807 efforts, the AZARNG recognizes that there will be cases when providing consulting parties with a
808 full 30-day review period is not feasible. In these cases, the reports that shall document the efforts
809 taken by the AZARNG to comply with Section 106 of the NHPA.

810 **7.12.6 Natural Resources Management Implications for Cultural Resources**

811 Natural resources management on Camp Navajo has potential to affect cultural resources, especially
812 with respect to traditional cultural properties and resource uses. Natural resources practices with
813 potential to adversely affect cultural resources are outlined below.

- 814 • Prescribed burning: Prescribed fire has some potential to affect archeological sites by denuding
815 areas of vegetation and promoting erosion. Fire has greater potential to adversely impact
816 historic archeological sites with significant surface features. Generally, prescribed burns would
817 have positive effects for historic properties management if burning schedules can be
818 coordinated to assist in archaeological inventory.
- 819 • Forest Management: Proposed forest treatments using mechanical thinning methods have the
820 potential to affect archeological sites through ground disturbance.
- 821 • Firebreak maintenance: Maintenance of firebreaks involves significant ground disturbance that
822 can damage archeological sites and promote erosion. However, without firebreaks, the potential
823 impacts from a large-scale wildfire and subsequent erosion would be much greater.
- 824 • Outdoor recreation programs: Public access associated with hunting, fishing, woodcutting and
825 outdoor recreation activities has limited potential to increase the risk of vandalism to
826 archeological sites.

827 Even with proper review, natural resources projects still have some potential to affect archeological
828 sites through accidental discovery. Natural resources management can be used to protect and sustain
829 historic properties, traditional cultural properties, and sacred sites. AZARNG will implement this INRMP
830 in a manner consistent with the protection of historic properties on Camp Navajo.

831 **7.13 PUBLIC OUTREACH**

832 **7.13.1 Conservation Education**

833 The AZARNG coordinates environmental issues with government agencies, private organizations, and
834 the public. Conservation education provides a means to develop and distribute materials related to the
835 sound environmental stewardship of AZARNG natural resources. Conservation education efforts involve
836 and inform troops and the public in natural resources stewardship efforts.

837 **7.13.2 Hunter Education**

838 Hunters on Camp Navajo must attend an installation orientation/safety briefing prior to hunting and
839 must possess an Arizona Hunter Education card, National Rifle Association card, or the equivalent. The
840 installation orientation/safety briefing covers the regulations particular to the installation (such as the
841 locations of restricted areas), meets the requirements of MEC and cultural resources awareness training,
842 describes required check-in procedures, and conveys restrictions related to OHV and weapons use. This
843 required briefing provides an excellent opportunity for Camp Navajo to provide hunters and other
844 recreational users with natural and cultural resources information and general environmental
845 awareness. Camp Navajo incorporates natural resource awareness information into these briefings.

846 7.13.3 Youth Groups

847 Natural resources personnel have cultivated a conservation ethic in local youth in the past and will
848 continue this effort. On occasion, personnel have given talks about natural resources to youth groups
849 such as the Boy Scouts of America. Because work with youth groups is an investment in the future,
850 Camp Navajo's natural resources personnel will continue to work with these groups whenever possible.

851 7.13.4 Other Conservation Education Opportunities

852 Because of the secure nature of Camp Navajo, interpretive trails throughout the installation are not
853 feasible. However, Camp Navajo does maintain a Congressional Medal of Honor Park in the Cantonment
854 Area. This park contains 21 different species of trees that are each associated with a Congressional
855 Medal of Honor recipient. At the base of each tree is a plaque with information on the recipient as well
856 as the tree species. This park will be maintained. Other potential conservation education opportunities
857 are being developed such as interpretive centers at Indian Village and Prisoner of War Camp on Camp
858 Navajo as well as participation in events or presentations throughout the local community.

859 7.13.5 Best Management Practices

860 Camp Navajo implements a variety of BMPs, developed from those described in the United States
861 Department of Agriculture's (USDA's) Four Forest Restoration Initiative management plans, the
862 installation's SPCC and Hazardous Waste Management Plan to help manage its resources. The BMPs
863 (adapted from the USDA's Four Forest Restoration Initiative's management plan) followed by Camp
864 Navajo to best implement its soil, water, wildlife, cultural, and fire management can be found in
865 **Appendix J.**

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40 **GOAL 2:** Control noxious weeds and invasive species.

41 **OBJECTIVE 2A:** Reduce and prevent the spread of non-native species.

42 **OBJECTIVE 2B:** Monitor invasive species and noxious weeds.

43 **GOAL 3:** Sustain or improve current conditions of the training site.

44 **OBJECTIVE 3A:** Provide designated areas for sustainable military training operations that maintain
45 ecosystem integrity.

46 **8.2 GRASSLAND AND MEADOW MANAGEMENT**

47 Grasslands, mountain meadows, and wet meadows are found on Camp Navajo. These areas are
48 important to sustain military training; provide forage for deer, elk, and pronghorn; provide movement
49 corridors for pronghorn; and provide habitat for many species of birds and small mammals.

50 **8.2.1 Grassland and Meadow Management Goals and Objectives**

51 **GOAL 4:** Restore resiliency and function to grassland and meadow habitats.

52 **OBJECTIVE 4A:** Restore historic grassland conditions.

53 **OBJECTIVE 4B:** Increase ground cover and native diversity to reduce and prevent non-native
54 species from establishing and to protect from soil erosion.

55 **OBJECTIVE 4C:** Restore meadows to natural conditions (**Appendix A, Figure 16**).

56 **8.3 WATER RESOURCES**

57 The AZARNG will comply with applicable federal, state, and local regulations to protect water resources,
58 including wetlands.

59 **8.3.1 Water Resources Goals and Objectives**

60 **GOAL 5:** Maintain water quality and sustain wetland and riparian in functional condition.

61 **OBJECTIVE 5A:** Maintain and enhance earthen water tanks for wildlife away from major training
62 areas and ranges.

63 **OBJECTIVE 5B:** Identify and protect ephemeral streams from disturbance.

64 **OBJECTIVE 5C:** Manage and maintain ecosystem function of wetlands.

65 **OBJECTIVE 5D:** Restore springs to natural conditions.

66 **8.4 SOIL MANAGEMENT**

67 Soils will be managed on Camp Navajo in order to decrease and/or prevent erosion and the
68 contamination of groundwater.

69 **8.4.1 Soil Management Goals and Objectives**

70 **GOAL 6:** Protect soils to prevent erosion and to maintain realistic training ground for missions.

71 **OBJECTIVE 6A:** Reduce the footprint and impact of hardened sites.

72 **OBJECTIVE 6B:** Protect ecologically sensitive areas.

73 **OBJECTIVE 6C:** Improve roads and trails.

74 **8.5 SPECIAL STATUS PLANT AND WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT MEASURES**

75 In addition to the aforementioned measures listed under forest, meadow, grassland, and water resource
76 management, there are additional measures needed to protect special status plant and animal species.
77 The aforementioned goals and objectives help lay out the process to protect various ecosystems needed
78 for said wildlife populations, the following are more specific research and management needs to ensure
79 the viability of species within the ecosystems. The AZARNG protects native plants within Camp Navajo
80 by compliance with ANPL and ESA.

81 **8.5.1 Special Status Plant and Wildlife Management Goals and Objectives**

82 **GOAL 7:** Protect native plants.

83 **OBJECTIVE 7A:** Maintain native plant diversity through the management of sensitive habitats.

84 **GOAL 8:** Manage MSO PACs and recovery habitat.

85 **OBJECTIVE 8A:** Implement the Recovery Plan for the MSO.

86 **OBJECTIVE 8B:** Continue to follow conservation measures from existing 2005 and 2015 BOs
87 **(Appendix H).**

88 **GOAL 9:** Manage bald eagle populations.

89 **OBJECTIVE 9A:** Continue to follow bald eagle mitigation from existing 2005 and 2015 BOs
90 **(Appendix H).**

91 **GOAL 10:** Manage northern goshawk.

92 **OBJECTIVE 10A:** Survey and monitor northern goshawk populations.

93 **GOAL 11:** Monitor and study passerine and raptor species.

94 **OBJECTIVE 11A:** Monitor and study passerine and raptor populations.

95 **GOAL 12:** Manage small mammal populations.

96 **OBJECTIVE 12A:** Monitor and study bat populations.

97 **OBJECTIVE 12B:** Monitor Gunnison's prairie dog populations.

98 **8.6 GAME MANAGEMENT**

99 Game species are managed by analyzing scientific data to determine hunting quotas, maintain healthy
100 populations and environments, and improve those that have become degraded. The AZARNG and AGFD
101 will meet annually to discuss changes to the hunting program on Camp Navajo.

102 **8.6.1 Game Management Goals and Objectives**

103 **GOAL 13:** Manage big game species (elk, pronghorn, deer, and Merriam's turkey).

104 **OBJECTIVE 13A:** Protect important big game habitat features located away from major training
105 areas.

106 **OBJECTIVE 13B:** Ensure viable species populations.

107 **8.7 PEST SPECIES MANAGEMENT**

108 Pest management at Camp Navajo is implemented according to the goals and objectives detailed in the
109 AZARNG IPMP. The criteria and measurements for success of this goal are detailed in the AZARNG IPMP
110 (AZARNG 2013b).

111 **8.8 WILDLAND FIRE MANAGEMENT**

112 Camp Navajo lands will be managed proactively to reduce wildland fire potential. Wildland fires will be
113 managed on Camp Navajo in order to maintain training lands and protect and enhance valuable natural
114 resources.

115 **8.8.1 Wildland Fire Management Goals and Objectives**

116 **GOAL 14:** Manage wildland fires to sustain Camp Navajo training lands.

117 **OBJECTIVE 14A:** Implement the IWFMP (**Appendix F**) for Camp Navajo to reduce wildfire
118 potential, effectively protect and enhance valuable natural resources, integrate applicable state
119 and local permit and reporting requirements, and implement ecosystem management goals and
120 objectives.

121 **8.9 ENFORCEMENT MANAGEMENT**

122 The goal of the enforcement program is to manage for an efficient response to an incident by the
123 appropriate authority (security personnel, MPs, AGFD, Coconino County Sheriff, or Department of Public
124 Safety).

125 **8.9.1 Enforcement Management Goals and Objectives**

126 **GOAL 15:** Enforce wildlife and natural resource laws to best manage, maintain, and protect resources.

127 **OBJECTIVE 15A:** Enforce wildlife and natural resource laws and state and federal regulations.

128 **8.10 CULTURAL RESOURCE PROTECTION**

129 The goal is to protect cultural resources during INRMP related actions, including recreational activities.

130 **GOAL 16:** Protect cultural resources during INRMP related actions

131 **OBJECTIVE 16A:** Implement cultural resource survey and monitoring requirements for INRMP-
132 related actions.

133 **OBJECTIVE 16B:** Develop a plan for determining the limits of acceptable change for recreational
134 and natural resources.

135 **8.10.1 Public Outreach**

136 The goal of public outreach is to continue to implement proactive programs involving government
137 agencies, private organizations, and the public.

138 8.10.1.1 Public Outreach Goals and Objectives

139 **GOAL 17:** Educate Soldiers and the public as to how their activities impact the environment and their
140 responsibilities as stewards of the environment.

141 **OBJECTIVE 17A:** Educate Soldiers and the public on environmental issues.

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SECTION 9 IMPLEMENTATION

The AZARNG depends on natural resources for the sustainability of many training programs and will manage natural resources to ensure sustainable use. The INRMP is not intended to impair the ability of the AZARNG to perform its mission. However, the INRMP does identify usage restrictions on sensitive attributes such as wetlands and threatened and endangered species.

Implementation of this INRMP will be realized through the accomplishment of specific goals and objectives as measured by the completion of projects described within this INRMP. In accordance with the 25 May 2006 *Army Guidance for Implementation of the SAIA*, an INRMP is considered implemented if an installation:

- Actively requests, receives, and uses funds for “must fund” projects and activities required to meet recurring natural resources conservation management requirements or current natural resources compliance needs;
- Ensures that sufficient numbers of professionally trained natural resources management staff are available to perform the tasks required by the INRMP;
- Coordinates annually with cooperating agencies; and
- Documents specific INRMP action accomplishments undertaken each year.

9.1 PROJECT MATRIX AND FUNDING

Appendix G, the project matrix for Camp Navajo, is used to develop budget requests and schedule annual project requirements. Funding requests are submitted in accordance with current NGB procedures for conservation projects.

9.1.1 Funding Sources

Implementation of this INRMP is subject to the availability of annual funding. The installation requests project validation and funding through Status Tool for the Environmental Program (STEP), completed by the EPM. Funding sources for projects can be grouped into three main categories by source: federal NGB funds, other federal funds, and non-federal funds. Each is discussed in the following subsections.

Where projects identified in the plan are not implemented due to lack of funding or other compelling circumstances, the installation will review the goals and objectives of this INRMP to determine whether adjustments are necessary. The following discussion of funding options is not all-inclusive of funding sources. Since many funding sources rely on a variety of grant programs, award criteria and amounts can change considerably from one year to another. Funding through grant programs can occur on a one-time award, annually, or multi-year.

9.1.1.1 National Guard and Arizona Army National Guard Funding

Funding from the NGB/AZARNG will be required to implement the INRMP over the next 5 years. NGB is the primary source of funding to support the management of natural resources at Camp Navajo through a Master Cooperative Agreement with the State of Arizona. Only projects approved in STEP receive funding. This budget is managed by the EPM.

The NGB provides funding for facilities maintenance in support of the AZARNG CFMO. The CFMO is involved in planning, scheduling, and oversight of maintenance of roads and trails, vegetation

39 management, pest management implementation, facilities infrastructure, construction, and master
40 planning, all of which impact, and are impacted by, the natural resources management program.

41 9.1.1.2 Other Federal Funds

42 Cooperative agreements may be entered into with states, local governments, non-governmental
43 organizations, and individuals for the improvement of natural resources or to benefit natural and
44 historical research on federally owned training sites. Upon written concurrence of the Camp Navajo
45 INRMP by the USFWS and AGFD, these agencies become signatory cooperators of this plan. As such, the
46 potential for access to matching funds programs and services offered by these agencies will be available.

47 Program initiatives under the CWA provide funding through several sources. The EPA Office of Water
48 sponsors those projects related to the CWA. Available funding may support programs such as cost-
49 sharing for overall water-quality management (e.g., monitoring, permitting, and enforcement), lake
50 water quality assessments and mitigation measures, and implementation of non-point source pollution
51 control measures. Refer to the EPA's Office of Water funding website for potential sources of funding
52 ([https://www.epa.gov/
53 cwsrf/learn-about-clean-water-state-revolving-fund-cwsrf#assistance](https://www.epa.gov/cwsrf/learn-about-clean-water-state-revolving-fund-cwsrf#assistance)).

54 The Legacy Resource Management Program provides financial assistance to DoD efforts to conserve
55 natural and cultural resources on federal lands. Legacy projects could include regional ecosystem
56 management initiatives, habitat preservation efforts, archeological investigations, invasive species
57 control, and/or flora or fauna surveys. Legacy funds are awarded based on national visibility. Project
58 proposals are submitted directly to the Legacy Resource Management Program
59 (<https://www.dodlegacy.org/legacy/intro/about.aspx>).

60 The NRCS manages the Federal Domestic Assistance Program (Plant Materials for Conservation) that
61 assembles, evaluates, selects, releases, and introduces into commerce and promotes the use of new,
62 improved plant materials for soil, water, and related resource conservation and environmental
63 improvement programs ([https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/wps/
64 portal/nrcs/main/national/programs](https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/wps/portal/nrcs/main/national/programs)).

65 9.1.1.3 Non-Federal Funds

66 Other funding sources that could be considered include the Public Lands Day Program, which
67 coordinates volunteers to improve the public lands they use for recreation, education, and enjoyment,
68 and the National Environmental Education and Training Foundation, which manages, coordinates, and
69 generates financial support for the program.

70 **9.1.2 Priorities and Scheduling**

71 The STEP database will be used to validate projects and determine funding priority. Projects need to be
72 funded consistent with timely execution to meet future deadlines. Projects are generally prioritized with
73 respect to compliance. Highest priority projects are projects related to recurring or current compliance,
74 and these are generally scheduled earliest.

75 Recurring requirements include projects and activities needed to cover the recurring administrative,
76 personnel, and other costs necessary to meet applicable compliance requirements (federal and state
77 laws, regulations, Executive Orders [EOs], and DoD policies) or which are in direct support of the military

78 mission. Recurring costs include manpower, training, supplies; hazardous waste disposal; operating
79 recycling activities; permits and fees; testing, monitoring and/or sampling and analysis; reporting and
80 record keeping; maintenance of environmental conservation equipment; and compliance self-
81 assessments.

82 Current compliance includes projects and activities that are needed because an installation is currently
83 or will be out of compliance if the determined projects or activities are not implemented in the current
84 program year. Examples include:

- 85 • Environmental analyses, monitoring, and studies required to assess and mitigate potential
86 effects of the military mission on conservation resources;
- 87 • Planning documents;
- 88 • Baseline inventories and surveys of natural and cultural resources (historical and archaeological
89 sites);
- 90 • Biological assessments, surveys, or habitat protection for a specific special status species;
- 91 • Mitigation to meet existing regulatory permit conditions or written agreements;
- 92 • Wetland delineations in support of subsequent jurisdictional determinations and consequent
93 permitting;
- 94 • Efforts to achieve compliance with requirements that have deadlines that have already passed;
95 and
- 96 • Initial documenting and cataloging of archaeological materials.

97 Maintenance requirements include those projects and activities needed that are not currently out of
98 compliance but shall be out of compliance if projects or activities are not implemented in time to meet
99 an established deadline beyond the current program year. Examples include:

- 100 • Compliance with future requirements that have deadlines;
- 101 • Conservation and GIS mapping to be in compliance;
- 102 • Efforts undertaken in accordance with non-deadline specific compliance requirements of
103 leadership initiatives;
- 104 • Wetlands enhancement, in order to achieve the EO for “no net loss” or to achieve enhancement
105 of existing degraded wetlands; and
- 106 • Public education programs that educate the public on the importance of protecting
107 archaeological and natural resources.

108 Lower priority projects include those that enhance conservation resources of the installation mission, or
109 those that are needed to address overall environmental goals and objectives but are not specifically
110 required under regulation or EO and are not of an immediate nature. These projects are generally
111 funded after those of higher priority are funded. Examples include:

- 112 • Community outreach activities, such as “Earth Day” and “Historic Preservation Week” activities;
- 113 • Educational and public awareness projects, such as interpretive displays, oral histories, nature
114 trails, wildlife checklists, and conservation teaching materials;
- 115 • Biological assessments, surveys, or habitat protection for a species;

- 116 • Restoration or enhancement of cultural or natural resources when no specific compliance
117 requirement dictates a course or timing of action;
- 118 • Reinternment of Native American remains on DoD-managed or controlled land; and
- 119 • Management and execution of volunteer and partnership programs.

120 **9.1.3 Staffing**

121 The Camp Navajo Natural Resources Office is staffed with NRMs who are employed by the AZDEMA and
122 supervised by the Conservation Programs manager.

123 **9.1.4 Personnel Training**

124 The Wildlife Society, National Military Fish and Wildlife Association, Society of American Foresters,
125 Society for Ecological Restoration, and the Society of Range Management are among the professional
126 societies applicable to meeting the needs of Camp Navajo's NRMs. Membership in these societies is
127 encouraged, as they provide some of the best scientific publications in their professions. Attending the
128 meetings of these societies provides excellent opportunities to communicate with fellow professionals,
129 as well as maintain professional standards. The AZARNG natural and cultural resources staff will send
130 personnel to each ARNG approved course, such as:

- 131 • National Environmental Workshop;
- 132 • SRP workshop;
- 133 • NEPA courses; and
- 134 • GIS training.

135 Other conferences/workshops will be evaluated for their usefulness and decisions to send personnel will
136 be made based on the appropriateness to on-going projects and funding availability by the EPM.
137 Especially useful options include National Military Fish and Wildlife Association workshops, the North
138 American Natural Resources Conference, the United States Army SRP workshop, GIS and GPS
139 workshops, environmental communications, conferences on forest management, NGB
140 courses/conferences, and PIF workshops.

141 **9.1.5 Outside Assistance**

142 Implementation of this INRMP will require limited assistance from INRMP partners. A list of
143 partnerships, cooperating agencies, and other interested parties are presented in Section 2.3.

144 **9.2 INRMP REVIEWS**

145 **9.2.1 Review for Operation and Effect**

146 The INRMP will be reviewed for operation and effect to determine if the INRMP is being implemented to
147 meet the requirements of the SAIA and contributing to the conservation and rehabilitation of natural
148 resources at Camp Navajo, no less than every five years (Sikes Act SEC. 101. 16 USC 670a (b) (2)). The
149 review will be conducted by the three cooperating parties to include the commander responsible for the
150 INRMP, USFWS, and AGFD. These agencies have technical representatives who will complete the review.

151 The review for operation and effect will either conclude that the INRMP is meeting the intent of the
152 SAIA and it can be updated and implementation can continue or that it is not effective in meeting the

153 intent of the SAIA to conserve natural resources while providing for no net loss in training capability and
154 it must be revised. The conclusion of the review will be documented in a jointly executed memorandum,
155 meeting minutes, or in some other way that reflects mutual agreement. If only minor updates are
156 needed, they will be done in a manner agreed to by all parties. The updated INRMP will be reviewed by
157 the local USFWS office, USFWS regional director, local AGFD office, and AGFD director. Once
158 concurrence letters or signatures are received from USFWS regional director and the AGFD director, the
159 INRMP will continue to be implemented. A new NEPA review is not necessary for an update and the
160 continued implementation of an existing INRMP that has previously undergone NEPA review. In this
161 case, an Environmental Checklist and Record of Environmental Consideration citing the previous NEPA
162 document is needed.

163 If a review of operation and effect concludes that an INRMP must be revised, there is no set time to
164 complete the revision. The existing INRMP remains in effect until the revision is complete and USFWS
165 and AGFD concurrence on the INRMP is received. The AZARNG will endeavor to complete such revisions
166 within 18 months depending upon funding availability. Revisions to the INRMP will go through a more
167 detailed review process similar to development of the initial INRMP to ensure AZARNG military mission,
168 USFWS, and AGFD concerns are adequately addressed and the plan meets the intention of the SAIA.
169 Revisions will usually require a new NEPA analysis. An EA will be completed as part of the revision
170 process, if determined by NGB to be necessary.

171 **9.2.2 Annual Agency Reviews and Coordination**

172 Per DoD policy, the AZARNG will review the INRMP annually in cooperation with the USFWS and AGFD.
173 On an annual basis the AZARNG will invite the USFWS Regional Office, the USFWS local field office, the
174 AGFD, and NGB to attend a meeting at Camp Navajo to review previous year INRMP implementation
175 and discuss implementation of upcoming programs and projects. Invitations will either be by letter or
176 email. Attendance is at the option of those invited, but at minimum the USFWS local field office and
177 AGFD are expected to attend. The meeting will be documented with an agenda, meeting minutes, and
178 sign-in roster of attendees.

179 The need for updates or revisions will be discussed at the annual meeting. If minor updates are needed,
180 the requesting party will initiate the updates, and after agreement of all three parties, they will be
181 added to the INRMP. If it is determined that major changes are needed, all three parties will provide
182 input and an INRMP revision and associated NEPA review will be initiated with the AZARNG acting as the
183 lead coordinating agency. The annual meeting will be used to help expedite the more formal review for
184 operation and effect. If all parties agree and document their mutual agreement, the requirement to
185 review the INRMP for operation and effect will have been fulfilled.

186 If not already determined in previous annual meetings, by the fourth year of annual reviews a
187 determination will be jointly made to continue implementation of the existing INRMP with minor
188 updates or to proceed with a revision. If the parties believe that the annual reviews have not been
189 sufficient to evaluate operation and effect and they cannot determine if the INRMP implementation
190 should continue or be revised, a formal review for operation and effect will be initiated. The
191 determination on how to proceed with INRMP implementation or revision will be made after the parties
192 have had time to complete this review. In accordance with the *Army Guidance for Implementation of the*
193 *SAIA* dated 25 May 2006, annual reviews shall at minimum verify that:

- 194 • All “must fund” projects and activities have been budgeted for and implementation is on
195 schedule;
- 196 • All required trained natural resources positions are filled or are in the process of being filled;
- 197 • Projects and activities for the upcoming year have been identified and included in the INRMP
198 (an updated project list does not necessitate revising the INRMP);
- 199 • All required coordination has occurred;
- 200 • All significant changes to the installation’s mission requirements or its natural resources have
201 been identified;
- 202 • The INRMP goals and objectives are still valid; and
- 203 • No net loss of training capability has occurred due to implementation of the INRMP in
204 accordance with the SAIA.

205 As part of the annual review, the AZARNG will specifically:

- 206 • Invite feedback from the USFWS and AGFD on the effectiveness of the INRMP;
- 207 • Inform the USFWS and AGFD which INRMP projects and activities are required to meet current
208 natural resource compliance needs; and
- 209 • Document specific INRMP action accomplishments from the previous year.

210 Information for the annual reviews comes from the AZARNG environmental staff, Camp Navajo military
211 leadership, cooperating agencies, project files, and Army Environmental Database-Environmental
212 Quality as applicable. Natural resource data and program and project information are available to
213 cooperating agencies. They may request to see project folders or to have a site visit to view natural
214 resources projects in progress at any time. Annual review results will be available to the public and can
215 be requested through the EMO at Camp Navajo.

216 **9.2.3 Tribal Reviews and Coordination**

217 As the AZARNG intends to maintain regular and consistent consultation with affiliated Tribes, the
218 AZARNG has endeavored to confirm which types of projects they are interested in participating in
219 through consultation. The AZARNG’s installations contain an abundance of prehistoric archaeological
220 sites, historic structures, and modern buildings. Prior to the start of any AZARNG project, a thorough
221 Class I background search is conducted to identify which types of sites, if any, are located in the project
222 area, within 250 meters of the project area, and within 1 mile of the project area. Frequent project
223 categories include military training exercises; maintenance of modern and historic buildings such as
224 latrine modernizations and roof replacements; the installation of fire suppression systems; utility repair
225 and replacement such as maintenance on water and sewer lines; road and trail maintenance;
226 remediation activities to mitigate or monitor past environmental damage; and forest management
227 including timber sales, tree thinning, and prescribed burns.

228 Tribes may be interested in consulting upon the following categories:

- 229 • Any project taking place near known prehistoric archaeological sites;
- 230 • Any project taking place inside or near historical-period structures;
- 231 • Any project taking place inside or near modern, non-historical-period structures;

- 232 • Any project involving ground disturbance;
- 233 • Only projects involving ground disturbance near known prehistoric archaeological sites; and
- 234 • Any project, even those not involving ground disturbance and not near any known prehistoric
- 235 archaeological site.

236 Until directed otherwise, the AZARNG will send consultation correspondence for every upcoming project

237 according to the instructions currently posted online on the government-to-government website.

238 **9.3 MONITORING INRMP IMPLEMENTATION**

239 Monitoring of INRMP implementation is necessary to facilitate the legal requirements of the SAIA to

240 review for operation and effect. This section lists the implementation requirements given in the *DA*

241 *Guidance for Implementation of the SAIA*, dated 25 May 2006. An INRMP is considered implemented in

242 regard to the SAIA if the requirements in the Army guidance are met. These SAIA implementation

243 criteria do not necessarily measure the effectiveness of an INRMP in facilitating mission accomplishment

244 while conserving natural resources. Camp Navajo INRMP implementation will be monitored for meeting

245 the legal requirements of the SAIA as well as for other mission and biological measures of effectiveness.

246 The ultimate successful implementation of this INRMP is realized in no net loss in the capability of Camp

247 Navajo training lands to support the military mission while at the same time conserving and

248 rehabilitating natural resources found on the training site.

249 Much of the INRMP implementation is done through internal coordination in regard to training site

250 operations and land use decision-making. This type of implementation cannot be measured by project

251 implementation or funding but is evidenced by such things as the ability to continually train, sustainable

252 land use, on-going regulatory compliance, retention of species diversity, retention of surface water

253 quality, and the acknowledgement of sustainable natural resources management by partnering

254 conservation agencies and other interested organizations and individuals. In order to monitor and

255 evaluate the effectiveness of the INRMP implementation, the following will be reviewed as applicable

256 and discussed within the context of the annual review and/or a formal review of operation and effect:

- 257 • Impacts to/from the military mission;
- 258 • Conservation program budget;
- 259 • Staff requirements;
- 260 • Program and project implementation;
- 261 • Trends in species and habitat diversity as evidenced by recurring biological surveys, land use
- 262 changes, and opinions of NRMs;
- 263 • Compliance with regulatory requirements; and
- 264 • Feedback from military trainers, the USFWS, the AGFD, and other stakeholders.

265 Some of these areas may not be looked at every year due to lack of data or pertinent information. The

266 effectiveness of the INRMP as a mission-enabling conservation tool will be decided by mutual

267 agreement of the USFWS, AGFD, and AZARNG during annual reviews and/or reviews for operation and

268 effect.

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CAMP NAVAJO FOREST MANAGEMENT PLAN

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CAMP NAVAJO PROJECT MATRIX

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**APPENDIX I
ANNUAL UPDATE FORM**

ANNUAL REVIEW AND COORDINATION OF THE CAMP NAVAJO INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PLAN, BELLEMONT, ARIZONA

The annual review will be conducted by in October Environmental Management System staff and FMO staff. Annual review will include feedback from USFWS, USFS, AGFD, and ASLD personnel as appropriate. The review shall consider operation and effect of the INRMP at Camp Navajo.

REVIEWED BY:

**The Adjutant General
Arizona Army National Guard**

_____ **Date**

**Environmental Program Manager
Arizona Army National Guard**

_____ **Date**

**Field Supervisor,
Arizona Ecological Services
United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Region 2**

_____ **Date**

**Flagstaff Regional Supervisor
Arizona Game and Fish Department**

_____ **Date**

APPENDIX J
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